

UNIVERSITY OF APPLIED SCIENCE RHEINMAIN
FRANKFURT UNIVERSITY OF APPLIED SCIENCE

MASTER THESIS

Consideration of Initial Embodied Energy for Building Envelopes in Façade Engineering

Author:

Pouya ASHDGE-MAHDAVI

Student number: 1194225

Hindenburgstraße 52,

55118 Mainz

First supervisor:

Prof. Dr.-Ing.

Daniel PFANNER

Second supervisor:

Prof. Dr.-Ing.

Christoph GEGNAGEL

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Engineering Science**

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Declaration of Authorship

I, **Pouya Mahdavi**, declare that this thesis titled, “Consideration of Initial Embodied Energy for Building Envelopes in Façade Engineering” and the work presented in it are my own. I confirm that:

- This work was done wholly or mainly while in candidature for a research degree at this University.
- Where any part of this thesis has previously been submitted for a degree or any other qualification at this University or any other institution, this has been clearly stated.
- Where I have consulted the published work of others, this is always clearly attributed.
- Where I have quoted from the work of others, the source is always given. With the exception of such quotations, this thesis is entirely my own work.
- I have acknowledged all main sources of help.
- Where the thesis is based on work done by myself jointly with others, I have made clear exactly what was done by others and what I have contributed myself.

Signed:

Date:

“If we knew what it was we were doing, it would not be called research, would it?”

Albert Einstein

“Have the courage to follow your heart and intuition. They somehow already know what you truly want to become.”

Steve Jobs

UNIVERSITY OF APPLIED SCIENCE RHEINMAIN
FRANKFURT UNIVERSITY OF APPLIED SCIENCE

Abstract

Architectural and Civil Engineering
Engineering Science

Master of Engineering
“Konstruktiver Ingenieurbau/Baumanagement”

Consideration of Initial Embodied Energy for Building Envelopes in Façade Engineering

by Pouya ASHDGE-MAHDAVI

Long before Sir Nicholas Stern¹ described climate change as the greatest market failure that the world has ever known, the great economist John Kenneth Galbraith² warned against conventional wisdom and the ‘tendency to associate truth with convenience, with what most closely accords with self-interest and personal well-being or promises best to avoid awkward effort’. It turns out his warning would be swift to demonstrate its accuracy. Few now doubt that climate change is the greatest threat that we have ever faced and that we must use every ‘weapon in our armoury’ in order to defeat it. With that in mind, having a precise measurement of the environmental performance of materials and buildings is crucial. One important discovery is that, over time, building codes have been improved. Because of this, the emissions from operational energy (HVAC) compared to the emissions embodied in building materials have been optimised. Historically, the OE assumed a dominating role, traditionally accounting for some 80–90% of total emissions. However, more recent studies have concluded that particularly when buildings with low energy consumption are evaluated, such as in low-energy or passive-house designs, the share of embodied emissions from materials is considerable. Highly insulated building envelopes have become more commonplace as environmental imperatives require a reduction in the building of carbon footprints. Whilst increased insulation levels reduce OE demand, the additional embodied energy investment can increase a building’s overall environmental impact. The embodied energy consideration can determine whether, and to what extent, additional insulation is justifiable.

This thesis starts by offering a basic definition of *sustainability* and how it has altered since its first introduction. It then provides a concise philosophy of one of the most common tools for assessing the environmental impacts, which is *Life Cycle Assessment*. After that, this study dedicates itself to the main subject of *Embodied Energy*, especially *Initial Embodied Energy*, which is known as the sum of all energy embedded in products and processes used in constructing a building. In order to be able to reduce the used amount of EE in a building, the EE should be calculated and considered in the early stages of designing and construction planning.

The integration of the calculated IEE with the newest conventional planning tools for building envelopes is the core focus of this thesis. This research does not dive into the best way, which is to calculate the IEE, but rather it takes the available data inventory and assigns to façade components. The final applicable result is an implementation which can help façade planners to acknowledge the IEE.

¹British economist and academic.

²Also known as Ken Galbraith, was a Canadian-American economist, diplomat, public official and intellectual.

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List of Abbreviations

ADP	Abiotic Depletion Potential
AIA	American Institute of Architects
AP	Acidification Potential of soil and water
BIM	Building Information Modeling
CBA	Cost Benefit Analysis
CED	Cumulative Energy Demand
CF	Carbon Footprint
c-PCR	complementary Product Category Rules
CRED	Center for Research on the Epidemiology of Disasters
DE	Demolition Energy
EE	Embodied Energy
EEC	Embodied Energy Coefficient
EIA	Environmental Impact Assessment
EISF	Exterior Insulation Façade System
EoL	End of Life
EP	Eutrophication Potential
EPD	Environmental Product Declaration
EPI	Environmental Pressure Indicators
ES	Environmental Sustainability
ESI	Environmental Sustainability Index
ESL	Estimated Service Life
EWI	Ecosystem Wellbeing Index
GDP	Gross Domestic Product
GHG	Greenhouse Gas
GPI	General Progress Indicator
GWP	Global Warming Potential
HDI	Human Development Index
HWI	Human Wellbeing Index
IEE	Initial Embodied Energy
IPCC	Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change
ISEW	Index of Sustainable Economic Welfare
LBD	Literature Based Discovery
LCA	Life Cycle Assessment
LCEA	Life Cycle Energy Assessment
LCI	Life Cycle Inventory analysis
LCIA	Life Cycle Impact Assessment
MFA	Material Flow Analysis
MGE	Main Gate East
MIPS	Material Input per unit of Service
NIBS	National Institute of Building Science
NNP	Net National Product
nZEB	net Zero Energy Building
ODP	Depletion Potential of the stratospheric Ozone layer

OE	Operational Energy
OECD	Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development
PCR	Product Category Rule
PEF	Product Environmental Footprint
PEF	Primary Energy Factor
POCP	Photochemical Ozone Creation Potential
REE	Recurrent Embodied Energy
RSL	Reference Service Life
SEA	Strategic Environmental Assessment
SETAC	Society of Environmental Toxicology And Chemistry
SFA	Substance Flow Analysis
SIA	Sustainability Impact Assessment
SNI	Sustainable National Income
UNCSD	United Nations on Sustainable Development
UNDP	United Nations Development Programme
USBEA	U. S. Bureau of Economic Analysis
USCB	United States Census Bureau
WBCSD	World Business Council for Sustainable Development
WCED	World Commission on Environment and Development
WMO	World Meteorologic Organization

Physical Constants

Speed of Light $c_0 = 2.99792458 \times 10^8 \text{ m s}^{-1}$ (exact)
Age of Earth $y = 4.543 \times 10^9$ years (a)

List of Symbols

<i>a</i>	annum	a
<i>E</i>	energy	MJ or (kWh)

*Dedicated to 'Rumi'
and countless scientists and unnoticed activists around the
globe working to fight global warming and climate change.*

Chapter 1

Building Envelope

1.1 Introduction to Façade Development

The Cambridge Dictionary describes a façade as being the front of a building, especially a large or attractive structure. In civil engineering science, the notion of ‘façade’ is defined as ‘the visible envelope of a building’. Originally the concept façade was adapted from the Latin expression ‘facies’ meaning face, appearance, or shape. Thus, the term façade became the recognised global term for the building envelope or outer skin of a building (Gütegemeinschaft Fenster, 2017). Façades are not limited to the actual space they occupy as part of the entire structure, but instead influence the space in and around the building. A façade is the key element when observing the exterior of a building and has an impact on the interior. View, lighting, ventilation, user comfort, some building services, and possibly load-bearing are all tasks which the façade may need to address. Façades are an integral element of the entire building, relating directly to design, use, structure, and building services. This has a decisive impact on the whole design and construction process (Knaack et al., 2014).

Designing a façade is a process of communication and decision-making that focuses on the overall formulation of the building. The following steps can be recognised as specific phases:

- Initial conception
- Definition of functionalities
- Design
- Implementation
- Coordination and Assembly

Certain processes should occur during all of these phases, including:

- Feedback on overall design
- Definition of functionalities
- The element’s importance within the overall structure of the building (structure, building services engineering, usage, safety)

1.1.1 Façade planning engineering

Façade planning is an integral part of the design process that employs constant feedback. It is a process based on progressive steps. [Table 1.1](#) and [Table 1.2](#) describe the development of today’s façades and their typological classification.

TABLE 1.1: Typologically assigned façades due to their functionalities.
Mostly adapted from (Knaack et al., 2014).

Type	Elucidation
Solid wall construction	Solid wall constructed from monolithic or composite elements. Often, the masonry is plastered.
Warm façade	Warm façades have a thermal insulation layer applied directly to the surface of the building. If the insulating layer is applied on the outside, it also has to be water-resistant to ensure that the insulating properties are not lost due to weathering. If the insulating layer is on the inside, the ability of the solid wall to store heat will no longer actively influence the interior environment.
Cold façade	Cold façades are characterised by the presence of a cavity, ventilated internally, between the outer layer that offers protection against the weather and the thermal insulation layer. Potential condensate can escape via the cavity.
Openings in solid wall construction	Openings in a solid wall allow fresh air and light access to a building.
Closing apertures—single glazing	Single glazing was used in apertures to provide natural lighting, to allow views out from inside the building and vice versa, and to prevent heat loss from the building. Various techniques were developed to join initially available small panes of glass so that larger openings could be filled.
Box window	A box window is produced when a second pane of glass is installed to meet seasonal conditions. Depending on the temperature, the user can decide how many panes should be opened.
Insulated glazing	Two panes of glass permanently joined together to give insulated or double glazing a more effective barrier between the internal and external environments.
Walls with skeletal structure	Tent-like structures emerged through the need to move one's home frequently from one place to another as is inherent in the nomadic way of life. These structures were designed for ease of assembly and dismantling, which made it necessary to separate the functions of support and enclosure from each other.
Half-timbered construction	In a half-timbered construction, the load-bearing capacity is provided by the skeletal structure while the infill in the intermediate spaces merely has an enclosing function. The overhanging of successive storeys is clearly visible.
Balloon framing	A balloon frame consists of posts one storey high which offer cladding on the inside and the outside. In contrast to platform frames, balloon frames have the ceiling/floor unit built into the wall.
Post-and-beam façade	Post-and-beam façades consist of storey-high vertical posts linked by horizontal beams. The spaces between these members house the appropriate functions.

TABLE 1.2: Typologically assigned façades continued from Table 1.1.
Mostly adapted from (Knaack et al., 2014).

Type	Elucidation
Post façade	The storey-high posts lead wind loads and the self-weight of the structure to the ground.
Beam façade	Façade constructions in which only beams are used require a vertical suspension system to bear the weight of the façade. Wind loads are here transferred to the ground via the beams.
Curtain wall	Unlike pure post-and-beam systems, curtain walls are suspended from above with the aid of tie rods. This approach has the advantages of avoiding buckling in the posts and of providing a large degree of independence from the main structure of the building.
System façade	System façades, unlike post-and-beam systems, can be fully prefabricated and mounted on site by a small labour force.
Double façades	A double façade is obtained by adding an extra layer of glazing outside the façade to provide the building with ventilation or additional sound-proofing. This system may be realised in various ways, depending on the functions desired and the requirements made of the façade.
Second-skin façade	A second-skin façade is produced by adding an external layer of glass to the inner façade. This has the advantage of being easy to construct but the disadvantages of limited control possibilities on the interior and, in the case of high buildings, the attendant risk of overheating.
Box-window façade	Storey-high box windows with ventilation flaps at top and bottom offer the possibility of individual control.
Corridor façade	Corridor façades connect neighbouring double-façade elements in order to permit staggered ventilation of the space between the two skins.
Shaft-box façade	Shaft-box façades, featuring box windows that release their exhaust air into a shaft that extends over several floors, offer a double façade system that requires complex installation but is highly effective.
Alternating façade	In alternating façades, a second skin is added locally to a single-skin façade construction to provide the benefits of the buffering effect of the double façade in the areas affected. A grating can be mounted in front of the single-skin areas to allow for ventilation during rain and at night-time regardless of weather conditions.
Integrated façade	The integrated façade incorporates not only ventilation functions but also active environmental-control or lighting components.

FIGURE 1.1: Clustering of the building envelopes. Adapted from (Gütegemeinschaft Fenster, 2017).

1.1.2 Criterion for differentiation of façades

Coming from the aforementioned global definition, different types of facade constructions have developed over the past century. A first rough subdivision of load-bearing and non-load-bearing facades can be established. In addition, the structure as a single-skin or multi-skin construction can serve as a differentiation. Another criterion for differentiation is the transparency of facades. Based on this rough clustering, a narrowing down of the products due to their assembly characterisation is depicted in [Figure 1.1](#).

1.2 Principles of Construction

The façade separates the interior from the exterior. In addition to addressing today's façade construction development in [section 1.1](#) the different functions that a façade serves could be summarised as:

- Defining the architectural appearance of the building
- Providing views to the inside and outside
- Absorbing push and pull forces from wind loads
- Bearing its self-weight as well as that of other building components

The façade also allows sunlight to penetrate into the building while usually providing protection from the sun at the same time. It resists the penetration of rainwater and has to handle humidity from inside and outside. The façade provides insulation against heat, cold and noise and can facilitate energy generation. In addition, it must be long-lasting, easy to maintain and simple to clean (see [Figure 1.2](#)).

1.3 Principles of Structure

The main structural elements of a façade can be defined as follows (see [Figure 1.3](#)):

- Primary structure (shell of building) forming the main load-bearing structure of the building.

FIGURE 1.2: Conventional requirements of a façade (Knaack et al., 2014). However, nowadays other requirements such as environmental aspects, burglary prevention, fire resistance, and more can be considered. These requirements need to be addressed during all phases of the facade construction: during the conceptual phase, while working on the principles of construction, during detailing, and lastly during construction and usage.

FIGURE 1.3: Simplified representation of the elements of façade construction. Principally all facade constructions are based on this simplified design; however, different functional requirements can be combined into one component. Adapted from (Knaack et al., 2014).

- Secondary structure, which is the load-bearing structure for the façade and constitutes the connecting element between levels one and three.
- Infill elements.

The primary purpose of this assembly presents a simplified structural model that should fulfil the requirements mentioned in [Figure 1.2](#). The functions are distributed among several different components. This arrangement simplifies the connection of individual façade components with each other and provides options to compensate for movement due to wind as well as thermal expansion.

The primary structure takes on the load-bearing function of the entire building and transfers the loads from the façade to the foundation.

The secondary structure comprises the load-bearing structure of the façade. It transfers its loads onto the primary structure. At this ‘interface to the interior’ the different movements of the shell of the building and the façade need to be balanced. Additionally, these two structures are typically assigned to different subcontractors. As these elements are manufactured by different companies, there is a need for special coordination at these interfaces. Manufacturers’ tolerances of the shell of the building (concrete) lie within the centimetre range where the façade (metal) colour is only

deviations of millimetres.

At the same time infill elements such as glazing, panels, etc. are mounted on the secondary structure. This 'interface to the exterior' has to fulfill certain functions: the elements have to be windproof, they must resist water penetration (or must rechannel water to the exterior), movements between the elements and the secondary structure have to be tolerated and thermal bridges have to be avoided. Thus the secondary structure is a very complex component.

In conclusion, there are numerous structural systems available for façade construction. The decision for a specific system depends on the following factors (Knaack et al., 2014):

- Type of primary structure or shell of building.
- Load transfer from the exterior towards the interior.
- The size and properties of the infill elements (glass dimensions, deflections, weight, etc.).
- Architectural design.

1.4 Environmental Footprints of a Façade

The construction of a façade is a process that begins with the architectural concept and ends with the assembly of the final product. However, this is not a linear process but rather depends on regular feedback arising from complex decision making and communication processes (see [Figure 1.4](#)).

No matter if the façade is a post-beam-façade or a curtain wall, a consideration of the environmental footprint of the building envelopes has not always been a conventional part of decision-making.

Instead, as the construction industry develops and new regulations and demands arise either from the standards organisation or from the clients who wish to consider the environmental aspects of their design, there is an urgent need to develop new concepts to consider these innovative requirements in the planning process.

Additionally, not only is the consideration of environmental footprint significant in itself, it is also crucial to find the most straightforward way of integrating it into the modelling steps.

FIGURE 1.4: Designing a façade is not a linear process but rather depends on regular feedback, adapted from (Knaack et al., 2014). In the conventional design process, there is no effort at all to contemplate the environmental footprints of a design. This way of design-thinking could not be tolerated nowadays when climate change is one of the critical issues that we face.

Chapter 2

Introduction to Sustainability

2.1 Initiative

As humankind strives for more comfort and financial independence, urban areas are densified, there are strong increases in traffic and electrosmog¹ grows due to new communication technologies. Combined, these consequences lead to ever-increasing burdens in the immediate environment of each individual. Quality of life is limited and health is weighed down. Reinforced by the prevalence of news about global climate change, a gradual rethinking in society is emerging (Bauer, Mösle, and Schwarz, 2013).

Ultimately, the economic damage caused by climate change must be borne by society. The years 1990-2000 saw a significant increase in environmental catastrophes, 40% higher than the destructions occurring between 1950-1990 (see [Figure 2.1](#)). This situation has not yet improved but, rather, has worsened. [Figure 2.2](#) shows the different disaster types and the frequencies of their occurrences from 2009 until 2018. Between 2009–2018 the annual average of climatic disasters was 343, increasing to 396 in 2019. Without the introduction of effective measures, this expected damage is unlikely to be limited. The distressing climax of this development was certainly the nuclear catastrophe in Fukushima in Japan in 2011, an event which even prompted politicians in Germany to make a U-turn away from nuclear and towards a renewable energy supply. Companies across all economic sectors are now recognising that only the responsible use of resources will lead to long-term success. Sustainable solutions (to be discussed in [section 2.2](#)) that conserve resources and protect the environment are therefore being increasingly valued over solutions that are only superficially economic (Bauer, Mösle, and Schwarz, 2013).

In addition to the social and economic framework conditions, the move towards sustainability has been favoured by the sharp rise in energy prices in recent years. The price of oil has more than doubled since 1970 (putting aside the extrema), with an annual increase of 25% between 2004 and 2006. However, a plentiful oil supply set against a backdrop of continued weak oil demand is mainly responsible for the observed drop in prices in the last six years (see [Figure 2.3](#)). However, the decrease of the crude oil price does not justify the fact that this type of energy supply is not renewable and, more importantly sustainable. Taking into account today's energy prices and crude oil ending resource, price increases and energy-saving measures are therefore indispensable. Another reason to support a conscious use of energy is the strong dependence on energy imports. In the European Union, for example, more than 60% of the primary energy required has to be imported, and the trend is rising

¹Refers to all artificially generated electromagnetic fields in the environment and the resulting permanent exposure of people and the environment to them. Source: www.vivobase.de.

FIGURE 2.1: The number of weather-related disasters. Dark blue: others, light blue: flooding and yellow: storm (Bauer, Möhle, and Schwarz, 2013).

FIGURE 2.2: Occurrence by disaster type: 2019 compared to 2009–2018 annual average (Research on the Epidemiology of Disasters, 2020).

FIGURE 2.3: The price of the crude oil and its development since 1950 until 2020, source: www.google.com.

in EU. The dependence unsettles consumers and the energy policy of the countries is therefore questioned. With the energy turnaround, Germany has now set an example and wants to reverse its dependency. Since nothing works without energy, many investors and operators are focusing on new technologies and resources in order to become more independent of global developments.

But in a world in which we are connected globally, no country can individually withstand the consequences of climate change. Around the world, there is talk of the pursuit of a more the *sustainable* future. So, with this in mind, *what does sustainability mean?*

2.2 What is Sustainability?

In April 2010, a report of the Secretary General of the UN² Assembly stated:

“the environment and development are not two separate agendas, but two faces of the same agenda. Development is the midwife of sustainability, just as sustainability is the life support system for development. At its advent over two decades ago, this idea offered tremendous excitement and hope. The time has come not only to review and assess what has been achieved on the basis of this vision, but also to build upon it and revive its promise of integration, unity and aspiration.”

The necessity to review, assess, build upon and revive the concept of sustainability guided the development of this chapter. Sustainability began as a promising inspirational, and hope-filled worldwide endeavour yet has developed into a buzzword, often with little more behind it than rhetoric. The idea of creating a more sustainable future for ourselves and our children through sustainable development has been widely embraced, but it is unclear whether we all have the same understanding as to what it is that we are embracing, at what cost, and under what circumstances. It cannot confidently be asserted that sustainability is universally understood.

Beyond the confusion of what is meant by sustainability, the concept has been widely abused too. As a guiding principle, sustainability has been co-opted by numerous actors who, rather than use the concept to make transformational changes that improve environmental, social, and economic systems, have instead made the term fit their own agendas which frequently have little to do with change or transformation. From the building organisations who are in charge of issuing *Green Building Certifications* to other environmental politicians who blindly support these misguided concepts rather than scrutinise the scientific facts behind them, the focus has always been on certification beneficiary, not the environment. This business-as-usual default mode has meant that the global endeavour to employ sustainability as a development maxim is failing to close the gap between implementation and the scope of the problem. That being said, some progress has been made. More parties are discussing sustainability today, and many are implementing programmes and projects that they hope will contribute to sustainable development goals. Yet the kinds of programmes, the types of actions and the degree of change are not sufficient to guarantee a more sustainable future (M. Farley and A. Smith, 2020).

²United Nations.

In Germany, the word sustainability was first used in forestry. A pioneer in this field was Hans Carl von Carlowitz with his book “*Sylvicultura Oeconomica*”, which was published 1713 in Leipzig (Carlowitz, 2000). Carlowitz was no forester, but in his position as Superintendent of the Saxon Silver Mines he needed large quantities of timber and found that the German forests were in very bad conditions. Forestry had been a lifelong interest and so he conceived the principle of ‘sustainable forestry’, which proposed that only as much wood as would regenerate should be logged. He had already perceived interconnections between environmental factors and economic and social interests (as we would formulate today). Even if the book with its, baroque language and gothic printing is not easy to read, the message is nevertheless clear and quite relevant for today’s sustainability discussion. The German word ‘nachhaltig’ was even translated into the French ‘soutenu’³ ultimately developing into the English term ‘sustainable’ (Grober, 2010).

Sustainability has been defined as the level of human consumption and activity which can continue into the foreseeable future, so that the systems which provide goods and services to humans persist indefinitely (WCED, 1987; National Research Council, 1999). The practical implications of this definition are diverse, ranging from the consumption of resources with respect to their rate of renewal, the efficiency of resource use, and the equity of their use across societies and generations, with different emphases according to discipline and political ideology (L. Mayer, 2008; Ulgiati and MT. Brown, 1998; T. Parris and R. Kates, 2003). Ultimately, sustainability should not be defined as a tool to improve human welfare by protecting the sources of raw materials, but as a conscious understanding that without nature we cannot survive. So, humanity must learn to live in harmony with the biophysical environment.

In order to make the sustainability concept implementable, recent sustainability research has become more quantitative and includes more dimensions of sustainability simultaneously [Figure 2.4](#), which will allow for more targeted policies to be implemented and their successes tracked more closely (L. Mayer, 2008).

To date, this idea has been associated with the global development policy defined in the WCED report (WCED, 1987) from which the following lines are often quoted:

“Sustainable development is development that meets the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs.”

This statement addresses the worldwide responsibility of humans living today to future generations. This ambitious goal was rapidly included within a political discussion: in 1992, the United Nations in Rio de Janeiro declared sustainability as being the guiding principle for the twenty-first century, which was confirmed 10 years later at the succeeding conference in Johannesburg. The relation to the entire lifecycle of products, lifecycle thinking, was already recognised as an important principle. Beyond political declarations of intent the necessity for a quantification and operationalisation of sustainability remains untouched. This is addressed, for example, by a statement of the Advisory Board for Sustainability in Germany concerning indicators for the national sustainability strategy (Rates für Nachhaltige Entwicklung, 2008). It was stressed that sustainability without quantified goals threatens to evolve into

³Now mainly: durable.

FIGURE 2.4: The trajectory of a system, and the position of the system with respect to multidimensional sustainable boundaries, are both necessary to determine system sustainability. A system which is unsustainable in one dimension is not generally sustainable. Multiple indicators are measured for each dimension, and aggregated into an index which identifies the overall position and trajectory of the system (H. et al., 2003).

an empty concept. In addition, the Advisory Board's definition of sustainability emphasised the global claim:

"Sustainable development is the creation of economic and social development by means of preservation of natural fundamentals of life and an achievement of economic and social welfare for present and future generations – for us and globally."

2.3 Main Characteristics of Sustainability

Quantitative sustainability analysis currently employs a variety of methodological foundations. Hicksian income from economics and lifecycles, as well as material flows from industrial ecology (Jelinski et al., 1992; Ehrenfeld, 2004), provide perspectives that emphasise the human–component of sustainable socioeconomic structures. Since its broad range of models may recognise crucial feedback through seemingly different dimensions of a system, a foundation focused on complex systems and catastrophe theory enhances the research's applicability to every system, regardless of form or scale. Ecosystems, factories, and countries all have numerous modes of feedback and nonlinear relationships among their constituents. When systems are overwhelmed by a disruption, these interactions and means of feedback may result in long periods of relative stasis, punctuated by very rapid changes to new conditions or 'regimes' (Thom, 1994; SR. Carpenter, 2003). Three key characteristics define the long-term viability of human environmental systems: resistance to natural and anthropogenic disruptions, desirability to human societies, and (often implicit) temporal and spatial scale boundaries. Policy goals are determined by resilience and desirability, and the size stipulates the structure that must be controlled and managed to achieve those goals (L. Mayer, 2008).

The definitions of sustainability given in [section 2.2](#) are not directly useful for the purpose of (mostly comparative) product assessments. The standard model,

FIGURE 2.5: Natural basis of life is the prerequisite for sustainable development.

which is also accepted by industry, is called *the triple bottom line*,⁴ an interpretation of sustainability based on *the three pillars of sustainability*. It basically states that for the achievement and, of course also, for the analysis of sustainability of anthropogenic activities ecological, economic and social aspects have to be considered.

This three-fold interpretation, on the other hand, is not clear since it implies that all three 'pillar' are equally weighted within the context of sustainability and that each 'pillar' can be formed independently of the others. Aside from that, it is unclear what they have in common. Figure 2.5 thus assigns micro- and macroeconomic perspectives, as well as the demand for intercultural participation and fairness, to the technosphere, which is rooted in the ecosphere, assuming that the natural resources of life are carefully managed (L. Mayer, 2008).

2.3.1 Resilience

The concept and measurement of resilience, as developed in ecology, were inspired by dynamic systems theory and catastrophe theory (SR. Carpenter, 2003; Fiksel, 2006). The use of resilience in other disciplines and its application to multidimensional systems is increasing, particularly with respect to sustainable systems management (B. Walker et al., 2002a; Mayer, Thurston, and Pawlowski, 2004; Folke et al., 2005; Fiksel, 2006; Garmestani et al., 2006; Kinzig et al., 2006). Dynamic regimes (also called 'alternative stable states', (Mayer and Rietkerk, 2004) are areas of state space in which a system can persist in the presence of disturbances. The resilience of a regime is the degree to which the system can adjust to disturbances without shifting to a new regime (Holling, 1973; Grimm and Wissel, 1997; S. Carpenter et al., 2001). The system remains in that regime because of feedback between components of the system that prevent the system from straying too far. However, if a system moves into a new regime, new feedback will form to maintain the system within the new

⁴A similar popular formulation is 3P or PPP (People, Planet, Profit).

regime. Feedback in dynamic systems tends to be self-organising (SR. Carpenter, 2003; Rietkerk et al., 2004). Human activities which increase the sustainability of one system dimension (e.g. economic well-being) at the expense of another (e.g. ecological integrity) can degrade this feedback and hence system resilience (B. Walker et al., 2002b; Mayer and Rietkerk, 2004; Folke et al., 2005; L. Mayer, 2008).

2.3.2 Desirability

Sustainability applies not just to a system's resilience in a given regime, but also to the regime's desirability to humans (Troell et al., 2005). The durability of an Earth devoid of all life forms except bacteria may be high, but its desirability is poor. The optimal value of acceptable regime characteristics (e.g. what degree of disease risk in a population is tolerable?) and the means through which the regimes should be sustained (e.g. which policies are the most fair?) are both subjective decisions (P. Ehrlich and Kennedy, 2005; AA. Leiserowitz, RW. Kates, and TM. Parris, 2006; L. Mayer, 2008).

2.3.3 Scale

The resolution and scope (or time period) at which the device is observed, including temporal and spatial dimensions, are referred to as 'scale'. Some sustainability indices can be applied to structures of any spatial scale (e.g. households, watersheds, and nations) and over long periods of time (e.g. generations). The size of the data used to calculate sustainability indices, as well as the indices' own scale limitations, have an effect on their usefulness for decision-making (OECD, 2002; L. Mayer, 2008).

2.4 Environmental Sustainability (ES)

Sustainable development used to be more or less understood as social and economic development that should be environmentally sustainable (Moldan, Janoušková, and Hák, 2012). However, it was probably utilised by scientists who adopted this term from the original one used by the World Bank in 1992: 'environmentally responsible development'. This term was subsequently altered to 'Environmental Sustainability' and (Goodland, 1995) was the one of the very first experts who developed the ES as the 'maintenance of natural capital' so leading to the "three pillars" concept. The concept can be addressed as input/out rules which are defined as follows:

1. Output rule: Waste emissions from a project or action being considered should be kept within the assimilative capacity of the local environment without unacceptable degradation of its future waste absorptive capacity or other important services.
2. Input rule:
 - (a) Renewables: Harvest rates of renewable resource inputs should be within regenerative capacities of the natural system that generates them.
 - (b) Non-renewables: depletion rates of nonrenewable resource inputs should be set below the rate at which renewable substitutes are developed by human invention and investment according to the Serafian quasi-sustainability rule (36-38)⁵. An easily calculable portion of the proceeds from liquidating

⁵See (Goodland, 1995).

non-renewables should be allocated to research in pursuit of sustainable substitutes.

3. Operational principles:

- (a) The scale (population \times consumption per capita \times technology) of the human economic subsystem should be limited to a level which, if not optimal, is at least within the carrying capacity and therefore sustainable.
- (b) Technological progress for sustainable development should be efficiency-increasing rather than throughput-increasing.
- (c) Renewable resources should be exploited on a profit-optimising, sustained-yield, and fully sustainable basis.

This succinct description of ES from (Goodland, 1995) is the most useful so far, and it is gaining traction. Since its inception, it has increasingly come to be recognised that economic and social sustainability have merits of their own. As a part of individual, social, political, or economic advancement, their merits are of precise and concrete significance. The most important aspect of this term to remember is that ES is a natural scientific principle that follows biophysical laws (see aforementioned rules) (L. Mayer, 2008).

In light of such an understanding, it is necessary to closely scrutinise the ‘third pillar concept’ to focus on the definition of environmental sustainability and ask for a full clarification of its exact meaning. However, this general definition could be assumed to be robust irrespective of country, sector, or future epoch (L. Mayer, 2008).

Goodland’s conceptualisation of environmental sustainability fits into the resource-limited ecological economic framework of ‘limits to growth’ (Moldan, Janoušková, and Hák, 2012). He explains that each country’s journey to achieving sustainability would be different. Despite the fact that all countries must adhere to the input/output rules, countries vary in the amount of attention they devote to output and input in order to achieve ES. Some countries or regions, for example, must focus more on pollution control (e.g. former centrally planned economies); some countries must focus more on bringing harvest rates of renewable resources down to regeneration rates (e.g. tropical timber-exporting countries); some countries must reduce their population to below carrying capacity; and others must reduce their per capita income (e.g. all OECD⁶ countries) (L. Mayer, 2008).

Environmental sustainability is also described as a collection of constraints on the four main activities that regulate the scales of the human economic subsystem, according to (Moldan, Janoušková, and Hák, 2012). These four major activities are defined in [Table 2.1](#).

(L. Mayer, 2008) focuses on the bio-geophysical aspects of environmental protection when defining it (Holdren, Daily, and P. R. Ehrlich, 1995). Biophysical sustainability refers to the preservation or enhancement of the Earth’s life-supporting structures. Sustaining the biosphere with sufficient arrangements for maximising future options involves allowing current and future generations to achieve economic and social progress within a cultural diversity context that aims to preserve (Moldan, Janoušková, and Hák, 2012):

⁶Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development.

TABLE 2.1: Four set of constraints as environmental sustainability which scale the human economy.

Number	Activity
1 and 2	The use of renewable and non-renewable resources on the source side
3 and 4	Pollution and waste assimilation on the sink side

- a Biological diversity
- b The biogeochemical integrity of the biosphere by means of conservation and proper use of air, water, and land resources

2.5 Environmental Sustainability Scope

The term 'environmental sustainability' has gradually become commonly established (Moldan, Janoušková, and Hák, 2012). As an, the Commissioner for Environmental Sustainability of the Australian State of Victoria, (Sutton, 2004) defined environmental sustainability as: 'the ability to maintain the qualities that are valued in the physical environment'. The Environmental Sustainability Program of the U.S. National Science Foundation for 2009 advocates engineering research with the goal of promoting sustainably engineered systems that support human well-being and that are also accordingly compatible with sustaining natural systems.

There are compelling reasons from the point of view of (Weizsacker, 1992) as to why industrial countries should lead in devising paths toward sustainability. They have to adapt far more than developing countries do. If OECD countries cannot act first and lead the way, it is less likely that developing countries will choose to do so. Not only would it be enlightened self-interest for the north to act first, but it could also be viewed as a moral obligation. Second, developing countries are rightly pointing out (Agarwal and Narain, 1991; Declaration, 1991) that OECD countries have already consumed substantial amounts of environmental sink capacity (e.g. nearly all CFCs⁷ that are damaging the atmosphere were released by OECD countries) as well as source capacity (e.g. several species of great whales are extinct, and many stocks of fish and tropical timbers have been depleted below economically harvestable levels). Third, OECD countries can afford the transition to sustainability because they are richer. The rich would do themselves good by using the leeway they have for cutting overconsumption and waste (Goodland, 1995).

In addition to the facts above, (Bartlet, 1994) defines laws relating to sustainability and hypotheses about sustainability which could be considered as initial frameworks to establish Environmental Sustainability Scope. They are as follows:

Laws:

1. Neither growth in human population nor growth in the rates of resource consumption can be sustained.

⁷Chlorofluorocarbons.

2. The larger the population of a society and the larger its rates of consumption of resources, the more difficult it will be to transform the society to the condition of sustainability.
3. The response time of populations to changes in the total fertility rate is the length of time people live from their childbearing years to the end of life, or approximately 50 years.
4. The size of population that can be sustained (the carrying capacity) and the sustainable average standard of living are inversely related to one another.
5. Sustainability requires that the size of the population be less than or equal to the carrying capacity of the ecosystem for the desired standard of living.
6. The benefits of population growth and of growth in the rate of consumption of resources accrue to a few individuals; the costs are borne by all of society (the tragedy of the commons).
7. (Any) growth in the rate of consumption of a nonrenewable resource, such as a fossil fuel, causes a dramatic decrease in the life expectancy of the resource.
8. The time of expiration of nonrenewable resources, such as a fossil fuels, causes a dramatic decrease in the life expectancy of the resource.
9. When large efforts are made to improve the efficiency with which resources are used, the resulting savings are easily wiped out by the added resource needs that arise as a consequence of modest increases in population.
10. When rates of pollution exceed the natural cleansing capacity of the environment, it is easier to pollute than it is to clean up the environment.
11. Humans will always be dependent on agriculture, so land and other renewable resources will always be essential.

Hypotheses:

1. For the 1994 average global standard of living, the 1994 population of the Earth exceeds carrying capacity.
2. Increasing population size is the single greatest and most insidious threat to representative democracy.
3. The costs of programmes to stop population growth are small compared to the costs of population growth.
4. The time required for a society to make a planned transition to sustainability increases with increases in the size of its population and the average per capita consumption of resources.
5. Social stability is a necessary, but not a sufficient, condition for sustainability. Social stability tends to be inversely related to population density.
6. The burden of the lowered standard of living that results from population growth and from the decline of resources falls most heavily upon the poor.
7. Environmental problems cannot be solved or ameliorated by increases in the rates of consumption of resources.

TABLE 2.2: ES focus areas of Current Opinion in Environmental Sustainability journal

Focus area	Explanation
Climate systems	covering climate and climate change, climate risk management, mitigation and adaptation
Human settlements and habitats	covering cities, urbanisation and transport
Energy systems	covering energy use, energy conservation, renewable energy, energy efficiency and bioenergy
Terrestrial systems	covering natural and managed ecosystems, forestry, food systems, biodiversity and ecosystem services
Carbon and nitrogen cycles	covering sources and sinks, feedback processes and links to other systems
Aquatic systems	covering marine and fresh water ecosystems, fisheries, currents and biodiversity

8. The environment cannot be enhanced or preserved through compromises.
9. By the time overpopulation and shortage of resources are obvious to most people, the carrying capacity has already been exceeded. It is then too late to think about sustainability.

One of the new journals explicitly focuses on environmental sustainability scope. *Current Opinion in Environmental Sustainability* is the first scholarly journal to review and synthesise research on sustainability and environmental change. It provides its audience with a new vehicle to offer timely updates on science and research programmes (Moldan, Janoušková, and Hák, 2012). It focuses on six areas (see Table 2.2).

An important contribution to the concept of environmental sustainability scope was made by the OECD Environmental Strategy for the First Decade of the 21st Century (Moldan, Janoušková, and Hák, 2012; OECD, 2001). The strategy defines four specific criteria for environmental sustainability: regeneration (renewable resources shall be used efficiently and their use shall not be permitted to exceed their long-term rates of natural regeneration), substitutability (non-renewable resources shall be used efficiently and their use limited to levels which can be offset by substitution with renewable resources or other forms of capital), assimilation (releases of hazardous or polluting substances into the environment shall not exceed their assimilative capacity) and avoiding irreversibility. It identifies five inter-linked objectives for enhancing cost-effective and operational environmental policies in the context of sustainable development:

- Maintaining the integrity of ecosystems through the efficient management of natural resources
- Decoupling environmental pressures from economic growth
- Improving information for decision-making: measuring progress through indicators
- The social and environmental interface: enhancing quality of life

TABLE 2.3: Four categories of ecosystem services

Description	Examples
Providing	food, freshwater, wood and fiber, fuel, etc.
Regulatory	climate regulation, flood regulation, disease regulation, water purification, etc.
Cultural	aesthetic, spiritual, educational, recreational, etc.
Supporting	nutrient cycling, soil formation, primary production, etc.

- global environmental interdependence: improving governance and co-operation.

To expand the list of the basic principles of environmental sustainability scope (without pretending it is fully comprehensive), we may further add (Moldan, Janoušková, and Hák, 2012; Moldan, 2009):

- Long-term perspective (without any designated time limit)
- Understanding of the non-linear evolution of complex systems (tipping points, thresholds, sudden unpredictable changes)
- Taking feedbacks into account (in particular the positive ones)
- Regard for different scales (in time and space)
- Flexibility (the ability to react to a changing situation, learning by doing)
- Key importance of local conditions
- Respect for living nature in general and for biological diversity in particular

Further development of the concept was aided by the Millennium Ecosystem Assessment Project. Although The Synthesis Report (MEA, 2005) does not use the term environmental sustainability, it contributes substantially to its elucidation. It identifies ecosystem services and recognises four categories within them (Moldan, Janoušková, and Hák, 2012) (see Table 2.3).

The idea of ecosystem services can be broadened by services provided by global life-supporting systems (such as the stratospheric ozone layer, climatic system, hydrological cycle, and global biogeochemical cycles), by goods provided by the geosphere (mineral resources) and by three-dimensional open space: land on the Earth's surface and the space beneath and above it. To use the term coined by Daily, we may call all these goods and services 'nature's services' (Daily, 2005).

The ecosystem and nature's services are jointly linked to human well-being because it depends on them. To secure well-being, it is essential to maintain the ecosystem and nature's services at an appropriate standard. In other words, environmental sustainability may be defined as maintaining nature's services at a suitable level. Pointing out the indivisible connection between these services and human well-being, and indicating the many concrete expressions of this relationship, is the fundamental contribution of the Millennium Ecosystem Assessment Project.

Maintaining the adequate quality of nature's services necessitates sufficient care for the systems providing the services: ecosystems and global life-supporting systems that may be called 'environmental infrastructure'. The supply of necessary services is only possible if global ecological systems are in a healthy state. Concern for goods and services provided by nature means concern for nature itself, i.e. for global ecosystems and for biodiversity. Biological diversity is the most important element of environmental infrastructure and an overarching prerequisite for most of the services.

During the years after its introduction in the 1980s, the idea of sustainable development evolved from its rather fuzzy original notion to more precise specifications covering its fundamental pillars. Many important definitions are now presented in quantitative terms using different indicators. The need for a comprehensive analysis of indicators is thus obvious.

Ultimately environmental sustainability (ES) needs sustainable production and sustainable consumption. The two fundamental environmental services—the source and sink functions—must be maintained unimpaired during the period over which the scope of sustainability is required (H. Daly, 1991; HE. Daly, 1988; HE. Daly, 1992).

2.6 What is circular economy?

The concept of circular economy was first presented in the late 1970s (EMF, 2013). From then, it has exponentially gained importance (Geissdoerfer et al., 2016). (Boulding, 1966) in 'The Economics of the Coming Spaceship Earth' refers to the Earth as a closed and circular system with a limited assimilative capacity and infers from this that the economy and the environment should coexist in equilibrium. Since, many scholars (Andersen, 2007; Ghisellini, Cialani, and Ulgiati, 2016; Su et al., 2013; Pearce and R. Turner, 1989) have investigated the linear and open-ended characteristics of contemporary economic systems. They do so by describing how natural resources influence the economy by providing inputs for production and consumption and, at the same time serving as a sink for outputs in the form of waste.

(Stahel and Reday, 1976) focused on waste prevention, regional job creation, resource efficiency, and dematerialisation of the industrial economy to describe the industrial economy. They conceptualised a loop industrialised economy and introduced certain features of the circular economy to it. (Stahel, 1982) also emphasised selling utilisation instead of ownership of goods as the most relevant sustainable business model for a loop economy, allowing industries to profit without the external costs and risks associated with waste (Geissdoerfer et al., 2016).

The most renowned definition has been framed by the Ellen Mac Arthur Foundation, introducing the circular economy as 'an industrial economy that is restorative or regenerative by intention and design' (EMF, 2013; Geissdoerfer et al., 2016). Similarly, (Geng and Doberstein, 2008), focusing on the Chinese implementation of the concept, describe circular economy as the 'realisation of a closed loop material flow in the whole economic system'. (Webster, 2017) adds that 'a circular economy is one that is restorative by design, and which aims to keep products, components and materials at their highest utility and value, at all times'. Accordingly, (Yuan, Bi, and Moriguchi,

TABLE 2.4: Identified similarities between sustainability and the circular economy. Source: (Geissdoerfer et al., 2016).

Similarities	
1	Intra- and intergenerational commitments
2	More agency for the multiple and coexisting pathways of development
3	Global models
4	Integrating non-economic aspects into development
5	System change/design and innovation at the core
6	Multi-/interdisciplinary research field
7	Potential cost, risk, diversification, value co-creation opportunities
8	Cooperation of different stakeholders necessary
9	Regulation and incentives as core implementation tools
10	Central role of private business, due to resources and capabilities
11	Business model innovation as a key for industry transformation
12	Technological solutions are important but often pose implementation problems

2006) state that ‘the core of the circular economy is the circular (closed) flow of materials and the use of raw materials and energy through multiple phases’. (Bocken et al., 2016) categorise the characteristics of circular economy by defining it as ‘design and business model strategies that are slowing, closing, and narrowing resource loops’.

Based on these different contributions, (Geissdoerfer et al., 2016) defines the circular economy as *a regenerative system in which resource input and waste, emission, and energy leakage are minimised by slowing, closing, and narrowing material and energy loops. This can be achieved through long-lasting design, maintenance, repair, reuse, remanufacturing, refurbishing, and recycling.*

This definition is one of the conclusive ones that this study tends to refer to.

2.7 Sustainability vs. circular economy

One of the main questions that many peers are trying to answer is: What are the main conceptual similarities and differences between sustainability and the circular economy? This study will address (Geissdoerfer et al., 2016)’s contribution in this matter. Their article has been cited over 2000 times since 2016. The answers to the above-mentioned question can also be found in [Table 2.4](#) and [Table 2.5](#).

2.8 Circular economy of building envelope

The construction industry consumes the most raw materials in the world. In order to minimise the rate of consumption, more effective recycling and reuse activities in the construction industry are critical. The circular economy system (circularity) is emerging to meet this need. It is a philosophy that seeks to distinguish ‘economic development from environmental degradation.’ The output of a key field of

TABLE 2.5: Selected differences between sustainability and the circular economy. Source: (Geissdoerfer et al., 2016).

	Sustainability	Circular Economy
Origins of the term	Environmental movements, NGOs, non-profit and intergovernmental agencies, principles in silviculture and cooperative systems	Different schools of thought like cradle-to-cradle, regulatory implementation by governments, lobbying by NGOs like the EMF, inclusion in political agendas, e.g. European Horizon 2020
Goals	Open-ended, multitude of goals depending on the considered agent and her interests	Closed loop, ideally eliminating all resource input into and leakage out of the system
Main motivation	Diffused and diverse reflexivity and adaptive/past trajectories	Better use of resources, waste, leakage (from linear to circular)
What system is prioritised?	Triple bottom line (horizontal)	The economic system (hierarchical)
To whose benefit?	The environment, the economy, and society at large	Economic actors are at the core, benefitting the economy and the environment. Society benefits from environmental improvements and certain add-ons and assumptions, like more manual labour or fairer taxation
How did they institutionalise (wide diffusion)?	Providing vague framing that can be adapted to different contexts and aspirations	Emphasising economic and environmental benefits
Agency (Who influences? Who should influence?)	Diffused (priorities should be defined by all stakeholders)	Governments, companies, NGOs
Timeframe of changes	Open-ended, sustain current status “indefinitely”	Theoretical limits to optimisation and practical ones to implementation could set input and leakage thresholds for the successful conclusion of the implementation of a Circular Economy
Perceptions of responsibilities	Responsibilities are shared, but not clearly defined	Private business and regulators/policymakers
Commitments, goals, and interests behind the use of the term	Interest alignment between stakeholders, e.g. less waste is good for the environment, organisational profits, and consumer prices	Economic/financial advantages for companies, and less resource consumption and pollution for the environment

modern architecture, the exterior envelope layers of timber framed buildings, is critically evaluated using the circularity framework, as exemplified by (Finch et al., 2021).

The study by (Finch et al., 2021) collects circular assessment criteria from the literature that is applicable to the evaluation of building envelope layers. The study identifies two main patterns restricting circularity in the building envelope, using real-world deconstruction tests and the aforementioned circularity evaluation criteria: the widespread existence of fixings that irreversibly harm components, and the widespread use of chemically modified materials (i.e. treated and/or manufactured timber). Given the widespread use of such construction methods in New Zealand, Australia, and North America, there is a strong need for research into fixing and material technologies for building envelopes that follow circular economy design criteria (Finch et al., 2021).

The study by (Finch et al., 2021) also developed a curated set of assessment criteria for the design of a circular building envelope based on the circular economy's theoretical structure. A multi-pronged criteria creation framework was used, which looked at both generic circular evaluation methods from the literature as well as those that had already been optimised for use in the built environment. Twenty important circular success criteria were defined and grouped into three evaluative groups. The study then used these parameters to test the circular capacity of modern platform timber wall construction to see if they were correct. As a result of the study, all layers in the platform device assembly are found to be in violation of circular design guidelines (as expected). However, by using the criterion, the evaluation was able to distinguish particular patterns that avoid circularity. The widespread existence of repairing systems that irreversibly harm goods was described as the first pattern. Structural adhesives and nail fixings that penetrated several building layers are among them. The widespread existence of materials with chemical alterations that make them unable to be recycled in a meaningful way (if direct reuse is not an option) was described as a second pattern. Copper, chrome, and arsenic (CCA) pressure-treated wood and engineered wood products were the most prominent examples of this (such as plywood). The geometric qualities of shaped components were the third major concern (Finch et al., 2021) (see also [Table 2.6](#)).

TABLE 2.6: Circular performance of external functional layers of proposed circular design (structure, waterproofing, thermal resistance, air and vapour control layers) by (Finch et al., 2021).

Performance criteria	Circular performance notes
Discrete characteristics	
Recycled materials and recyclable materials	Timber=no, Building wrap=yes, fixings=yes, insulation=yes, cladding=yes
High value recycling possible?	Yes
Secondary finishes on materials	No
Chemically hazardous materials	No
Chemical material connections	No
Reversible mechanical connections	Yes
Structurally independent layers	Yes
Qualitative characteristics	
Material types identified	Some identifiable to specialist (thermally modified timber) and some printed on materials (insulation and building wrap)
Components sized to suit the means of handling	Assembled panels must be lifted in place and out of place by at least 2 people
Use of modular design	Modular based on a 1.2 m module, but requires custom elements for non rectilinear geometry
Provision for 'realistic' tolerances for assembly and disassembly	Unknown—requires physical fabrication, construction, deconstruction and reconstruction
Disassembly requires only common tools and equipment	An impact driver is required to fix bolts quickly. This is common depending on the builder
Joints and materials withstand repeated use (durability)	Generally all fixings are reversible. The long term durability of timber mortise and tenon connections is unknown
Adopt prefabrication	Level of prefabrication could vary depending on cost and availability. Prefabricated structural elements are mixing with roll and bag products that are not required to be fitted off-site
Use of lightweight materials	Typically materials are categorised as lightweight. Cladding/rain protection could be heavy depending on client selection
Measurable characteristics (for 1 m² wall)	
Quantity of different types of materials	4
Quantity of different types of connectors	4
Quantity of Connectors	8
Quantity of devalued materials (waste) after a use and deconstruction cycle	Currently Untested—Requires physical fabrication, assembly and disassembly

Chapter 3

Sustainable Development

3.1 Introduction

The concept of sustainable development (SD) has become an important objective of policy makers in the construction industry (Singh et al., 2008). The term ‘sustainable development’ was coined by the IUCN’s 1980 World Conservation Strategy (Moldan, Janoušková, and Hák, 2012; IUCN, UNEP, and WWF, 1980). It stated that “for development to be sustainable it must take account of social and ecological factors, as well as economic ones”. At present, both the term and its tenor have become so widespread and well-known that we may take them as being commonly understood. Moreover, the term is inevitably incorporated into any important political, business or other strategic document (e.g. most of the fundamental documents of the European Union, including the recent Lisbon Treaty) (Moldan, Janoušková, and Hák, 2012; EU, 2007). Seven years after 1980, Our Common Future (WCED, 1987) then gave further direction to comprehensive global solutions.

“Sustainable development is development that meets the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs”. (see also [section 2.2](#)).

This has since become an often-quoted definition (Singh et al., 2008). The definition was extended by the Earth Summit in 1992 (UN, 1992), the 40 chapters (150.000+ words) for Agenda 21 (Moldan, Janoušková, and Hák, 2012). After that, the formalisation of the term was completed by the World Summit on Sustainable Development in 2002 (UN, 2002b) with the notion of there being three pillars – social, environmental, economic – as symbolised by the summit motto “People, Planet, Prosperity” (which is already mentioned in [section 2.3](#)).

Through studying both cited documents as well as others see (Bell and Morse, 1999), it goes without saying that sustainable development and sustainability is not identical, even though their fundamental senses are basically the same (Moldan, Janoušková, and Hák, 2012). While sustainability denotes a system property referred to as quality, some believe that the key to the sustainable development concept is provided by the already quoted Brundtland report definition and Article 1 of the Rio Declaration (Moldan, Janoušková, and Hák, 2012):

“Human beings are at the centre of concerns for sustainable development. They are entitled to a healthy and productive life in harmony with nature”.

The message of these two fundamental documents could be summarised into three brief points.

1. The idea of sustainable development is a pragmatic and anthropocentric one. It primarily focuses on people and their well-being. At the base of sustainability is our needs. One approach, known as Maslow's Pyramid, assumes that human beings are motivated by unsatisfied needs. Certain basic needs must be fulfilled before higher needs can be met (Maslow, 1998). According to Maslow, there are universal needs (physiological, survival, safety, love, and esteem) that must be fulfilled before a person can act unselfishly. This foundation for unselfish behaviour could certainly then be seen as one of the conditions for accomplishing sustainable development. We would agree with the essential elements of human well-being stipulated in the (MEA, 2005), these being: security, the basic material for a good life, health, good social relations, and freedom of choice and action (Moldan, Janoušková, and Hák, 2012).
2. Human life should be: "healthy, productive and in harmony with nature" (UN, 2002b). This principle implies a quest for balance among the three sustainable development pillars. Human life is neither independent nor isolated; it is part of a complex web of natural and social phenomena and depends on a myriad of relationships and interdependencies. In particular, the necessary "harmony with nature", which addresses the environmental pillar, is stressed.
3. Another essential feature of sustainability is dynamic and long-term nature. The formulation takes into account "present and future generations" and simultaneously points out the changing situation and emphasises concerns for the future without any explicit time limit or target. The time dimension is tied to the average human life span and highlights a necessary extension – possibly a very long extension – above and beyond it.

These three simple principles could apply to all three pillars. However, after summarising the scientific facts above, we do not believe that sustainable development to be an anthropocentric matter. Given the latest knowledge and understanding of human behaviour when it comes to dealing with nature, the human being should accept that the age of nature, especially the Earth (4.543×10^9 a) is not comparable with the age of humanity (approx. 3×10^5 a). During this long period of time in which there were no humans on Earth, the Earth and its environment maintained an intelligent and sustainable course of development. A good example of this can be observed Chernobyl where, following an environmental catastrophe caused by humans, the environment pursued its own sustainable path to recovery. Today, whole area of the Chernobyl is covered in green and nature is returning. There are numerous other cases which can be concluded in the same manner. So, if humankind cannot learn to live *with* nature rather than *in* nature, we may not be able to survive.

3.2 Sustainability Assessment

There are a number of sustainability assessment frameworks that evaluate the performance of companies (see Table 3.1). These act as the foundation for sustainability reporting. (Azapagic, 2004) developed a framework for sustainability indicators for the mining and minerals industry, which is also compatible to GRI¹. (Krajnc and Glavic, 2005) collected and developed a standardised set of sustainability indicators for companies covering all main aspects of sustainable development (Singh et al.,

¹Global Reporting Initiative.

TABLE 3.1: Sustainable assessment initiators.

Framework	Reference
The World Business Council for Sustainable Development	(WBCSD, 1997)
The Global Reporting Initiative	(GRI, 2002b; GRI, 2002a)
Development of Standards	(OECD, 2002)

2008).

Even recently, the European Union's Gothenburg Sustainable Development Strategy approved in 2001 with the renewed version endorsed again in 2006 placed four of its six main objectives more or less within the environmental realm:

1. Climate change and clean energy
2. Sustainable transport
3. Sustainable consumption and production
4. Conservation and management of natural resources and public health

The other two objectives pertained to social inclusion: demography and migration, and global poverty and sustainable development challenges (Moldan, Janoušková, and Hák, 2012; European Union, 2006).

According to (R.W. Kates et al., 2001; R.W. Kates et al., 2007), the purpose of a sustainability assessment is to provide decision-makers with an evaluation of global to local integrated nature – society systems in short – and long-term perspectives in order to help determine which actions should or should not be taken in an attempt to make society sustainable (Singh et al., 2008).

There is a widely recognised need for individuals, organisations and societies to find models, metrics and tools for articulating the extent to which, and the ways in which, current activities are unsustainable. This need emerges on multiple levels including supranational (e.g. the negotiation of protocols for environmental protection), national (e.g. via some version of 'greening' GDP) and sub-national levels (e.g. in regional development forums) (Ramachandran, 2000).

Indicators and composite indicators are increasingly recognised as useful tools not only for policy making but also for public communication. They can help to convey information on countries' performances in fields such as environment, economy, society, or technological development (Singh et al., 2008).

"Indicators arise from values (we measure what we care about), and they create values (we care about what we measure)" (Maslow, 1998). Some scholars have mentioned that the main feature of indicators is their ability to summarise, focus and condense the enormous complexity of our dynamic environment to a manageable amount of meaningful information. By visualising phenomena and highlighting trends, indicators simplify, quantify, analyse and communicate otherwise complex and complicated information (Warhurst, 2002).

TABLE 3.2: Framework for sustainability assessment tools.

Factor	Example
Temporal characteristics	i.e. if the tool evaluates past development (ex-post or descriptive), or if it is used for predicting future outcomes (ex-ante or change-oriented) such as a policy change or an improvement in a production process
The focus (coverage areas)	for example, if their focus is at the product level, or on a proposed change in policy
Integration of nature–society system	i.e. to what extent the tool fuses environmental, social and/or economic aspects

In an effort to introduce and define sustainability science, (R.W. Kates et al., 2001; R.W. Kates et al., 2007) provide seven core research questions. Two are particularly connected to the issue of assessing sustainability (Ness et al., 2006):

1. “How can today’s operational systems for monitoring and reporting on environmental and social conditions be integrated or extended to provide more useful guidance for efforts to navigate a transition toward sustainability?”
2. “How can today’s relatively independent activities of research planning, monitoring, assessment, and decision support be better integrated into systems for adaptive management and societal learning?”

The need for an integrated systematic approach to defining and measuring indicators is recognised (Bossel, 1999) in order to give well-structured methodologies, allow for easy reproduction and to assure that all important aspects are included in the measurement. However, before developing the methodology and the indicators, it is important to establish a clear definition of the policy goals pertaining to sustainability. This appears to be even more difficult since, in most cases, the development of indicators has started while there is still contention over what constitutes sustainable development in the first place (Singh et al., 2008).

3.3 Environmental Assessment Methods

Knowing what factors drive emissions and impacts over the entire life span of a building is essential to achieve significant environmental improvements in the building stock (Lausselet, Borgnes, and Brattebø, 2018). Earlier overviews of assessment methods/tools/indicators have demonstrated that approaches can be categorised based on numerous factors or dimensions (Ness et al., 2006; Baumann and Cowell, 1999; Moberg, 1999; Wrisberg et al., 2002; G. Finnveden, M. Nilsson, et al., 2003; G. Finnveden and Moberg, 2005; R. W. Kates, T. Parris, and A. Leiserowitz, 2005). The factors in Table 3.2 can be taken into account.

The sustainability assessment tool framework is adapted from (Ness et al., 2006) and is illustrated in Figure 3.1. It consists of three umbrellas or general categorisation areas, these being:

1. Indicators and indices, which are further broken down into non-integrated and integrated
2. Product-related assessment tools with a focus on the material and/or energy flows of a product or service from a life cycle perspective
3. Integrated assessment which is a collection of tools usually focused on policy change or project implementation

3.3.1 Indicators and indices

Indicators and indices fall into the first category of sustainability evaluation instruments. Indicators simply and numerically reflect the state of economic, social and/or environmental growth in a given region—usually at the national level. The resulting metric is an index where metrics are aggregated in some way. Indicators, according to (Harger and Meyer, 1996), should have the following characteristics: simplicity, (a broad) reach, quantifiability, the ability to evaluate patterns, methods that are responsive to change and the ability to identify trends quickly. Indicators and indices that are continuously monitored and calculated allow for the retrospective monitoring of longer-term sustainability trends. Understanding these patterns allows for accurate short-term forecasting and effectively made future decisions. The instruments in the category of indicators and indices are either non-integrated, meaning they do not incorporate nature–society parameters, or integrated, meaning they aggregate the various dimensions. Non-integrated methods are often divided into a subcategory that focuses on regional flow indicators.

Non-integrated indicators

Environmental Pressure Indicators (EPIs), produced by Eurostat², are an example of non-integrated indicators. Eurostat's mission is to collect and prepare comparable and understandable data for EU countries and regions in close cooperation with member state statistical offices. The EPI collection includes 60 indicators, six for each of the ten policy areas covered by the Fifth Environmental Action Programme (Lammers and Gilbert, 1999). The six measures in each policy area can also be combined into an index, resulting in a total of ten environmental pressure indices. The aim of these indicators, which include things like forest damage, fishing pressure, tourism intensity, and waste landfilling, is to give EU member states a standard and detailed collection of indicators to assess and measure environmental sustainability. These indicators allow for a comparison of environmental conditions in different EU member countries, as well as an assessment of developments in individual countries and in the EU as a whole. EPI studies from the years 1999 and 2001 are currently available (European Commission and Eurostat, 1999; European Commission and Eurostat, 2001).

Another example is the UNCED's collection of 58 national indicators. The UNCED³ was founded in 1992 to carry out the goals of the United Nations Conference on Environment and Development, which took place in Rio de Janeiro, Brazil. These metrics go beyond traditional economic indicators to include social, environmental, and institutional monitoring frameworks (UNCED, 2001) in order to achieve

²Statistical Office of the European Communities.

³United Nations Commission on Sustainable Development.

FIGURE 3.1: Framework for sustainability assessment tools. The proposed assessment tool framework is based on the temporal focus of the tool with the tool’s object of focus. The arrow on the top of the framework shows the temporal focus, which is either retrospective (indicators/indices), prospective (integrated assessment) or both (product-related assessment). The object of focus of the tools is either spatial, referring to a proposed change in policy (indicators/indices and integrated assessment), or at the product level (product-related assessment). The *monetary valuation* tools on the bottom are used when monetary valuations are needed in the above tools. Thick lines around the boxes mean that these tools are capable of integrating nature–society systems into single evaluation (Ness et al., 2006).

a: “a broader, more complete picture of societal development”. The indicators are not combined or grouped in any way. Water quality levels in the environmental category, national education levels, and population growth rates as social determinants, GNP⁴ per capita in the economic sphere, and the number of ratified global agreements in the institutional sustainability category are all examples of UNCSO indicators (UNCSO, 2001). Since 1994, several member countries have submitted national reports and country profiles based on these indicators (UN, 2002a).

Regional flow indicators

Analysis of material and energy flows allows an overview of the structure of resource flows and identification of inefficiencies within a system. Such studies may be used both for reconstructing historical flows and emissions and for forecasting and decision support. MFA⁵ analyses the physical metabolism of society in order to support dematerialisation and reduction of losses to the environment connected to the extensive societal resources (Kleijn, 2001). MFA studies have been performed in many countries and the number of regional MFA studies has increased during the last decades. Overviews and analysis of various studies up to the 1990s have been presented by researchers such as (Fischer-Kowalski and Hüttler, 1998; Anderberg et al., 2000). Regional flow indicators are also non-integrated as they only focus on physical flows.

Eurostat’s economy-wide MFA is the most standardised instrument for MFA for regions. It is mostly used at the national level, but can also accommodate other spatial levels. The World Resources Institute’s research on total material flows in developed economies (Adriaanse et al., 1997; Matthews et al., 2000) was crucial in standardising regional material flow analysis. Eurostat established guidelines for performing an economy’s MFA (Eurostat, 2001). The most common output of flow analyses is comprehensive flow diagrams, but there are many indicators that are based on this type of analysis. Material flow indicators are divided into three groups by Eurostat: input, output and consumption indicators. Depending on whether they cover domestic, international or secret flows, each category contains indicators at various levels. Excavation, non-saleable mining, soil degradation and other products that do not join economic processes are examples of hidden flows (Matthews et al., 2000). Indicators of material input demonstrate how materials enter the economy through local production and consumption. Material performance indicators monitor both waste and pollution outflows to the atmosphere, either during or after the production and consumption processes. The overall amount of materials used in an economy is measured by material use indices.

SFA⁶ focuses on regional flows of specific chemicals and/or chemical compounds, as well as the associated environmental losses. The ultimate aim of SFA is to minimise the amount of a specific material impacts a process. SFA is used to classify problem areas on a regional or national scale. The results of the SFA can be used to prepare and manage the environment at different levels. An analysis of cadmium flows in Swedish municipalities (Lindqvist and von Malmborg, 2004) exemplified how SFA could be used in decision-making processes.

⁴Gross National Product.

⁵Material Flow Analysis.

⁶Substance Flow Analysis.

Energy analysis examines all of an economy's energy flows. It is based on the first law of thermodynamics, which states that energy is constant and cannot be produced or destroyed, only transformed into different forms of energy (Hovelius, 1997). Input–output energy analysis, which is based on Leontief's economic input–output matrix and analyses the trade between various industries in the economy, is often used to conduct a national or regional energy analysis. Trade volumes are replaced by energy flows between industries in energy analysis (Hovelius, 1997; G. Finnveden and Moberg, 2005).

Energy analysis can also be carried out by using different types of energy measures, such as exergy and emergy. These both forms of analysis are more advanced since they consider both the quality and the quantity of energy (Rosen and Dincer, 2001; Herendeen, 2004). The exergy of a system is the maximal amount of mechanical work that can be extracted (Wall, 1977). An exergy analysis gives an overview of the effectiveness of resource utilisation, showing where losses occur and where technological improvements can be made to increase energy efficiency. There are examples of Regional Exergy Analyses for Sweden (Wall, 1997b; Wall, 1997a; R. Ayres, L. Ayres, and Warr, 2003). (Odum, 1996) has created a methodology for Regional Emery Analysis where all resources and goods are expressed in common units (solar emjoules) measuring the solar energy that was required to produce them (Doherty, P. Nilsson, and Odum, 2002).

Integrated indicators and indices

There have been several attempts to go beyond the non-integrated approach to instead incorporate various nature–society dimensions into a single measure or index. The framework's first four indices are attempts to create alternatives to national accounting indices like GDP⁷ and NNP⁸, which are commonly used as indicators of overall human welfare. GDP and NNP also give decision-makers false signals about true sustainability, omitting important factors such as income distribution, public safety, resource overuse, and other negative externalities that are not accounted for in these common steps (Gerlagh et al., 2002). A number of alternative calculation methods have been devised as a result of GDP failing to take environmental factors into account or act as an adequate quality of life indicator. Each one offers a slightly different assessment of long-term development. A concise overview of many of these measures, as well as the outcomes of the assessments, can be found in (Hanley et al., 1999).

The SNI⁹ index was created specifically for the Netherlands (Heuting, Bosch, and de Boer, 1993). By integrating sustainable resource utilisation indicators into national income accounting, the method aims to look beyond strict economic production thresholds to determine well-being. Social variables are not directly factored into SNI calculations. The index compares calculated sustainable national income with traditional national income accounting practices. The difference between the two numbers denotes the country's reliance on natural resource usage that exceeds what is sustainable (Gerlagh et al., 2002).

⁷Gross Domestic Product.

⁸Net National Product.

⁹Sustainable National Income.

The ISEW¹⁰ (H.E. Daly and J. Cobb, 1989) and the GPI¹¹ (C. Cobb, Halstead, and Rowe, 1995), both created by the non-profit organisation Redefining Progress in the mid-1990s, cover the dimensions of economic, society, and environment. Both of these instruments, which are closely related, modify national accounting standards to incorporate a wider range of welfare determinants, such as military spending deductions, environmental degradation and natural resource depreciation. For a variety of countries, calculations of ISEW can be found in the literatures.

Another alternative assessment method for determining national sustainability is Adjusted Net Savings, also known as Genuine Savings (Hamilton, G. Atkinson, and Pearce, 1997). This metric is most closely aligned with the World Bank. The Adjusted Net Saving rate now includes technological development, human resources, exhaustible resource exports, resource discoveries, and vital natural capital, in addition to resource depletion and environmental degradation. The tool focuses mostly on the economic and environmental aspects, but it also involves educational investments. A positive indicator value indicates a positive shift toward sustainability, while a negative indicator value indicates the polar opposite. As a result, it has the advantage of sending a strong signal about a country's development path (Everett and Wilks, 1999).

The Ecological Footprint (Wackernagel and Rees, 1996) is an accounting method that calculates a population's or economy's resource use and waste assimilation requirements in terms of a given land area. The method of calculating the Ecological Footprint is multi-staged. The annual consumption of food, lodging, transportation, household goods, and services by the average citizen is estimated. The land area required for development and the environmental effect of each of the consumption products are then measured, and all of the areas required are then added together. As a result, a per capita land area for annual consumption of goods and services has been calculated (Wackernagel and Rees, 1996). Several countries and regions have used the Ecological Footprint method. It has mostly been used to assess sustainability at the national level, but it has also been used to assess developments at the city or urban-region level, as well as aggregated indices (Venetoulis, Chazan, and Gaudet, 2004).

The Wellbeing Index (Prescott-Allen, 2001) was used in a survey of 180 countries for the World Summit for Sustainable Development in Johannesburg in 2002. The HWI¹² and EWI¹³ are two indices that combine data from over 60 different variables to create the Wellbeing Index. EWI aggregates soil, water, and air dimensions, biodiversity issues, and resource use indicators, while HWI includes population and health parameters, wealth indicators, and indicators on knowledge, culture, environment, and equity issues. When the two indices are combined into an illustrative instrument called the Barometer of Sustainability, they are assigned equal weight.

The ESI¹⁴ was created to track the: "overall progress toward environmental sustainability" (International Earth Science Information Network, 2002). It includes 68 indicators in five categories: the condition of environmental systems (air, water, soil, ecosystems, and so on), the reduction of pressures on environmental systems, the

¹⁰The Index of Sustainable Economic Welfare.

¹¹General Progress Indicator.

¹²Human Wellbeing Index.

¹³Ecosystem Wellbeing Index.

¹⁴Environmental Sustainability Index.

reduction of human vulnerability to environmental change, social and institutional capacity to cope with environmental problems and compliance with international standards and agreements (International Earth Science Information Network, 2002). Despite the fact that this index is primarily concerned with environmental protection, it also addresses social and institutional concerns. The aim of ESI is to allow for cross-national comparisons and to aid in environmental decision-making.

The UNDP¹⁵ uses the HDI¹⁶ to assess social and economic development in various countries. It is made up of three main components: longevity, knowledge, and living standards (UNDP, 2004). The adult literacy rate and the combined primary, secondary, and tertiary gross enrolment ratio are used to calculate longevity, while knowledge is determined by a combination of the adult literacy rate and the combined primary, secondary, and tertiary gross enrolment ratios. Finally, GDP per capita is used to determine a person's standard of living. Since 1975, the HDI has been calculated for UN member countries with adequate data as well as a small number of non-member countries. Historical comparisons have been complicated due to the index having undergone a major reform in 1999 (Lind, 2004).

3.3.2 Product-related assessment

The second umbrella includes product-related instruments that are concerned with flows associated with the manufacture and consumption of products and services. They are closely related to the regional flow indicators of the previous group, since they are built on a common flow perspective (Anderberg et al., 2000). However, instead of focusing on continents, the methods in this category evaluate different flows in relation to various goods or services. They assess resource usage and environmental effects during the manufacturing process or a product's life cycle (from cradle to grave). The goals of defining specific risks and inefficiencies to aid decision-making are close to those of regional flow indicators, but this time in relation to product and production system design. Since they are primarily concerned with environmental issues, these tools do not incorporate nature–society processes. Life cycle costing tools, on the other hand, can take into account both environmental and economic factors. Product-related methods facilitate decision-making by accommodating retrospective and prospective evaluations.

Life cycle assessment

Life cycle assessment is the key and core method that this study would choose to utilise. Thus, [chapter 4](#) focuses on the principles of this method and its characteristics.

Life cycle costing

The phrase 'life cycle costing' refers to an economic method of calculating the: "total costs of a product, process, or operation discounted over its lifetime" (Gluch and Baumann, 2004). In theory, LCC is not linked to environmental costs, but to all costs. A traditional LCC is a form of investment calculation that ranks different investment options to help you choose the best one for your needs. Life cycle costing analysis can be done using a variety of methods, but only two of them include environmental

¹⁵United Nations Development Programme.

¹⁶Human Development Index.

costs: Life Cycle Cost Assessment and Full Cost Environmental Accounting. For more information on life cycle costing tools, see (Gluch and Baumann, 2004).

Product material flow analysis

For product systems, an analysis of material and content flows is often used. Material Intensity Analysis, based on the MIPS¹⁷ index (expressed in weight), has been developed by the Wuppertal Institute for Climate, Environment and Energy (Spangenberg et al., 1999). This research takes into account all material flows associated with a specific product or service, such as the so-called ecological 'rucksack'. The ecological rucksack is made up of all the materials needed for the entire manufacturing process minus the product's actual weight, and it reflects the product's actual material intensity. The MIPS concept has been the starting point for strategic discussions on the Factor 4 and Factor 10 goals.

Substance Flow Analysis is carried out at various points of the life cycle to determine where inflows and outflows of substances occur. The study allows for the identification of the cause of the environmental effect and, as a result, the direction of any resulting reduction in the environmental burden. SFA can be used to analyse a product's life cycle, but it is most often used to analyse industries (Antikainen, Haapanen, and Rekolainen, 2004).

Product energy analysis

Product energy analysis calculates how much energy it takes to make a product or provide a service (Herendeen, 2004). Both direct and indirect energy flows are included. Indirect energy is the energy used to generate inputs, such as metal for the automobile industry. Process Energy Analysis is an example of a method for analysing product or service energy requirements (Hovelius, 1997). It focuses on various processes and levels during the product life cycle, and sums up the energy flows across each stage of the manufacturing process. Exergy and emergy analyses based on the life cycle are also used. Exergy analysis has been used to analyse energy systems such as heating and electricity production (D. Nilsson, 1997; M.T. Brown and Ulgiati, 2002), while emergy analysis has been used to analyse the production processes of a particular product (Hovelius, 1997) as well as whole industries (Doherty, P. Nilsson, and Odum, 2002).

3.3.3 Integrated assessment

Integrated evaluation tools fall under the third umbrella and are used to help decisions about a policy or a project in a particular area. Local scale evaluations are conducted using project-related instruments, while policy-related assessments are conducted on a local to global scale. Integrated assessment methods have an ex ante emphasis in the sense of sustainability assessment and are often carried out in the form of scenarios. Many of these integrated evaluation techniques are based on system analysis methods and take into account both nature and society. Integrated evaluation is a set of methods for dealing with complex problems (Gough, Castells, and Funtowicz, 1998). There are numerous examples of integrated evaluations of major environmental concerns, alongside well-established methods such as Multi-Criteria Analysis, Risk Analysis, Vulnerability Analysis, and Cost Benefit Analysis. These are not limited

¹⁷Material Input per unit of Service.

to sustainability issues but can be applied to a number of other problems across disciplinary boundaries.

Conceptual modelling and systems dynamics

Conceptual modelling is also known as, mental modelling or soft-systems modelling, though the words have somewhat different connotations (Checkland, 1981). Stock and flow diagrams, flow maps and causal loop diagrams are often used in conceptual modelling to analyse qualitative (causal) relationships. Conceptual modelling can be used to visualise and detect where changes in a system can be made to improve sustainability, or it can be used as the initial conceptualisation process in a broader computer modelling strategy. Systems Dynamics refers to: “the building of computer models of complex problem situations and then experimenting with and studying the behaviour of these models over time” (Caulfield and Maj, 2001). The IIASA air pollution model (RAINS), the IMAGE model for analysing social, biosphere and climate system dynamics and the Wonderland model for illustrating economic–environmental interactions are all examples of models relevant to sustainability assessment.

Multi-criteria analysis

Where there are overlapping evaluation criteria, Multi-Criteria Analysis (MCA) is used for evaluations. MCA defines broad goals or priorities and then tries to recognise trade-offs among them, with the ultimate aim of being to determine the best strategy. This method has the benefit of using both qualitative and quantitative data in the process (Wrisberg et al., 2002). MCA has been used in the Netherlands (Brouwer and van Ek, 2004) to choose the best solution for flood control policies, as well as to design energy and environmental policies (Greening and Bernow, 2004).

Risk analysis and uncertainty analysis

Risk is defined as: “the possibility that certain losses or damages occur as the result of a particular event or series of events” (Rotmans, 1998). The calculation of these possible losses is known as risk analysis. The phase starts with the recognition of the risk and progresses to a qualitative and/or quantitative evaluation of the risk, which leads to specific managerial decisions about risk minimisation (Vose, 2000). The final stage of the risk analysis involves communicating with stakeholders about the evaluation and the decisions that will be made to reduce the risk. Risk and uncertainty are inextricably linked, so risk analysis and uncertainty analysis are too inextricably linked (Rotmans, 1998). There are two types of uncertainty: stochastic uncertainty and fundamental uncertainty. Stochastic uncertainty refers to the system’s inherent variability, while fundamental uncertainty refers to the inability to predict due to a lack of understanding about the system (Kann and Weyant, 2000; Vose, 2000). Both forms of uncertainty are present in uncertainty and risk analysis. They estimate the likelihood of events and make predictions based on the information they have. Because of these facets of natural variability and a lack of expertise, social and environmental risk evaluations are types of sustainability assessments.

Vulnerability analysis

Vulnerability analysis assesses the vulnerability of coupled human–environment systems in order to decide how responsive and adaptive they are to change (B. Turner

et al., 2003), as well as their ability to cope with it. A risk analysis may be done if the analysis concludes that a human or environmental structure is vulnerable. Vulnerability analysis has been used a lot recently in the sense of climate change, and it has shown that certain populations and ecosystems are far more vulnerable to the impact of climate change than others (P. Kelly, 2000; Dixon, Smith, and Guill, 2003; O'Brien, Sygna, and Haugen, 2004).

Cost benefit analysis (CBA)

CBA¹⁸ is a welfare economics instrument that dates back to the early twentieth century (P.-O. Johansson, 1996). It is used to balance the project's costs against the potential benefits when assessing public or private investment proposals. CBA can be a useful method for weighing the social costs and benefits of various options in the field of sustainability evaluation, such as electricity and transportation (Wrisberg et al., 2002). This aspect of calculating expected benefits, or assigning monetary units to them, is often problematic with CBA (Moberg, 1999).

Impact assessment

Impact assessment is a subset of forecasting instruments that are used to improve the foundation for policymaking and project approval. They all stem from founded on methodologies that try to factor in concerns from a variety of stakeholder groups during the evaluation process.

Since the 1960s, EIA¹⁹ has been used to assess the possible environmental impacts of major construction projects with the aim of minimising negative consequences (Sadler, 1999). In 1985 (EU Commission, 1985; EU Commission, 1997), the European Union passed a directive making EIA mandatory for any planned public and private projects (such as building projects) that are likely to have environmental impacts. Many other countries have incorporated EIA into their laws (Petts, 1999). The EIA procedure in the EU and other countries is governed by strict guidelines as a result of certain legal criteria (J. Walker and Johnston, 1999).

SEA²⁰ is a method used to assess the possible environmental impacts of strategic decisions that evolved from EIA in the 1990s (Partidario, 1999). Two main distinctions exist between SEA and EIA. SEA must be completed sooner than EIA, and it is used in situations where there is less detail, greater uncertainty and less concreteness, as is often the case with political decisions. Meanwhile, EIA is used in the specific circumstances of a project. Despite these distinctions, many of the concepts and procedures of both systems are identical (Partidario, 1999). In both EIA and SEA, involvement of the public is a key part of the process, and diverse interests should be able to have a voice in connection with the recommendations.

The EU has recently released the SIA²¹ method, which is a more robust tool. Its goal is to move away from sectoral, often fragmented assessments and towards an integrated evaluation that takes into account environmental, economic and social factors. The aim of this new tool is to improve our ability to recognise: "the possible

¹⁸Cost Benefit Analysis.

¹⁹Environmental Impact Assessment.

²⁰Strategic Environmental Assessment.

²¹Sustainability Impact Assessment.

positive and negative impacts of potential policy decisions, allowing informed political choices about the initiative and identifying trade-offs in achieving conflicting objectives” see (EU Commission, 2002). The first use of the sustainability impact assessment was in early 2003, and it is now used by all major Commission initiatives. (Wilkinson et al., 2004) concluded, among other items, that none of the initial SIAs had adopted the Commission guidelines to the letter. This same study also revealed that the number of impacts evaluated was small, and that the focus remained on economic factors rather than environmental or social ones. In the near future, further guideline production and revisions are planned.

Chapter 4

Life Cycle Assessment

This chapter is dedicated to the LCA and its structure. This chapter is inspired mainly by (Walter Klöpffer and Grahl, 2014) who also define the LCA as a product-related sustainability assessment method within its boundaries.

4.1 What is Life Cycle Assessment?

4.1.1 Definition and limitations

The most established and well-developed tool in the product-related assessment category is the Life Cycle Assessment (see [Figure 3.1](#)). LCA has been used in varying forms over the past 35 years to evaluate the environmental impacts of a product or a service throughout its life cycle. It is an approach that analyses the real and potential pressure that a product has on the environment during the raw material acquisition, production process, use, and disposal of the product (Lindorfs, 1995). The International Standards Organisation (ISO) has established guidelines and principles for LCA that have been further interpreted and developed by many (Ciambrone, 1997; M. Hauschild and Wenzel, 2000; Ross and Evans, 2002; O. Jolliet et al., 2004). LCA results provide information for decisions regarding product development and ecodesign, production system improvements and product choice at the consumer level. LCA has been performed for the pulp and paper industry (Ekvall, 1999; Ross and Evans, 2002; Lopes et al., 2003), the waste and energy field (Lunghi, Bove, and Desideri, 2004; G. Finnveden, J. Johansson, et al., 2004; Moberg et al., 2004), as well as a multitude of other product and service areas.

In the introductory part of international standard (ISO 14040, 2009) serving as a framework as mentioned, LCA has been defined as follows (see [Figure 4.1](#)): “LCA addresses the environmental aspects and potential environmental impacts (e.g. use of resources and the environmental consequences of releases) throughout a product’s life cycle from raw material acquisition through production, use, end-of-life treatment, recycling and final disposal (i.e. cradle-to-grave).” A similar definition of LCA was adopted as early as 1993 by the Society of Environmental Toxicology and Chemistry (SETAC, 1993) in their ‘Code of Practice’.

4.1.2 Life cycle of a product

The centre of the LCA is a product, a process, a service or, in the widest sense, a human activity (SETAC, 1993). In an LCA, systems that serve a specific function and therefore have a specified performance are analysed.

“Therefore, the quantified performance (avail) of a product system is the intrinsic

FIGURE 4.1: Simplified life cycle of a tangible product (Walter Klöpffer and Grahl, 2014).

standard of comparison (reference unit). It is the sole correct basis for the definition of a 'functional unit'" (Fleischer and Schmidt, 1996).

4.1.3 Functional unit

To compare tangible products (goods) with *services*, they should have the same or a very similar function. It is, then, essential to note that systems (not products) with matchable functions are compared (Boustead, 1996).

Within an LCA, products are defined as goods and services. As with goods, services require energy, transport, and so on.

4.1.4 System boundary of LCA

Additionally, the system boundary of LCA is one of the factors that requires sensible consideration. To clarify that, the following example indicates how many different approaches for choosing a system boundary are possible.

Example

LCA deals with the comparison of product systems, not of products. This translates to the following:

Within the product segment 'towel dispenser', for example, paper towels and cotton rolls are two possible variations. The cotton roll needs to be cleaned to fulfil its function. This means, the cleansing process (detergent, water and energy consumption) is part of the product system and must surely be considered. In addition, washing machines must be utilised for cleaning.

With in this mind, should the production of washing machines also be considered? Their production requires, for example, steel. Steel is made from iron ore that must be transported, and so on. It is obvious that limitations need to be set, because every small product is linked to the entire industrial system.

On the other hand, nothing essential shall be omitted.

System analysis and the meaningful selection and definition of system boundaries are therefore central and labour-intensive tasks within every LCA. The main advantage of 'from cradle to grave' the life-cycle approach lies in its ability to smoothly detect the shifting of environmental burdens, the so-called *trade-offs*, which may, occur due to material substitutions.

4.1.5 LCA and operational input/output analysis

Gate to gate analysis: If, for instance, the system boundary is set equal to the fence around a factory (gate-to-gate), the fundamental concept of LCA is not satisfied, for neither the production of pre-products nor the disposal of end products have been considered. The same logic occurs regarding (e.g. just in time), outsourcing and parts of waste management activities (e.g. municipal waste water sewage plants).

The next example could offer a better understanding of not-equitable and equitable outsourcing.

Example*Pseudo improvement by outsourcing*

A manufacturer of fine foods intended to not only advertise his products for taste and salubrity but also for environmental aspects. For this purpose, data concerning energy and water consumption was gathered in an operational input–output analysis (gate-to-gate), which allowed the allocation of on-site environmental burdens to the production of different salads. It was striking that potato salad constitute an immense water supply. The reason was that potatoes, usually covered by earth, had to be washed. This waste water was then assigned to the potato salad. Some weeks later, the water supply per kilograms of salad had drastically diminished. This was not due to a technical innovation at the cleaning plant but due to the washing being outsourced to another enterprise. For this reason, washing water was not a factor anymore in the operational input–output analysis within the system boundary of the investigated site.

If, however, all companies involved in the manufacture, distribution and end-of-life management of the product (supply chain) had data from their specific operational input–output analysis in a product-related format, these results could be merged. Nevertheless, product-related data acquisition is not common practice in operational input–output analyses.

4.2 Timeline of LCA

4.2.1 Early LCAs

LCA is a relatively recent methodology, but not as recent as many believe. Approaches to life cycle thinking have already been reported in early literature. In the 1880s the Scottish economist and biologist Patrick Geddes has developed a procedure that can be considered a precursor to Life Cycle Inventory (LCI) (Suter and Walder, 1995). His interest focused on energy supply, especially on coal.

The first LCAs in the modern sense were conducted around 1970, termed *REPA*¹ at Midwest Research Institute in the United States (R. Hunt and Franklin, 1996). As with nearly all early LCAs or ‘proto-LCAs’ (W. Klöpffer, 1994; W. Klöpffer, 1997; W. Klöpffer, 2006), these analysed an analysis of resource consumption and emissions caused by product systems, the so-called inventories without impact assessment. To date, such studies are termed *Life Cycle Inventory studies* (ISO 14040, 2009). The new methodology was first applied to compare beverage packaging. The same applies to the first LCA conducted in Germany (Oberbacher, Nikodem, and W. Klöpffer, 1996) in 1972 under the leadership of B. Oberbacher at Battelle-Institute in Frankfurt, Main. The new method – originally proposed by Franklin and Hunt, USA – additionally captured costs (among others, those of disposal procedures). Interestingly, light polyethylene pouches, already in use at that time, obtained the best results, similar to the results of more recent studies (Schmitz, Oels, and Tiedemann, 1995).

Furthermore, early LCAs were conducted by Ian Boustead in the United Kingdom (Boustead, 1996; Boustead and Hancock, 1979) and Gustav Sundström in Sweden (Lundholm and Sundström, 1985; Lundholm and Sundström, 1986). In addition, Swiss studies, which can be considered as proto-LCAs, date back to the 1970s. They

¹Resource and Environmental Profile Analysis.

were conducted at the EMPA² in St. Gallen; see memories of Paul Fink, former director of the EMPA (Fink, 1997).

4.2.2 Environmental policy background

Why did the development of LCA start in the early 1970s? At least two reasons can be determined:

1. Rising waste problems (therefore, studies into packaging).
2. Bottlenecks in energy supply and acknowledgement of limited resources.

4.2.3 The 1980s

For the first half of the 1980s, studies on LCA were sparse in the German language area. However, one of the few studies is the development of PLA³ by the Ökoinstitut⁴. PLA surpasses LCA as it is based on a needs assessment (NA) analysing the usefulness of a product and consumer behaviour. Here, the product-related environmental analysis is complemented by the investigation of the social aspect (SA) and economical aspect (EA) of the product system:

$$\text{PLA} = \text{NA}^5 + \text{LCA} + \text{SA}^6 + \text{EA}^7$$

with LCA = inventory + environmental impact assessment.

4.2.4 The role of SETAC

From 1990 to 1993 SETAC⁸ and SETAC Europe were leading agents in the development, harmonisation and early standardisation of LCA. Their reports (J.A. Fava et al., 1991; J. Fava, Consoli, et al., 1993; J. Fava, Lindfors, et al., 1994) are part of the most important information sources concerning the development of the methodology.

The greatest achievement of CML⁹ was undoubtedly its heightened focus on the ecological aspects of LCA, compared to the earlier more technical ones. Nevertheless, a prior Swiss LCA had already featured a simple method of impact assessment (BUS, 1984). In practice, the CML method tended to overemphasise chemical releases in the impact assessment.

4.2.5 Energy analysis

The (primary) energy demand summarised through all stages of the life cycle is called *cumulative energy demand* (CED) (VDI-Richtlinie, 1997). Subsection 4.5.7 will discuss this topic through giving an example.

²Swiss Federal Laboratories for Materials Testing and Research.

³Produktlinienanalyse.

⁴Projektgruppe Ökologische Wirtschaft.

⁵Needs assessment.

⁶Social aspect.

⁷Economical aspect.

⁸Society of Environmental Toxicology and Chemistry.

⁹Centrum voor Milieukunde Leiden; the Centre of Environment of University Leiden.

FIGURE 4.2: Analysis of matter and energy of a product system (Walter Klöpffer and Grahl, 2014).

4.3 The Structure of LCA

4.3.1 Structure according to SETAC

Inventory in the context of LCA (LCI) means material and energy analysis of the examined system from cradle to grave. The resulting inventory table contains a list of all material and energy inputs and outputs (see Figure 4.2). These numbers of LCI need an ecological analysis or weighting. Inputs and outputs are sorted according to their impact on the environment. Thus, for instance, all releases into the air causing acid rain are aggregated. This procedure was formerly called *Impact Analysis* by SETAC, and later *Impact Assessment*.

Furthermore, the introduction of improvement assessment was regarded as vast progress because the interpretation of the data was conducted according to specific rules. The Environmental Agency Berlin (UBA) has included this task in 1992 in its recommendation to the conduct of LCAs as an option. The rules for interpretation were later modified during the standardisation process of ISO (see subsection 4.3.2). To date this phase is named *interpretation* (ISO 14040, 2009).

4.3.2 Structure of LCA according to ISO

The phases of LCA have been renamed, compared to earlier structures, and the following terms are now internationally mandatory:

- Goal and Scope Definition
- Life Cycle Inventory Analysis
- Life Cycle Impact Assessment
- Interpretation

The arrows in Figure 4.3 allow an iterative approach that is often necessary.

4.3.3 Valuation – a separate phase?

A valuation is always necessary when the results of a comparative LCA are not straightforward. A trade-off of system A against system B needs to be made when, for example, the former has lower energy consumption, but on the other hand has releases of substances leading to water eutrophication¹⁰ and the formation of near-ground ozone: At this point, it must be questioned which is of greater importance.

¹⁰See section 4.7.1.

FIGURE 4.3: LCA phases according to (ISO 14040, 2009).

For these decisions, subjective and/or normative notions of value are necessary and common in daily life, for example, during purchase decisions (J. Giegrich et al., 1995; W. Klöpffer and Volkwein, 1995; Neitzel, 1997).

These methodological rules were subordinated to the phase Impact Assessment (see also section 4.7).

4.4 Standardisation of LCA

4.4.1 Process of formation

LCA standards ISO 14040 and 14044 belong to the ISO 14000 family concerning various aspects of environmental management (see Figure 4.4). The first series of the international LCA standards closely followed the structure of Figure 4.4:

- ISO 14040: LCA – principles and framework; international standard 2006
- ISO 14041: LCA – goal and scope definition and inventory analysis; international standard 1998
- ISO 14042: LCA – life cycle impact assessment; international standard 2000
- ISO 14043: LCA – interpretation; international standard 2000

4.4.2 State of affairs

The basic standard continues to be called (ISO 14040, 2009) with no mandatory directives. Two technical reports (TRs) and two technical specifications (TSs) have been added:

- ISO/TR 14047:2012 Illustrative example of how to apply ISO 14044 to impact assessment situations.
- ISO/TS 14048:2002 Data documentation format.

FIGURE 4.4: ISO 14000 Model from Normenausschuss Grundlagen des Umweltschutzes (NAGUS) in DIN Deutsches Institut für Normung e. V. (2013).

- ISO/TR 14049:2012 Illustrative examples of how to apply ISO 14044 to goal and scope definition and inventory analysis.
- ISO/TS14067:2013 Carbon footprint of products – requirements and guidelines for quantification and communication.

LCA is therefore the only internationally accepted standardised method for analysing the environmental aspects and potential impacts of product systems.

4.4.3 References and information on LCA

Since 1996, The International Journal of Life Cycle Assessment has been published by eco-med publishers Landsberg/Lech and Heidelberg and, since the beginning of 2008, by Springer and Heidelberg. Current information can be found [here](#)¹¹. The journal has rapidly developed into a leading publication with regards to the promotion of LCA methodology (Heinrich, 2013).

Further journals with regular contributions to LCA are the Journal of Industrial Ecology¹², Cleaner Production¹³ and Integrated Environmental Assessment and Management¹⁴.

4.5 Goal and Scope Definition

4.5.1 Goal definition

While an iterative approach within the standard (ISO 14040, 2009) is explicitly intended (see double arrows in [Figure 4.3](#)), any change of goal or scope must be documented during the conduct of an LCA. The International Standard 14044 reads: “The goal and scope of an LCA shall be clearly defined and shall be consistent with the intended application. Due to the iterative nature of LCA, the scope may have to be refined during the study”.

The goal definition is a declaration made by the organisation (such as companies, industries or trade associations, environmental offices, NGOs, etc.) commissioning an LCA by providing an explanation regarding the following (ISO 14040, 2009):

- Range of application: *What is the objective of the study?*
- Interest of realisation: *Why is an LCA study to be conducted?*
- Target group(s): *For whom will an LCA study be conducted?*
- Publication or other accessibility for the public: *Are comparative assertions intended in the study?*¹⁵

An LCA represents the commissioner’s free will decision and as such shall not be challenged by the critical review.

First an adaptation of the general methodology to the problem in question must be specified. This is achieved by defining the scope of the study.

¹¹ Accessible on the digital version of this thesis.

¹² MIT Press, part of Wiley-Blackwell since 2008.

¹³ Elsevier.

¹⁴ IEAM (SETAC Press).

¹⁵ Comparative assertions in the sense of ISO standards mean that product A under environmental aspects is alike or better than product B; products in the sense of LCA standards are any goods and services.

FIGURE 4.5: Simplified flow chart of the product system PVC window.

4.5.2 Scope: product system

A product system is best described in a system flowchart.

In a system flowchart, unit processes and their interrelations are usually represented by boxes. The entire, often very complex, pattern is reminiscent of a tree and is therefore often called product tree. Since an essentially linear system definition is aimed for, branches occur only at the boxes (by several inputs with pre-chains or by several outputs in waste treatment), but no network. An exception is the treatment of recycling. Within a complete LCA, the presentation ends at the disposal or at a point where co-products, by-products or waste for reutilisation exceed the system boundary (thus leaving the product system).

Here, particular attention should be paid to the LCIA¹⁶, because, compared to mass, very small emissions can nevertheless show large effects. Within comparative LCAs, large parts of the life cycle may be omitted in principle if they match accurately in all systems compared (black box method).

In Figure 4.5, for example, the construction elements on the right of the system boundary (screws, Teflon foil, fittings, etc.) are not considered. This is adequate, if, for instance, different windows (PVC, wood or aluminium windows) are to be compared

¹⁶Life Cycle Inventory Analysis.

with each other and if these construction elements are used similarly in all variants regarded. An estimation of relevance of the omitted sections should nevertheless be made so that the comparison of systems is not based on completely insignificant differences.

Should details in the context of LCI¹⁷ analysis indicate an inadequate description of the product system, the description of the scope must be iteratively modified.

4.5.3 Cut-off criteria

When two studies on a similar topic (e.g. single-use vs reusable packaging) contradict themselves, which may incidentally be the case, usually one or several of the following reasons are responsible:

1. Different methodology
2. Different data quality
3. Different system boundaries

With regard to the first point, great progress has already been made by the International Standardisation. To the second, a uniform data format for databases and data communication has been initiated. To the third criterion, no general presetting can be provided because system boundaries depend on the specific problem in question. In this context, as in LCA everywhere, *transparency* is very important.

Product systems are embedded within the large systems 'technosphere' and 'environment'¹⁸. It is a fundamental realisation of system analysis that all subsystems are linked, even though more or less intensely. To be able to study a subsystem for itself, numerous less important links must be broken. For this, rules are necessary. An important rule states that, for example, the infrastructure (roads, rails, etc.) is usually neglected (although there are important exceptions (R. Frischknecht et al., 2004)). A similar point is true for capital goods (e.g. the production of machines to manufacture the products), provided these are not the ones to be compared in a study.

ISO 14044 states three cut-off criteria applied for the entire product system as well as for individual unit processes:

1. Mass
2. Energy
3. Environmental relevance

Often, a proportion of 1% (mass, energy, etc.) of the overall system is chosen as the cut-off criterion. If a first analysis has, for example, shown that for the manufacture of a product 12 different materials are needed, their percentage ratio is determined in a first step. In the fictitious example of [Table 4.1](#), component ratios (mass) of 5, 6, 9 and 12 are below 1%. The cut-off criterion 'mass < 1%' alone entails that these components are not balanced over their entire life cycle. However, a first estimation of the energy consumption shows that component 9 has a mass ratio of only 0.2%,

¹⁷Life Cycle Inventory.

¹⁸Both together result in the world in which we live; the technosphere, according to this functional definition, is 'everything under human control', and the environment is 'all that is not technosphere' (Frische et al., 1982).

TABLE 4.1: Application of the cut-off criteria ‘mass’ and ‘energy’; Cut-off rules prevent arbitrariness in the choice of system boundaries. Example: Analysing material input.

Inp. descr.	Input Nr.	Mass fraction (%)	Energy (%)
Raw material	1		12.0
Pre-product	2	73.8	54.7
	3		23.3
	4	1.2	0.9
Ancillary material	5	0.1	0.1
	6	0.1	< 0.1
	7	1.7	0.6
	8	1.4	0.7
	9	0.2	2.7
	10	19.8	4.5
	11	1.7	0.4
	12	< 0.1	< 0.1
	13		
Sum		100.0	99.9

although for its production, 2.7% of the total energy is needed. Therefore, component 9 would be examined through its entire life cycle.

Therefore, the sole application of the 1% rule would result in large asymmetries when in a second variant, for example, just 1.5% would be the overall cut-off result. In systems with high energy or mass throughput and a simultaneous long product life-time of the product, the cut-off of less important branches of the product tree, infrastructure and so on, contributing less than 1% related to the entire life cycle is usually without problems (R.G. Hunt, Selleers, and Franklin, 1992). In any case, an error estimation is required.

The cut-off criterion ‘environmental relevance’ is to prevent, for example, the omission of highly toxic emissions (say polychlorinated dibenzodioxins) in the investigated product systems due to too small masses.

4.5.4 System surroundings

The system surrounding¹⁹ is composed by the ecosphere (‘environment’, ‘all that is not technosphere’) plus the large remainder of the technosphere not included in the analysis. The following inputs from the environment are to be considered:

- All processes necessary for the extraction of raw materials (mining industry, oil production, forestry, etc.) belong to the investigated system (‘exploitation of raw materials’).
- In addition, inputs which, due to the cut-off criteria, are not traced over their entire life cycle must be considered (‘miscellaneous’). These inputs may be

¹⁹The system surrounding is often called ‘system environment’, which can be misleading.

pre-products, ancillary material or lubricant produced in the remainder of the technosphere not included in the system under study.

- The entry 'energy' on the input side should actually be named 'energy raw materials', because the energy is produced from fossil, nuclear and regenerating raw materials. Exceptions to this are solar energy, potential energy of water (hydro power) and kinetic energy of wind (wind power). The energy supply, for example in power stations, is within the system boundary.

Co-products

'Usable products' are the products under study, *co-products* and *secondary raw materials*, which remain in the technosphere.

For example, with the production of grain, straw is produced as a co-product that is transferred as the 'usable product' to the system surrounding. In this case, the environmental loads of the processes must be allocated, according to defined rules, both to the examined product and the co-product. Co-products can play a role in different unit processes of a product tree.

Secondary raw material

Secondary raw materials that are gained from waste for reutilisation leave the system and are used as input in other product systems. Recycling of materials, which lead to new products, where the materials thus become parts of other systems, is called *open loop recycling* (R.G. Hunt, Selleers, and Franklin, 1992; Boustead, 1996). A good example of reuse is the refilling of returnable bottles. The system boundary requires further explanations, the most important concern being the geographical and temporal system boundary.

4.5.5 Geographical system boundary

Pollution of the environment also occurs in the countries of origin and in transportation from these. For export products, it must be noted that transportation, use and disposal predominantly take place in other countries. The international distribution of tasks in the context of the progressive globalisation of the world economy (supplier) must also be considered within the geographical system boundary.

4.5.6 Temporal system boundary / time horizon

The minimum specification to the system boundary 'time' is a year of reference or another time period for data acquisition. Accordingly, the modelling of these life cycle phases is difficult and uncertain.

It is unclear how LCA experts can determine (perhaps not even yet invented) methods of waste disposal will dominate in 50 years, how recycling will be organised, and other related queries.

On the side of impact assessment, the so-called *Eigenzeiten*²⁰ and 'rhythms' of ecosystems, which are affected by product systems (Held and Geißler, 1993; Held and Geißler, 1995), are to be considered. Today, it is not yet clear how time can be better

²⁰'Eigenzeit' is difficult to translate; it means a time specific or intrinsic for the system under consideration.

TABLE 4.2: Manual for system analysis.

Step	Descrip.
1	Set up a list of the materials contained in the product.
2	Make a first assessment of materials that may not be examined by their entire life cycle using the cut-off criterion 'mass'.
3	Draw the flowchart and indicate the technical system boundary in your sketch.
4	Make sure that in your flow chart the boxes (unit processes) indicate processes and not substances or materials.
5	Name in further sketches all inputs and outputs qualitatively for each process you considered. Since no detailed research has yet taken place, the degree of detail in this step is dependent on your background knowledge of the processes you defined.
6	Consider usual recycling pathways (open loop and closed loop) in your flowchart.
7	Explain the meaning of 'co-products'.
8	Define the geographical and temporal system boundaries.

integrated into LCA without making the method too complicated.

Statements to the time horizon must be provided at the beginning of the study; if necessary, modifications can be made during the progress of the study. In the initial phase of an LCA, it is always useful to have the product in reality and to weigh individual components, if necessary (see [Table 4.2](#)).

4.5.7 The functional unit

The next example will openly clarify the definition of a functional unit. The example calculates the CED²¹ ([subsection 4.6.3](#) describes the characteristic of the CED). If serious problems already arise within the definition of the fU, this indicates an unsatisfactory understanding of the system, serious data leaks or that LCA may not be a suitable method for solving the individual problem. The quantitative determination of fU and reference flow is, to a certain degree, arbitrary. A length of use time must be included into the description of function. It is important that early in the study, functions and performance of the product systems are correctly defined.

In the next step, the defined fU must be applied to the product variants to be examined, and thus a reference flow of data acquisition be defined.

²¹Cumulative Energy Demand.

Example*CED calculation for floor covering*

For illustration purposes, in the following example CED will be applied for both variants. The CED is the sum of the total energy demand over the entire life cycle regarded (see subsection 4.6.3). The CED for the production of plastic A as a European average may amount to 60 MJ kg^{-1} (under neglect of fillers, floor covering production and disposal). Considering the energy demand for the production of plastic A, the CED amounts to

$$\text{CED} \approx 3.6 \text{ kg m}^{-2} \times 60 \text{ MJ kg}^{-1} = 216 \text{ MJ m}^{-2}$$

A thinner covering of plastic B with $d = 2 \text{ mm}$ and $\rho = 0.9 \text{ g cm}^{-3}$ weighs only

$$2 \text{ mm} \times 0.9 \text{ g cm}^{-3} = 1.8 \text{ kg m}^{-2}$$

so that, despite a higher CED for the production of plastic B of approximately 90 MJ kg^{-1} (same neglects as with plastic A), the CED amounts to

$$\text{CED} \approx 1.8 \text{ kg m}^{-2} \times 90 \text{ MJ kg}^{-1} = 162 \text{ MJ m}^{-2}$$

As is often true, the lighter product would do much better, at least concerning the sum parameter CED, than its heavier counterpart. This is, however, only valid as long as an equal use time is presumed. If, for example, the thicker quality has a longer use time, which is very probable, the result will differ (lifetimes here are hypothetical and do not correspond to any real product performance):

Assumption:

Lifetime of plastic A (thick): 30 a

Lifetime of plastic B (thin): 15 a.

It can be directly deduced from the above example that while two thin coverings are needed (2 millim plastic B) for use over 30 a, only one of the thick covering (3 millim plastic A) is needed. Because the fU must relate to area and time (here: 30 a), the following reference flows result for the two variants, which must form the basis of data acquisition:

$$\text{Plastic A: } 3.6 \text{ kg m}^{-2} \times 1 \Rightarrow 3.6 \text{ kg fU}^{-1}$$

$$\text{Plastic B: } 1.8 \text{ kg m}^{-2} \times 2 \Rightarrow 3.6 \text{ kg fU}^{-1}$$

The reference flow is equal to the mass of the product that corresponds to the fU and is thus the basis for further work in LCA.

Therefore, the CEDs of the two variants amount to

$$\text{CED plastic A (3mm)} = 3.6 \text{ kg fU}^{-1} \times 60 \text{ MJ kg}^{-1} = 216 \text{ MJ fU}^{-1}$$

$$\text{CED plastic B (2mm)} = 3.6 \text{ kg fU}^{-1} \times 90 \text{ MJ kg}^{-1} = 324 \text{ MJ fU}^{-1}$$

The practical problem lies in the determination of realistic use times of long-lived products, including the buildings themselves, which set an upper limit for many building products. If use times as a function of thickness cannot be determined, there can be a way out by restricting the comparison to 'light commodity A versus light commodity B, C, and so on' and to 'heavy commodity A versus heavy commodity B, C, and so on'. It is therefore assumed that lifetimes within the groups are similarly long.

A discussion of the correct use of fUs can be found in Technical Report ISO TR 14049.

In view of the central importance of the fU in LCA, its correct determination has the highest priority. It should be unambiguously feasible in all those cases, where product systems to be compared have the same or a similar performance and fulfil a similar function, respectively.

If within the goal definition, product optimisation has the highest priority, a life cycle stage must not be omitted, under any circumstances.

Should an energy recovery occur within a variant with heating value, it can be considered as a bonus in the Inventory Analysis; not every small difference of performance needs to be considered by system expansion.

4.5.8 Further notes about the goal definition

The data records contain average values of, for example, different refineries or production locations, because with purchase of a polymer, the exact origin of the crude oil molecules from which it was produced cannot be traced. Such data sets are called generic data sets (see [section 6.6](#)).

According to ISO 14044 (see the following quote), the weighting of different impacts and their centralisation to one 'environmental indicator' are illegal for LCAs that are intended to provide comparative assertions to be disclosed to the public: "Weighting ... shall not be used in LCA studies intended to be used in comparative assertions intended to be disclosed to the public."

Critical review

- Are the methods used to carry out the LCA consistent with the international standards ISO 14040/44?
- Are the methods used scientifically and technically valid?
- Is the data used appropriate and reasonable in relation to the goal of the study?
- Does the interpretation reflect the goal of the study and the limitations identified?
- Is the study report transparent and consistent?

Besides these issues that were discussed in a relatively detailed capacity above, the international standard 14044 additionally requires the following specifications for the

task of 'Definition of Goal and Scope':

- Allocation procedures
- Methods for interpretation
- Restrictions
- Type and structure of the report intended

Goal definition

As described, the goal definition must answer questions, which, for every LCA conducted according to ISO 14040/44, ensure the necessary transparency of the framework. These questions are as follows:

- What is the objective of the study?
- Why is an LCA study to be conducted?

Scope and product system

ISO 14040/44 requires the clear exemplification of all methodical rules relevant in an LCA in the phase 'scope definition'.

This is due to transparency being a central requirement for all LCA studies, the product system, on the basis of the goal definition.

4.6 Life Cycle Inventory Analysis

4.6.1 Scientific principles

The revised ISO standard 14040:2020 defines 'life cycle inventory LCI' analysis as follows:

'Inventory analysis involves data collection and calculation procedures to quantify relevant inputs and outputs of a product system.'

LCI is a material and an energy analysis based on a simplified (linear) systems analysis, whereby loops can only be solved approximately by iteration.

LCI in its scientific part – by and large – is based on the following laws of nature (Walter Klöpffer and Grahl, 2014):

1. Conservation of mass
2. Conservation of energy (first principle of thermodynamics); The following applies for the conversion of thermal energy into other forms of energy – part of almost all LCAs – as well as to chemical thermodynamics
3. Increase of entropy (second principle of thermodynamics); Relevant for the explicit examination of chemical reactions (very frequent in LCI analyses, among others for the production and transformation of chemicals and, for example, the determination of CO₂ loads by incineration of fossil fuels)
4. Principles of stoichiometry (basis for all chemical reactions); Transitions of mass into energy and vice versa are only relevant in nuclear reactions, thus providing an exception to the first and second principle

5. $E = mc^2$ (equivalence of mass (m) and energy (E) according to Einstein)²²

These principles (1–5) belong to the scientifically best proven laws and thus provide a solid framework for processes analysed within LCIs (R.G. Hunt, Selleers, and Franklin, 1992; Hau, Yi, and Bakshi, 2007).

How much energy can be released maximally or is required as a minimum for a chemical reaction to take place, how much available ('free') energy can be generated from combustion heat, and so on. Technically achievable yields, efficiencies, and other metrics are almost always smaller than those expected theoretically, and seldom higher. In the context of LCI, this means that in the absence of precise, calculated data, estimates (Boustead and Hancock, 1979) can be made using technical handbooks and manuals, as well as technical knowledge from the Internet²³.

4.6.2 The unit process as the smallest cell of LCI

As a diagram of the examined product system, a system flow chart is made up of small boxes in which the processes are described and their mutual dependencies are shown by one- or two-sided arrows. Unit processes are the small boxes (1, 2, 3, 4 . . . , n, m) that can be used to label the manufacturing or processing steps of a product. These are the smallest elements considered in LCI for which input and output data are quantified, according to (ISO 14040, 2009) (see also Figure 4.6) (Walter Klöpffer and Grahl, 2014).

4.6.3 Cumulative energy demand

The CED is not an impact parameter but an inventory figure. Nevertheless it is used in the study as important information in the interpretation and is therefore specified here.

CED is applied as a category for the evaluation of primary energy. (Walter Klöpffer and Grahl, 2014) describe CED as:

"It is an inventory parameter and represents the sum of the energy content of all primary energy sources, which can be traced back to the system boundaries. 'CED fossil' is the sum of exclusively fossil primary energy sources. The consumption of uranium is assessed by 'CED nuclear'. The computation of 'CED nuclear' is done by an efficiency mark-up of 33% of the electricity generated by nuclear power used by the investigated systems. Besides, the 'CED water power', 'CED renewable' and 'CED other' as well as the 'CED sum' of all CED values as a result of the inventory is listed. 'CED other' is assessed as an energy demand related to data records with no information concerning the type of energy production. 'CED water power' is based on an efficiency of 85%".

4.7 Life Cycle Impact Assessment

"It must be emphasized that these methods of analysis do not indicate that actual impacts will be observed in the environment because of the life cycle of the product or process under study, but only that there is a potential linkage between the product

²²The use of Einstein's equation in LCA as a basis for an estimation of energy equivalence has also been discussed (R. Heijungs and R. Frischknecht, 1998).

²³Greatest care is to be taken to ensure legitimacy of data.

FIGURE 4.6: On the top a linear section of a system flowchart, on the bottom a schematic illustration of a unit process (without co-products).

TABLE 4.3: List of impact categories. Designation according to SETAC Europe (Walter Klöpffer and Grahl, 2014).

List	Impact categories
A	Input-related categories (resource depletion or competition) Abiotic resources (deposits, funds and flow) Biotic resources (funds)
B	Output-related categories (pollution) Global warming (later renamed as climate change) Eutrophication Acidification Depletion potential of the stratospheric ozone layer Formation of photochemical oxidants

or process life cycle and the impacts (Heijungs and Guinée, 1993).”

Table 4.3 shows an elaboration of the list of impact categories by a team of experts of the SETAC Europe chaired by ‘Helias Udo de Haes’ with the prospect of integration into regulations of the LCIA. An interrelation of these impacts and endpoints differing for each category is schematically illustrated in Figure 4.7 (Walter Klöpffer and Grahl, 2014).

4.7.1 Output-based impact categories

Global warming potential

A rise in the average temperature near the Earth’s surface is the primary consequence of the *global warming* potential (including the lower troposphere and the surface water of the oceans). This impact group was formerly (and still is sometimes) known as global warming, but that term does not accurately describe the primary influence or the aggregation of the subsequent sequels (Walter Klöpffer and Grahl, 2014).

A course for a relative scale of the impact is needed for an impact assessment in an LCA. It will allow for the conversion of methane, nitrous oxide, carbon dioxide, and chlorofluorocarbon (CFC) refrigerant emissions against one another. It applies to GWPs: they show the mass of CO₂ that has the same effect as 1 kg of another GHG released. However, since different GHGs have varying tropospheric lifetimes (methane with a tropospheric lifetime of about 10 a is generally short-lived), simulations must have a *time horizon* indicating the calculation’s validity span. For LCAs a time horizon of 100 a is usually chosen (Walter Klöpffer and Grahl, 2014).

CO₂ is the dominant contribution to the overall GWP/fU in most LCA studies. For a calculation of the GWP from the inventory, only the CO₂ that originates from fossils (incineration of coal, oil, etc.) and minerals (calcination of lime, production of cement) are considered, and therefore have to be separately assigned. CO₂ from biological sources should also be assigned separately. This amount is extracted from the atmosphere by photosynthesis a relatively short time ago and will again be released into the atmosphere by incineration or aerobic degradation. Such emissions are often called *CO₂-neutral*, though this is true only over a sufficiently long timescale. The

FIGURE 4.7: Impact category, classification/characterisation and assignment of end points (schematic): following the characterisation framework according to ISO CD 14042.3. Reproduced from (Walter Klöpffer and Grahl, 2014).

TABLE 4.4: Global warming potential (GWP_{100}) of some greenhouse gases (time horizon: 100 a). Data selection from IPCC fifth assessment report (2014).

Common name of the GHG	Life time in the troposphere (a)	GWP_{100} (kg CO ₂ -eq per kg GHG)
Carbon dioxide (CO ₂)	Determined according to Berne C-cycle (can not be described by a single value)	1
Methane (CH ₄)	12.0	28
Nitrous oxide (N ₂ O)	120	265

calculation of biogenic C-flow should not be omitted because the investigation of a credible C-balance must be ensured and documented transparently (Walter Klöpffer and Grahl, 2014).

The total GWP per fU is the sum of CO₂ equivalents which are calculated by a multiplication of GHG loads (m_i per fU) from the inventory, and the respective GWP_i :

$$GWP = \sum_i^n (m_i \times GWP_i) \quad m_i = \text{load of the respective substance } i \text{ per fU} \quad (4.1)$$

The GWP mainly selected for LCAs is GWP_{100} (see Table 4.4). If in an impact assessment, several time horizons are used, it must be ensured that only GWPs of the same time horizon are used in the summing up according to Equation 4.1. GWPs of various time horizons of very long-lived GHGs only differ slightly; therefore, the life times in Table 4.4 are to be considered.

GWP values should be adopted from the latest IPCC or WMO report or from recent secondary literature.

When global warming is used as the only impact category in an LCA-type analysis, the GWP is commonly referred to as a carbon footprint. Such studies may be used to estimate a material system's, process, company's, or country's contribution to CO₂-regulations like the Kyoto Protocol, CO₂-certificate trading, and so on. The name is catchy, but is a misnomer since carbon is a chemical element without which existence would be impossible (and therefore it cannot be harmful in and of itself). There are some powerful GHGs that do not contain carbon (N₂O; SF₆; NF₃). A separate standardisation of CF is nevertheless meaningful, since the international standards ISO 14040 + 14044 do not describe in detail how the $GWP = CF$ has to be determined (Walter Klöpffer and Grahl, 2014).

Furthermore, a life cycle assessment with only one impact category is not and will never be an (environmental) LCA, far less a life cycle sustainability assessment (LCSA). A low CF per fU may be overcompensated by other environmental and social risks and impacts, like nuclear electricity production (Walter Klöpffer and Grahl, 2014).

Depletion potential of the stratospheric ozone layer

Another global impact category concerns the human-caused depletion of the stratospheric ozone layer responsible for shielding short-wavelength solar radiation below 290-300 nm from the Earth's surface (WMO, 1999). Ozone molecules of low concentration in the stratosphere but within a large layer (about 20 km) are in a dynamic equilibrium of formation and decomposition (Chapman cycle; Equation 4.2 and Equation 4.3). High energy UV radiation plays a vital part in this dynamic process:

Formation of stratospheric ozone:

Photolysis:

Besides these, there are numerous ozone-forming and -degrading reactions in the stratosphere with trace components of the HO_x and NO_x 'family' (B. Finlayson-Pitts and J. Finlayson-Pitts, 1986).

With the introduction of supersonic airplanes in the 1980s, there were concerns about increased ozone depletion. The reason for this was nitrogen oxides being released into the lower stratosphere by aeroplanes. An extension of this work (Molina and Rowland, 1974; Rowland and Molina, 1975) to the newly formed chlorine cycle by Rowland and Molina in 1974 and 1975 resulted in postulating causality between refrigerants, persistent spraying agents, and other factors (freons, CFC), as well as an additional ozone depletion based on reasonable evidence and assumptions:

Chlorine cycle of catalytic ozone depletion:

The chlorine atom in Equation 4.4 necessary for the initiation of the cycle derives from photolysis of long-lived (persistent) chlorine compounds of anthropogenic origin that, due to their persistence, are capable of entering the stratosphere intact, especially as a result of an extremely slow reaction with OH-radicals (R. Atkinson, 1986; Klöpffer and Wagner, 2007).

Rowland and Molina's work elicited a strong and immediate response. (James E Lovelock, Maggs, and Wade, 1973)'s few measurements of freon concentrations in the atmosphere were repeatedly checked and revised. There was a general upward trend in freon or CFC concentrations, especially for the most important ones (J. Lovelock, 1975) : trichlorofluoromethane (CFC 11 R11), dichlorodifluoromethane (CFC-12, R12), and 1,1,2-trichloro-1,2,2-trifluoroethane (CFC-113, R113). However, some chlorinated solvents that were not considered freons were identified as possible ozone-depleting substances and so subjected to a long series of analytical tests.

Causing substances of freons were and still are partly used (in medicine) for the following products:

- Propellant for sprays
- Propellant for foam materials (e.g. polyurethanes)

- Refrigerant for refrigerators and smaller air conditioning systems (especially for cars)
- Cleaning agent (e.g. in the electronic industry)
- Smaller applications in medicine (asthma spray), analytic and spectroscopy (extraction agent, solvent for IR spectroscopy), and so on.

The accumulation of chlorine (and bromine) atoms in the stratosphere through photolysis of volatile and persistent substances with chlorine or bromine as a substituent is the effect predictor for the category 'stratospheric ozone depletion.' This description of the impact indicator includes both the ozone depletion expected by (Molina and Rowland, 1974; Rowland and Molina, 1975) in the homogeneous gaseous phase of the stratosphere (though it received little public attention) and a dramatic yet temporally and spatially restricted depletion related to the ozone hole (Walter Klöpffer and Grahl, 2014).

An ODP value was introduced for the quantification of a relative scale of ozone-harmful activities of substances. It literally reads (WMO, 1999): "The ODP represents the amount of ozone destroyed by emission of a gas over the entire atmospheric lifetime (i.e. at steady state) relative to that due to emission of the same mass of CFC-11."

The quantification (characterisation) of the impact category stratospheric ozone depletion results from ODP values as equivalence factors similar to those of the GWP:

$$ODP = \sum_i^n (m_i \times ODP_i) \quad (4.5)$$

The load of the ozone-depleting gases per fU (m_i) can be taken from the inventory table and appropriate ODP_i values from respective charts of the WMO.

Acidification

The inclusion of the impact category 'acidification' can be related to the following environmental problem areas:

- Acidification of unbuffered waters
- Damage to forests
- Acidification of soils

In the first example, which has been observed in particular in the crystalline area of South Scandinavia (Fabian, 1992), a direct causal chain between emissions and impact can be assumed. Acid precipitation turned freshwater lakes on granite bedrock in the south of Norway and Sweden into diluted acids. Al^{3+} ions, which are poisonous to marine organisms, dissolve from aluminium silicates when exposed to acids. At typical pH levels (around 5.5–6; unbuffered equilibrium with CO_2 in the troposphere), these ions are absent. Most species in these normally shallow lakes are extinguished by aluminum ions, the acid itself, and probably other dissolved materials. A chemical analysis of precipitation at various times in Scandinavia revealed a connection between wind direction and acid load. Winds from the United Kingdom and the Continent still brought the highest loads. Acidification was mostly caused by

power plants in Europe. A deceptive ‘policy of high chimneys’ was directed solely at pollutant dilution. Improvements in air purification technology gradually improved air quality, especially in terms of SO₂ (Walter Klöpffer and Grahl, 2014).

An acidification of waters that can be observed in Scandinavia is typical for all scarcely buffered surface waters, partly and indirectly also for the groundwater of the crystalline rock, which comes into contact with air masses from industrial areas. Part of the acid-forming gases also originates from agriculture. To these, belongs the base ammonia, which by oxidation is transformed into NO_x, which in the end reacts with water in an oxidising environment to become nitric acid. NH₃ and NH₄⁺ which, respectively enter soil and waters, are oxidised by bacterial nitrification and contribute to acidification.

A second environmental area related to acidification is the so-called novel damage to the forest. While direct damage to vegetation by acid gases has been known for 150 a (Stoklasa, 1923)—so to speak acute phytotoxic impacts by high concentration of acid gases—these novel damages have only been studied since around 1970. As early as at the end of the 1980s, it was concluded that novel damages of forests²⁴ were a multifactorial illness caused by various stress factors, the most important of these being air pollutants (Krahl-Urban et al., 1988).

- Sulphur dioxide(SO₂) | oxidation to sulphuric acid (H₂SO₄)
- Nitric oxides(NO_x) | oxidation to nitric acid(HNO₃)
- Ammonia (NH₃) | oxidation to NO_x and nitric acid
- Hydrofluoric acid (HF)
- Hydrogen chloride/hydrochloric acid (HCl)
- Photo oxidants (ozone, peroxyacetyl nitrate, ...)
- Organic compounds which only form in the troposphere by reaction with OH and NO_x

The details of the corresponding impacts are so far unknown. A simple conversion factor for novel forest damage is not possible because of the complexity of the symptoms and insufficient knowledge of the cause and effect relationship. Damaging impacts caused by acid gases, including the base ammonia, are handled by an *acidification potential* (AP) (Reinout Heijungs, Jeroen B Guinée, et al., 1992; H. A. U. d. Haes, Bovy, et al., 1996; H. A. U. d. Haes, Olivier Jolliet, et al., 1999). Other contributions are covered in the category of photo oxidants.

Acidification (current impact category) and over-fertilisation of low nutrition soils must be distinguished from one another. Further impacts caused by acidification are the washing out of nutritive substances (e.g. K⁺, Na⁺ and Mg²⁺) plus the mobilisation of heavy metals. Both can induce damage to vegetation. Furthermore, heavy metals that are washed out can pollute ground waters.

The impact category ‘acidification’ has been chosen in (ISO 14044, 2006) as an example to describe an approach corresponding to standards:

²⁴In German: ‘neuartige Waldschäden’; this rather vague expression was created after the realisation that acidification alone could not be the reason. It slowly replaced the older term ‘Waldsterben’ (dying of the forests) used mainly in the popular press.

- LCI results: Example; SO_2 , HCl, HF, and so on (kg per fU).
- LCI results assigned to impact category (classification): emissions with an acidifying impact, for example, NO_x , SO_2 , and so on, are assigned to the impact category acidification.
- Category indicator, characterisation model: release of protons (H_{aq}^+); calculation of AP equivalents (mostly as SO_2 -eq).
- Impact endpoints (see also [Figure 4.7](#)): acid-related damages on aquatic ecosystems, forests, vegetation, buildings, works of art, and so on.

Quantification by an AP as proposed by (Reinout Heijungs, Jeroen B Guinée, et al., 1992) starts on top of a stressor-effect-chain and 'counts' protons per fU as SO_2 equivalents, occasionally also as mass or mole of protons. The impact indicator of this simple model is the acid formation from precursor compounds and a successive entry of acid through water, whereby a total dissociation of the acid into protons and the respective anions is presumed. This is a very good approximation for strong acids, however weak acids can also shift basic milieus (e.g. sea water) in the direction of the neutral point (pH 7). This is often called *acidification* in spite of it being a mere reduction of alkalinity (but even that is dangerous for many marine organisms whose shells start to dissolve around the neutral point).

The AP is a typical *midpoint* (see [Figure 4.7](#)) indicator which neither names nor models endpoints. The endpoints as an entirety, however, are considered in the interpretation because the potential of acidification may cause numerous endpoints. Characterisation factors are calculated according to the stoichiometry of the formation of acid from precursors. Sulphur dioxide is a precursor of the two-base acid H_2SO_3 (sulphurous acid) formed by solution in water of the gas SO_2 . Because it can only produce one mol of protons (by dissolution+oxidation from NO_x), 1 mol HNO_3 thus corresponds to half a mole of sulphur dioxide, which produces 2 mol of protons following dissolution in water. It is not important that sulphurous acid is a relatively weak acid since in the environment it oxidises into very strong sulphuric acid (H_2SO_4).

It should be noted that the weak carbonic acid, formed by the dissolution of CO_2 in surface waters, especially the oceans, has never been included in the list of acidifying substances. It is actually the most relevant acid globally, but only one negative consequence of this gas is included in the impact category 'climate change' and the acidification potential is not considered.

As an alternative to mass equivalents mol protons were proposed for characterisation, which is chemically better justified. To ensure consistency with other impact categories, (Walter Klöpffer and Grahl, 2014) propose the ability to segregate protons as an indicator, and SO_2 kilogram equivalents as a characterisation factor. These can be easily, and above all unambiguously, calculated according to the laws of stoichiometry. The most important characterisation factors are listed in [Table 4.5](#). Very weak acids as, for example, carbonic acid (H_2CO_3 and its anhydride CO_2 , respectively) are not included in the calculation of the AP in spite of their strong contribution to the acidification of the seas (see above). In view of the decreasing pH-values of the oceans, characterisation factors for H_2CO_3 and CO_2 should also be included (separately calculated if meaningful) (WBGU, 2006). Organic acids, mainly weak acids, are currently also not assigned to the AP. Strong organic acids (e.g. TCA) should be

TABLE 4.5: Acidification potential (AP) of some gaseous emissions. Reproduced from (Reinout Heijungs, Jeroen B Guinée, et al., 1992; *Methodik der Wirkungsbilanz in Rahmen von Produkt-Ökobilanzen unter Berücksichtigung nicht oder nur schwer quantifizierbarer Umwelt-Kategorien / Umweltbundesamt n.d.*; G. Norris et al., 2001).

Release (compound)	Formula	AP (kg SO ₂ -eq)
Sulphur dioxide	SO ₂	1
Sulphur trioxide	SO ₃	0.08
Nitrogen monoxide	NO	1.07
Nitrogen dioxide	NO ₂	0.70
Nitrogen oxides (calculated as NO ₂)	NO _x	0.70
Nitric acid	HNO ₃	0.51
Ammonia	NH ₃	1.88
Phosphoric acid	H ₃ PO ₄	0.98
Sulphuric acid	H ₂ SO ₄	0.65
Organic acids	R-COOH	None at present
Carbon dioxide (carbonic acid)	CO ₂	None at present

assigned for the calculation of the AP in future. The impact category is converted into an AP according to the values listed in Table 4.5 or to equivalence factors, which can easily be determined stoichiometrically for every defined (strong) acid, and is then aggregated:

$$AP = \sum_i^n (m_i \times AP_i) \quad \text{kg SO}_2 - \text{equivalents} \quad (4.6)$$

where m_i = load of the substance contributes to acidification per fU.

The AP from the point of view of its simple and unambiguous determination is ideally suited for impact assessment. From the impact side, it may be doubtful whether, for example, acid gases released into oceans (SO₂ from crude oil of vessels!) are relevant in view of the alkaline buffering capability of the oceans. However, a recommendation not to consider emissions into the ocean as different from those released into the continental atmosphere is based on the precautionary principle (here: less is better). First, we know nothing of the impact of sulphur dioxide on stressed oceanic ecosystems; second, emission of gases by open sea vessels can drift for large distances along their routes, mostly along the coasts: third, an incentive to use purer oil should be provided. This would also diminish the high SO₂ load in harbours. Finally, it can also be presumed that during the incineration of low-quality bunker oil, numerous other pollutants are formed.

From the point of view of environmental politics, it can be noted that the presumed correlation between acid gases and forest damage in the 1980s introduced significant efforts to flue gas purification, especially in power plants. This has led to a substantial overall reduction of the SO₂ load. It is more difficult to remove NO_x from incineration gases. This is why the efforts to reduce the nitrogen oxides, which are not only acidifying but also eutrophying, toxic and additionally induce the formation of smog,

show much slower success. NO_x is not only released by chimneys of power plants high into the air, but also has sources near the surface, for example, car traffic.

Eutrophication

Eutrophication can best be translated as the over-fertilisation or excess supply of nutrients. The impact category eutrophication is listed in every LCA but at closer look poses some difficulties (*Methodik der Wirkungsbilanz in Rahmen von Produkt-Ökobilanzen unter Berücksichtigung nicht oder nur schwer quantifizierbarer Umwelt-Kategorien / Umweltbundesamt n.d.*; H. A. U. d. Haes, Bovy, et al., 1996; H. A. U. d. Haes, Olivier Jolliet, et al., 1999; G. Finnveden, J. Potting, et al., 2001; Göran Finnveden and José Potting, 1999; Jeroen B Guinée and Erwin Lindeijer, 2002).

The substances that cause eutrophication are more accurately described as plant nutrients than pollutants. As a first impact, its surplus implies a forced photosynthetic increase in biomass (growth of plants, especially algae). Changes in this supply lead to changes in the ecosystem's species spectrum.

The absorption of oxygen by bacteriological degradation of dead biomass is a significant secondary effect in water bodies. A significant increase in algae growth results in more extinct biomass at the bottom of the water body, which decays and changes the character of a lake or estuary. For example: a formerly clean lake with drinking water quality may evolve into water with an anoxic (oxygen-free) depth layer. The composition of species changes as the oxygen content is reduced. In extreme situations, an unfavourable anaerobic environment develops.

The impact assessment can be differentiated between aquatic eutrophication (eutrophication in the original sense) and terrestrial eutrophication or over-fertilisation²⁵. Gases like NO_x and NH_3 (terrestrial eutrophication) and substances in the effluent of wastewater sewage plants, which have not been completely decomposed or removed, are considered as well as untreated wastewater entries into water bodies (aquatic eutrophication).

Aquatic Eutrophication An entry of nutrients into water bodies can occur both by the water path and by air.

The most important nutrients for plants are the elements *phosphor* and *nitrogen* in a resorbable nutrition compound, primarily as water soluble salts. Gaseous nitrogen from the air can only be used by some 'specialised' plants like legumes in symbiosis with nodule bacteria. The impact assessment only considers compounds suited for uptake by plants and only these must be integrated into the inventory. Other elements important for plant nutrition like potassium, copper (high concentrations are toxic!) and other trace elements are not integrated into the impact assessment. Phosphor is the limiting²⁶ element in most freshwater bodies (surface water like lakes and rivers as well as groundwater) whereas in seawater nitrogen is generally the limiting element. Estuaries and brackish waters can be either P- or N-limited. Terrestrial ecosystems are mostly N-limited. These differences can only be considered in the

²⁵'Fertilisation' should not be misunderstood in an agricultural (intended) context, although agricultural wastes, increased run-off, and so on can (unintended) contribute to eutrophication.

²⁶If a shortage of a limiting element occurs even an overdose of other substances necessary for growth cannot produce biomass. The same applies for special amino acids in the food of animals.

impact assessment with geographically highly resolved inventory data. Without doubt, phosphorus and nitrogen are the highest contributors to the impact category eutrophication.

The former impact category 'chemical oxygen demand' has been integrated as an indicator for nutrients into the impact category 'eutrophication'. As a matter of fact, organic compounds that are biologically degradable under consumption of oxygen are better characterised by the *biochemical* oxygen demand (BOD) but the data availability of COD is much better and the BOD is included in the COD. As a result of aerobic bacterial degradation of organic compounds (particular or dissolved), the oxygen concentration decreases and the CO₂ concentration and the concentration of inorganic nutrient salts increase. The impact of an increased entry of these organic compounds, into the waters is therefore comparable to an over-fertilisation with P- and N-containing compounds followed by increased growth of algae.

Heat released by power plants into waters can have a qualitatively similar impact: bacterial degradation processes of organic matter are speeded up. Furthermore, different species compared to those of cooler waters are favoured. Keywords like eutrophication, BOD and heat have been included within one impact category by SETAC Europe (H. A. U. d. Haes, Bovy, et al., 1996).

An attempt can be made to comprise eutrophication and BOD or COD as one indicator; however, heat cannot be included. It has to be assigned and assessed separately, if relevant, in the study under consideration, as for instance for thermal power plants. Experience shows that heat is never an impact category of its own, nor nearly ever integrated as indicator into the eutrophication category.

Following the precautionary principle for a calculation of the aquatic eutrophication potential (EP) or *nutrification potential* (NP), it is presumed that every unintended nutrient supply to the environment, contrary to targeted fertilisation in the technosphere, can imply over-fertilisation. Neither the local situation nor pre-existing pollution loads of the site are considered. As a basic idea behind the scenes it is presumed that loads caused by humans, no matter whether by nutrient or pollutant overload, can have a damaging or at least an unintended impact on the environment. This is in accordance with experience: eutrophic lakes, unrestricted growth of algae in the estuaries and over-fertilisation of forests in case of terrestrial eutrophication (forest soils are generally nutrient-poor).

A specification of a relative fertilisation effect of P and N is at the centre of the definition of an equivalent or characterisation model. Derivations of factors are based on an average composition of algae biomass according to the relation C:N:P=106: 16: 1, named Redfield-ralation (Redfield, 1934) due to its revelation by Alfred Redfield (1890 – 1983), valid to a surprising accuracy in Deep Oceans:

A question arises with respect to the contribution of a nutritive substance (X) to the formation of algae biomass by photosynthesis if it contains the limiting element and if all other elements in biologically available forms are presumed to be abundantly present.

With this definition of EP, values of all P- and N-containing compounds can unambiguously be stoichiometrically calculated. This directness is the charm of the method

TABLE 4.6: Eutrophication potential (EP) of important emissions. Reproduced from (Reinout Heijungs, Jeroen B Guinée, et al., 1992; J. Fava, Lindfors, et al., 1994; *Methodik der Wirkungsbilanz in Rahmen von Produkt-Ökobilanzen unter Berücksichtigung nicht oder nur schwer quantifizierbarer Umwelt-Kategorien / Umweltbundesamt n.d.*).

Emission (Entry path)	Formula	EP (kg PO_4^{3-} - eq)
Nitrogen monoxide (air)	NO	0.20
Nitrogen dioxide (air)	NO ₂	0.13
Nitrogen oxides (air)	NO _x	0.13
Nitrate (water)	NO ₃ ⁻	0.1
Ammonium (water)	NH ₄ ⁺	0.33
Nitrogen	N	0.42
Phosphate	PO ₄ ³⁻	1
Phosphor (water)	P	3.06
Chemical oxygen demand (COD)	As O ₂	0.022

which disregards all local restrictions and derives a potential impact – similar to an AP – from the chemical formula alone. Of course it has to be reassessed with scientific prudence whether the regarded compound that can actually provide the nutritive element is biologically available! There is no taking into account of the regional composition of the water bodies or of observed discrepancies in the Redfield-relation.

For the sake of descriptiveness the EP refers to 1kg PO_4^{3-} Table 4.6. This definition on phosphate equivalents is arbitrary, like the choice of SO₂ as reference substance for an AP or the choice of CO₂ for the GWP of the greenhouse effect.

By simply equating the EP and the phosphate equivalents according to Table 4.6 the following is valid:

$$EP = \sum_i^n (m_i \times EP_i) \quad \text{kg } PO_4^{3-} \text{ - equivalents} \quad (4.8)$$

where m_i = load of the substance contributing to eutrophication per fU.

Terrestrial eutrophication The characterisation according to Equation 4.8 does not differentiate between aquatic and terrestrial eutrophication and therefore represents the simplest method. The advantage of clarity of this computation is a result of strong simplifications on the impact side. Therefore, attempts have been made to sacrifice part of the simplicity for an approach to reality, for example, by the 'Nordic Guidelines' (J. Fava, Lindfors, et al., 1994). A division of the impact category into aquatic and terrestrial seems to be the most promising (J. Fava, Lindfors, et al., 1994). As most emissions into the inland air are deposited on soils, emissions into air of compounds containing N, mostly as NO_x and NH₃, are the most important input to the soil and can therefore be assigned to terrestrial eutrophication.

Formation potential of tropospheric ozone photochemical oxidants

The photochemical smog (= photo smog), also called *summer smog* or *Los Angeles Smog* has a history of about 60 years to correlate to the air in California, particularly in the region of Los Angeles (McCABE et al., 1952). High motorisation following a *de facto* removal of rail traffic, high intensities of solar radiation and geographical conditions hindering the exchange of air masses (inversion weather conditions) are the ideal basis for the formation of photochemical smog.

For the formation of summer smog the following circumstances are thus necessary:

1. Intense solar radiation with a high UV contribution
2. Reactive nitrogen oxides NO_x (= $\text{NO} + \text{NO}_2$)
3. Reactive volatile organic compounds (VOC, especially alkenes) and/or CO.

The impact indicator of the category 'summer smog' is the formation of photo smog mostly measured by the formation of the leading substance of ozone (U. d. Haes et al., 2002; G. A. Norris, 2002; G. Norris et al., 2001). A list of characterisation factors is used for a quantification following similar considerations as the original list of (Darnall et al., 1976), but on the basis of model calculations. The *photochemical ozone creation potential* (POCP) of ethene serves as reference, which is arbitrarily set to one. Table 4.7 lists a selection of POCP values (G. Norris et al., 2001). The calculation of the less recent values is achieved according to three scenarios valid for Europe and for a time horizon of 9 days (ECE, 1991). The values by (Labouze et al., 2004) (Table 4.7 'POCP_{mean}') refer to an average daily ozone concentration from 0 to 2.2 km height, neglecting limit values for the environment and human health. Calculations considering those limits have also been accomplished but are not listed. The relative sequence of organic pollutant classes remains unchanged for various types of calculation. However, the POCP of NO_x (as NO_2), according to (Labouze et al., 2004), strongly depends on the fundamentals of the calculations (POCP: 0.27–0.95 ethene equivalents). Values averaged in space and time are graded as complementary to the values by (Derwent et al., 1998) as they are independent of meteorological conditions and emissions at a given time; they are valid for Europe only. They are usually below the values of Derwent because they were deduced for average atmospheric conditions, not for conditions that promote smog formation.

In the context of a uniform impact category for the formation of photooxidants, the quantification of the impact indicator is accomplished as follows with the help of the POCP characterisation factors:

$$POCP = \sum_i^n (m_i \times POCP_i) \quad \text{kg ethene equivalents} \quad (4.9)$$

where m_i = load of the substance i involved in summer smog formation per fU.

4.7.2 Input-related impact categories

This group of impact categories aimed at the preservation and sparing use of natural resources. According to (SETAC, 1993) this group includes:

- Abiotic resources

TABLE 4.7: POCP (kg of ethene equivalents per kg) of some substances after (Environmental Toxicology and Chemistry, 1996; Derwent et al., 1998; Labouze et al., 2004). Update from the CML-AI database of University Leiden.

Substance class	Emission (formula)	CML
Alkanes	Methane (CH_4)	0.007
	Ethane (C_2H_6)	0.082
Olefins (alkenes)	Ethene (C_2H_4)	1
	Propene (C_3H_6)	1.03
Alcohols	Methanol (CH_3OH)	0.12
	Ethanol (C_2H_5OH)	0.27

TABLE 4.8: Systematic of resources

Type of resources	Examples
Abiotic finite	Minerals, fossil raw materials
Abiotic regenerative	Groundwater, surface (fresh) water; oxygen ; not however: fossil groundwater
Biotic finite	Tropical wood from primary forests, species threatened by extinction
Biotic regenerative	Wild plants, wild animals (e.g. Sea fish); not however: agricultural and forestry products and fish from fish farms, since these products are generated within the technosphere

- Biotic resources
- Land use

This study will discuss only the first two impact categories. These first two impact categories can be divided into finite and regenerative resources, depending on their regenerative capacity (see Table 4.8).

As indicated by their name, and common to all categories of this group, inventory data to be classified and characterised occurs at the input side. Therefore, they concern raw materials and similar factors in the ecosphere, which are used, dispersed, stained or converted for the production of chemicals, materials and goods, fuels, and so on. As the overarching notion for these different uses, the expression 'consumption' is employed. It does not strictly apply physically or chemically, it does apply if the appropriate raw materials are regarded as economic goods (see for example the commonly used expression 'energy consumption' which physically makes no sense)²⁷. The characterisation of resource consumption is one in view of the *scarceness, regeneration ability and significance for the ecosystems*.

A comprehensive representation of resources within LCIA is yet to be achieved. An overview of the suggested characterisation factors as well as an attempt at a

²⁷Apart from Einstein's $E = mc^2$.

uniform treatment of resources in view of functionality and quality (with respect to quality reduction) has been published²⁸ by (Stewart and Bo Pedersen Weidema, 2005). However, in addition to a uniform representation, fundamental differences between plantation forests and jungles, breeding and wild animals, and so on, were not considered. There are also no *back-up technologies*²⁹, such as for extinct species, as requested by this method. With regards to the metallic resources a concern for quality (of the deposits) is adequate as once they are extracted they are not really consumed, but rather dispersed (if not recycled).

Abiotic depletion potential

Abiotic resources considered in LCIA are:

- Fossil fuels (oil, natural gas, hard coal and lignite in deposits); spatial reference: predominantly global (by worldwide trade), for lignite predominantly regional.
- Uranium ores (in deposits); spatial reference: global.
- Mineral raw materials (ores, sand, clay, gravel, limestone, rock salt, phosphates, etc.); spatial reference: global (ores) to local (sand, gravel, etc.).
- (Fresh) water; spatial reference: local to regional (is not traded on worldwide basis).
- Air and its components; Spatial reference: global (by the nature of the atmosphere).

Impact metrics and characterisation models were created for output-based impact categories and are meant to provide a quantitative relationship between the data collected in the inventory and possible negative consequences. A transition of these models to assessment tools (in this case, abiotic resources) requires first an answer to the question: what is the typical effect, followed by the creation of a quantitative model that is as easy as possible. This widespread impact is resource scarcity, which will first affect the technosphere through a rise in raw material prices. In the ecosphere, excessive water use will lower the groundwater table, causing changes in biodiversity, generated biomass, and, in extreme cases, steppe formation or desertification, a fundamental shift in the original ecological structure. Since endpoint modeling is difficult due to the need to account for future events and circumstances, shortage or scarcity is used as a mid-point indicator. For both cases – finite or non-regenerative and regenerative, respectively – the weighting factors described below attempt a quantitative overview. The characterisation factors are based on the weighting factors.

The simplest model for the exhaustion of non-renewable abiotic resources relates consumption per fU to the total reserves:

$$\frac{\sum_i^n \text{Consumption}_i (\text{kgfE}^{-1})}{\text{Reserves}_i (\text{kg})} \quad (4.10)$$

This formula however does not consider that even small reserves can practically be inexhaustible if the total consumption (not only for the examined product system) is accordingly small. Moreover, enormous reserves will be quickly exhausted with a

²⁸See also [University of St.Gallen](#).

²⁹Techniques, which serve the re-establishment of a condition before human interference.

very large total consumption.

A more accurate model will calculate the scarcity as follows: consumption of resources that will be consumed in 100 years assuming current overall consumption should be rated twice as scarce as resources that will be exhausted in 200 years assuming constant overall consumption. The quotient of reserves and consumption per time unit [Equation 4.11](#) for a nonrenewable resource is the available time ('static range') if annual consumption remains constant despite increasing scarcity:

$$\frac{\text{World reserves}(kg \text{ or } J)}{\text{World annual consumption}(kg a^{-1} \text{ or } J a^{-1})} \quad (4.11)$$

Energetically usable resources can be indicated in energy units (J, MJ, ...) or mass units (kg, t, ...); with natural gas also, a volume unit (Nm³) is used. Here unfortunately the barrel must be mentioned: the quantity of crude oil is often reported in the outdated (US) volume unit (Barrel, 159 l).

Chapter 5

Embodied Energy

5.1 Introduction

On a disciplinary level, considering façade planning in terms of its embodied energy is an important way to question broad binary notions of form/formlessness, stability/unstability, mechanical/biological, inert/alive, and hard/soft. Eben Bayer highlights this potential in his essay ‘The Future Will Be Biofabricated’ in (Benjamin, 2017), in which he discusses the specific issue of embodied energy under the broader umbrella of energy itself, contrasting the efficacy of biological energy—animal and non-animal to the production of mechanical energy. Bayer illustrates the possibility inherent in deploying a complexity even beyond our understanding by using the cheetah as an example of a biological entity capable of propelling itself with exponential efficiency compared to the steam engine (Benjamin, 2017).

Buildings consume approximately 40% of global energy annually in their life cycle stages of construction, use, repair, and demolition, demonstrating how planning by binary notions has been drying up energy consumption. Buildings absorb energy in a main (e.g. natural gas, oil) or delivered (e.g. electricity) form (Manish K. Dixit, Fernández-Solís, et al., 2010; Marszal et al., 2010). According to (Gupta, 2009), the energy used to operate a building in the United Kingdom accounts for nearly half of the country’s total energy consumption.

The concept of embodied energy invites façade engineers to consider the building as an active, absorptive mechanism, the presence of which is only a temporary suspension of material flows, as writes Blaine Brownell in his essay ‘Inventive Matter’ in (Benjamin, 2017). He also discusses how his colleagues’ work in ‘*Ecovative*’ on gaining control of biological processes can be motivating for a façade. If given a building made up of engineered species, living materials could synthesise compounds to produce different façades for summer, winter, and the climatic conditions of the region, cleaning the interior air or alerting its occupants when pollutants are detected. As a result, Michelle Addington indicates that despite the prevalence of metrics and guidelines such as LEED or Passivhaus, the building may not always be the most productive ‘location’ boundary, or scale at which to interfere. This appreciation not only allows for new insights into complex processes, but also opens up pathways for environmental and energy action (Benjamin, 2017).

Zooming in and out of the house, the capacity of embodied energy to bind the territorial and material scales allows the smallest invention to have the greatest effect, and vice versa.

Today, understanding how something is produced, preserved, recycled, or decomposed is an important part of the historical dimension of our enjoyment of it as

an immediate, profoundly sensorial, and also as an aesthetic experience. As Otero-Pailos points out, the cultural component of embodied energy is just as important as its theoretical, performative, and technical implications. Managing the uncertainty that comes with it will lead to new ways of thinking. This revived convergence is a valuable way for façade engineers to progress out of the binaries we're faced with, implying new possibilities for reconnecting aesthetic planning understandings with much-needed alternatives and possibilities (Benjamin, 2017).

Buildings are physical manifestations of concepts. They bear the weight of untold tales. They reflect culture, traditions, and technological advancements. They also reflect environmental effects. Buildings have always had a powerful physical presence. Building construction and operation have become more imposing as a result of climate change. However, there is a surprising twist in the tale of energy in structural engineering. In reality, operational energy—defined as energy used for needs like heating, cooling, and lighting—has decreased as a percentage of total energy consumption in buildings over the last fifty years. Simultaneously, embodied energy—which is usually characterised as the amount of all energy needed to extract raw materials, produce, transport, and assemble those materials into a building—has risen dramatically (Benjamin, 2017).

This trend is largely due to improved operational energy efficiency (based on this efficiency, a 'zero energy' house can now be built, though the concept is misleading since it requires zero percent operational energy and 100 percent embodied energy. Another consideration is that most modern building materials—especially glass, steel, and plastic—embody more energy than most older building materials, such as wood, brick, and stone. This shifting energy consumption ratio is obvious, and it necessitates a new sense of urgency in our approach to embodied energy, a closer examination of methodologies and boundaries to understand precisely how these quantities are measured, and a broadening of the geographic and time scales we currently use to understand buildings (Benjamin, 2017). As a result, it poses a number of important concerns about the properties of embodied energy:

- Where exactly is all of this embodied energy?
- What is left out of the equation?
- How is embodied energy actionable?
- How might façade planners design with it?

Before delving into the technical meaning of embodied energy, this research will look at (Benjamin, 2017)'s extended and complex interpretation of the concept. The following points are worth considering:

1. Embodied energy has a long and illustrious tradition. It requires a consideration of where the energy came from and what relationships it formed along the way. Clearly, energy derived from the wind and sun has a different past and effect than energy derived from the combustion of fossil fuels. We can restrict our ability to understand and work productively with embodied energy if we define energy too narrowly as simply fuel.
2. The length of time is important. Working with embodied energy entails a thorough understanding of both what happens to a building after it is constructed

(how long it lasts, whether it is rebuilt, how it is destroyed, and what happens to its constituent parts) all of the processes that occur before construction begins.

3. Material selection should consider not only observable characteristics such as form, colour, grade, strength, and finish, but also intangible characteristics such as the amount of embodied energy, the source of embodied energy, the quality of human labour involved, and the material's life span. As a result, we might consider defining 'fair trade' steel, which is intended to pay living wages to anyone who worked on it, from mining to factory smelting to ship and truck transportation. We may also specify 'fifty-year' bricks, which are planned to biodegrade after demolition rather than remain in landfill for hundreds of years.
4. Embodied energy is a component of a larger image. Carbon emissions, resource depletion, pollution, deforestation, habitat destruction, public health, social equity, land use, and global trade are all factors that go into making structural engineering, especially façade engineering. So, in addition to equations, designing with embodied energy requires synthetic thought, holistic principles, imagination, and reasoning.
5. Embodied labour is linked to embodied energy. Human effort could be used to create, transport, assemble, and repair architectural bricks without the use of any other energy. There's nothing inherently wrong with incorporating energy into planning, and the practice of using as many machines and as much energy as possible to produce materials and structures can be questioned.¹
6. Culture plays a role in embodied energy. Our shared cultural understanding of what makes a building, what it is worth, and how a type of cultural energy holds together is inextricably linked to the physical expression of energy in a building.²
7. It is essential to plan for embodied energy. It is not just a list of numbers. In these lines, how we understand embodied energy is influenced by how we draw it. Since drawings—including all of their digital manifestations—are architects' primary tool for imagination and problem solving, embodied energy must be drawn in order to be considered.
8. Embodied energy architecture demands the design of the whole device. It necessitates efforts in procurement, manufacturing, logistics, global supply chains, and waste management. As a result, the house, especially the façade, is not the best place to learn about and address embodied energy. A wider perspective is needed.

5.2 Definition

The total energy consumed by a building over its service life is known as life cycle energy. The total energy embedded in all products and processes that are used in constructing a building is known as embodied energy. Buildings are constructed with a variety of building materials, each of which consumes energy throughout its life cycle stages of manufacture, use, deconstruction, and disposal. The energy

¹It is relevant to the recent movement of 'repair cafes', where citizens come together to repair their clothes and electronics rather than buying new ones.

²Thinking of energy in ecological terms, we need to think of energy in cultural terms.

consumed in these stages is known as the embodied energy of a building material (Manish K. Dixit, Fernández-Solís, et al., 2010; Vukotic, Fenner, and Symons, 2010). Table 5.1 presents embodied energy definitions given by various research studies. Studies such as those of (Hegner, 2007) and (Upton et al., 2008) defined embodied energy as the nonrenewable fraction of the total embodied energy. Clearly, current embodied energy definitions represent differences of opinion about the material and energy inputs to be included in an energy analysis (Hegner, 2007; Nebel, 2007).

5.2.1 Direct and indirect energy

Energy consumed directly in on-site and off-site operations such as construction, prefabrication, assembly, transportation, and administration is termed direct energy (R. Fay and Graham Treloar, 2003; G. K. C. Ding, 2004; Manish K. Dixit, Fernández-Solís, et al., 2010). Meanwhile, the energy used indirectly by a building through nonenergy inputs is known as an indirect component. For instance, energy spent in manufacturing the building materials, assemblies, and equipment installed in a building is considered an indirect component (Boustead and Hancock, 1979; Graham J Treloar, 1998; R.H. Crawford, 2004; Manish K. Dixit, Fernández-Solís, et al., 2010; R.H. Crawford, 2004).

5.2.2 Life cycle energy model

The total life cycle energy used by a building includes direct and indirect components of embodied and operating energy. This energy use is distributed among three major stages of the life cycle: construction, use, and end-of-life stage. Figure 5.1 shows an embodied energy model and illustrates the energy use associated with each of the three stages. The energy used in manufacturing building materials, assemblies, and equipment, and in processes such as construction, installation, fabrication, transportation, and administration during a building's construction stage, is collectively termed the 'initial embodied energy' (IEE) (Cole, 1996; Cole and Wong, 1996; Manish K. Dixit, Fernández-Solís, et al., 2010; Vukotic, Fenner, and Symons, 2010; Manish K. Dixit, Culp, and Fernández-Solís, 2013).

The total LCEE³ of a building is the sum of its initial, recurrent, and demolition energy. The total LCE⁴ of a built facility includes LCEE and OE⁵ (Cole, 1996; Cole and Wong, 1996; Manish K. Dixit, Fernández-Solís, et al., 2010; Vukotic, Fenner, and Symons, 2010; Manish K. Dixit, Culp, and Fernández-Solís, 2013).

5.2.3 Initial embodied energy (IEE)

The IEE is composed of the total energy used during the building material production and building construction phase (Cole, 1996; Cole and Wong, 1996; Manish K. Dixit, Fernández-Solís, et al., 2010; Vukotic, Fenner, and Symons, 2010). In the material production phase, the upstream processes such as raw material extraction, treatment, and transportation to production units are quite energy intensive. The main production process involves the use of both electricity and fuels. Fuels are used both as an energy source and as a feedstock material. In the downstream, energy is expended when the final product is delivered to a construction site or a material supplier. During

³Life Cycle Embodied Energy.

⁴Life Cycle Energy.

⁵Operational Energy.

TABLE 5.1: Embodied energy definition. Adapted from the comprehensive literature review by (Manish Kumar, 2013).

Source	Embodied Energy Definition Provided
(Crowther, 1999)	“The total energy required in the creation of a building, including the direct energy used in the construction and assembly process, and the indirect energy, that is required to manufacture the materials and components of the buildings.”
(G. Treloar et al., 2000)	“Embodied energy (EE) is the energy required to provide a product (both directly and indirectly) through all processes upstream (i.e. traceable backwards from the finished product to consideration of raw materials).”
(Dewick and Miozzo, 2002)	“The total amount of energy used in the raw materials and manufacture of a certain quantity of material”
(Satori and A. Hestnes, 2007)	“The sum of all the energy needed to manufacture a good. It may or may not include feedstock energy. Generally expressed in term of primary energy.”
(Li et al., 2007)	“Embodied energy is the total energy embodied in construction materials during extraction, manufacturing, transportation, assembly, maintenance, demolition, and final disposal processes.”
(R. H. Crawford, G. J. Treloar, et al., 2006)	“The embodied energy of an entire building, or a building material or product in a building, comprises of indirect and direct energy. Indirect energy is used to create the inputs of goods and services to the main process, whereas direct energy is the energy used for the main process.”
(HUB, 2009)	“Embodied energy is the sum total of the energy used in a product from raw material extraction and transport to manufacturing, installation, use, disassembly, recycling and disposal and/or decomposition.”
(R. H. Crawford, Czerniakowski, and Fuller, 2010)	“Embodied energy accounts for the energy associated with the manufacture of products and materials including those resulting from the manufacture of goods and services used during this process.”
(Užšilaityte and Martinaitis, 2010)	“Embodied energy is the amount of energy consumed to create a product, material or service.”
(Ramesh, Prakash, and K. K. Shukla, 2010)	“Embodied energy is the energy utilized during manufacturing phase of the building. It is the energy content of all the materials used in the building and technical installations, and energy incurred at the time of erection / construction and renovation of the building.”

FIGURE 5.1: Embodied energy model for a building proposed by (Manish Kumar, 2013). The blue highlighted rectangles represent the embodied energy. The initial embodied energy as it is shown involves the production and construction phases.

construction phase, on-site and off-site processes such as material delivery, storage, construction, fabrication, administration, and project closeout also consume energy. The sum of all energy spent in delivering a building as a final product is known as IEE (Cole, 1996; Cole and Wong, 1996; Manish K. Dixit, Fernández-Solís, et al., 2010; Vukotic, Fenner, and Symons, 2010) (see Figure 5.1).

In the downstream of the main production process, when a finished product is packaged, labeled, stored, and transported to a construction site or a material supplier, energy is consumed directly and indirectly (Cole, 1996; Cole and Wong, 1996; Manish K. Dixit, Culp, and Fernández-Solís, 2013; G. Ding, 2004). In some cases, the delivery of finished building materials to their destination could be quite energy intensive depending on the distance and mode of transport (G. Ding, 2004).

5.2.4 Recurrent or recurring embodied energy (REE)

After a building is occupied and used, the processes of maintenance, replacement, and management consume energy and also non-energy inputs such as building materials, assemblies, and equipment. Also, if any part of the building is refurbished or a system is retrofitted, a considerable amount of energy and material is expended. The sum of the energy spent directly and indirectly in the use phase maintenance, replacement, and renovation is termed 'recurrent or recurring embodied energy'⁶ (Cole, 1996; Cole and Wong, 1996; Manish K. Dixit, Fernández-Solís, et al., 2010; Vukotic, Fenner, and Symons, 2010; G. K. Ding, 2007; Khasreen, Phillip FG Banfill, and Menzies, 2009).

5.2.5 Demolition energy (DE)

At the end of its service life, a building is demolished and its constituent materials are sorted, treated, and transported for reuse, recycling, or disposal to landfills or incinerators. Both the electricity and fuel are consumed directly and indirectly in the demolition and disposal processes. The sum of total energy consumed is termed 'demolition energy' (DE) (Cole, 1996; Cole and Wong, 1996; Manish K. Dixit, Fernández-Solís, et al., 2010; Vukotic, Fenner, and Symons, 2010).

5.3 Energy Use in Buildings

The sum of all energy used up directly and indirectly in the main production, upstream, and downstream processes until the final product reaches its destination is considered building materials' production energy. The energy of material production represents the largest share of a building's total LCEE (Vukotic, Fenner, and Symons, 2010; TY Chen, Burnett, and CK Chau, 2001; Scheuer, Keoleian, and Reppe, 2003). In an analysis of two high-rise residential buildings in Hong Kong, (TY Chen, Burnett, and CK Chau, 2001) concluded that the manufacturing energy comprise up to 90-92 % of a building's total LCEE. In a similar study of a six-storey university building done by (Scheuer, Keoleian, and Reppe, 2003), the total energy utilised in material production was found to be nearly 94% of the total LCEE (excluding construction and transportation). In Sweden, a study by (K. Adalberth, 1997) found that nearly 64-65% of the total LCEE (over 50 years' service life) of three prefabricated single-family dwellings came from building materials' production. Similarly, (Leckner and

⁶REE.

Zmeureanu, 2011) studied a base case and a net-zero energy version of a two-floor house in Canada and found the share of building materials as 70% of the total LCEE over 40 years' service life. They used embodied energy data from Athena Impact Estimator developed by the Athena⁷ Sustainable Materials Institute. The proportions of building material manufacturing energy in the total LCEE calculated by (TY Chen, Burnett, and CK Chau, 2001; Scheuer, Keoleian, and Reppe, 2003) was found to be higher than the ones calculated by (Adalberth, 1997) and (Leckner and Zmeureanu, 2011). The value calculated by (Scheuer, Keoleian, and Reppe, 2003) also included building materials used during replacement and maintenance processes over 75 years' service life, whereas (TY Chen, Burnett, and CK Chau, 2001) did not include building systems in the maintenance and replacement phase. As mentioned earlier, the most commonly-used materials such as aluminum, steel, and plastics have a higher embodied energy than other construction materials. Table 5.2 shows the energy embodied in some of the commonly used building materials. Building materials such as primary aluminium (129.5–378.5 MJ kg⁻¹), glass (6.8–83.6 MJ kg⁻¹), plastics (70–158 MJ kg⁻¹), and virgin steel (10.1–97.5 MJ kg⁻¹) are quite energy intensive and contribute significantly to a building's IEE (TY Chen, Burnett, and CK Chau, 2001; Dimoudi and Tompa, 2008).

It can be seen that there is a considerable variation in the reported values of embodied energy. Energy intensive materials such as aluminum and glass have a wider embodied energy range of 130 to 379 MJ kg⁻¹ and 7 to 84 MJ kg⁻¹, respectively.

The values calculated by (Graham J Treloar, Love, and Holt, 2001) and (Duell and Martin, 2005) are higher possibly due to a more comprehensive calculation method. Both the studies utilised data from the input-output-based hybrid approach proposed by (Graham J Treloar, 1998).

According to (TY Chen, Burnett, and CK Chau, 2001), the use of recycled steel (EE: 10 MJ kg⁻¹) and aluminum (EE: 8 MJ kg⁻¹) can save up to 70–96% of the manufacturing energy of virgin steel (EE: 32 MJ kg⁻¹) and primary aluminum (EE: 191 MJ kg⁻¹). At least 60% of the total manufacturing energy can be conserved by using recycled materials (TY Chen, Burnett, and CK Chau, 2001). According to (M. R. Fay, 1999), the energy used by sea vessels may be just 10% of the energy used in air transportation. (Kim, 2008) found that the energy consumed in the domestic transportation of materials was nearly 8% of its total embodied energy. (Miller, 2001) reported that if the return distance and road infrastructure are considered, the energy embodied in transporting building materials may increase drastically.

(Kim, 2008) found a higher energy of transport as 7% of the total LCEE due to inclusion of both the material and employee transportation. This opens a new topic of debate, regarding whether the energy of transporting materials should be mixed with the transportation energy spent during the construction stage (Vukotic, Fenner, and Symons, 2010). Another reason for the differing energy of transportation is that some materials such as sand, gravel, stone, and bricks (70 to 100 km) may be sourced locally using trucks, whereas materials such as aluminum, steel, insulation, and plastic may be delivered from a long distance using rail transport (400 to 500 km) (B. V. Reddy and Jagadish, 2003). Figure A.1 in Appendix A shows the values of transportation energy as a percentage of the total material's embodied energy calculated by various studies around the globe. The average values vary with a range of 0.01 to 0.66 GJ m⁻²

⁷ Athena website. Accessible on electronic version of this study.

TABLE 5.2: Embodied energy of commonly used building materials in MJ kg⁻¹. Adapted from the comprehensive literature review by (Manish Kumar, 2013).

Source	Virgin steel	Primary Aluminium	Glass	PVC	Fiberglass Ins.	Cellulose Ins.
(Buchanan and Honey, 1994)	34.9	129.5	31.5	96.0	23.0	
(Kernan, 1996)	28.0	274.0	18.7			
(K. Adalberth, 1997)	32.0		26.0	88.7		
(Blanchard and Reppe, 1998)	37.3	207.8	18.4	77.4	24.5	3.2
(Eaton et al., 1998)	25.5	200.0				
(T.Y. Chen, J. Burnett, and C.K. Chau, 2001)	32.0	191.0	16.1	70.0	30.3	3.3
(A. Alcorn, 2003)	31.3	192.0	15.9	60.9	32.1	4.3
(Scheuer, Keoleian, and Reppe, 2003)	30.6	207.0	6.8	60.7	17.6	
(V. B. Reddy, 2004)	42.0	236.8				
(Almeida, Bragança, and Mendonça, 2005)	10.1	160.2	18.4			
(Yohanis and Norton, 2006)	42.0	236.8	25.8			
(S. Pullen, 2007)	55.5	378.5	83.6	121.5		
(R.H. Crawford, 2004)	97.5	259.1		141.8		
(Huberman and Pearl-mutter, 2008)	35.0	211.0	18.0			
(G. Hammond and G. Jones, 2008)	35.3		15.0			
(Geoff Hammond and C. Jones, 2011)	31.3	218.0	15.0	70.6	28.0	3.3
(Ramesh, Prakash, and K. Shukla, 2013)	28.2	236.8	25.8	158.0		
Average	36.9	222.6	23.9	94.6	25.9	3.5

and a standard deviation of 0.18.

Resources such as labour, materials, equipment, and construction vehicles that are transported, maintained, and used during the construction phase deplete energy directly and indirectly (Cole, 1998; Vukotic, Fenner, and Symons, 2010). For instance, diesel burnt by an earth-moving machine is a direct energy use, whereas the energy consumed in manufacturing the machine represents the indirect energy component. The food consumed by labour is a direct consumption, whereas the energy used to prepare the food and to keep the human body fit for work is an indirect consumption (Cleveland and Costanza, 2010; Alshboul and Alzoubi, 2008; Manish K. Dixit, Culp, and Fernández-Solís, 2013). (S. F. Pullen, 2000) found that at least 3% of construction energy can be attributed to labour and 28% to equipment.

(S. F. Pullen, 2000; Cole, 1998) also asserted that construction energy is considered insignificant as compared to materials' embodied energy. In addition, little information is available in the literature on how to quantify construction energy. (M. R. Fay, 1999) cited studies by (Stein et al., 1980) and (Baird, 1995), which determined the construction energy within a range of 6–17% of the total LCEE. A large amount of waste is generated when building materials are moved, installed, and transformed during the construction process (T.Y. Chen, J. Burnett, and C.K. Chau, 2001; R. Fay and Graham Treloar, 2003). Energy embedded indirectly in construction waste could be significant, and would be lost if not recovered by reuse and recycling (Vukotic, Fenner, and Symons, 2010; R. Fay and Graham Treloar, 2003).

Figure 5.2 shows the average values of construction energy in various types of construction reported by studies mentioned in Table 5.3. Table 5.3 also provides the average values of materials' embodied energy and construction energy reported in the literature. The average results in Figure 5.2 further support the findings of (Cole, 1998) and (Vukotic, Fenner, and Symons, 2010) that the steel frame buildings required less construction energy than the wood frame. In addition, concrete frame is the most energy intensive type of construction. An increased need of labour, equipment, and formwork for concrete construction may be among the possible reasons for its higher energy requirement. The average as reported values ranged from 0.01 to 1.18 GJ m⁻² and varied with a standard deviation of 0.34.

Energy embedded indirectly in construction waste could be significant, and would be lost if not recovered by reuse and recycling (Vukotic, Fenner, and Symons, 2010; R. Fay and Graham Treloar, 2003).

(Cole, 1996) determined that for a service life of 25, 50, and 100 years, the REE of envelope, finishes, and services was 1.3, 3.2, and 7.3 times their IEE, respectively.

As buildings had differing service lives, for a fair comparison, REE values were annualised and expressed in MJ m⁻² year (Manish K Dixit et al., 2016).

The correlation of REE with the buildings' total LCE and LCEE means that the REE influences the LCE and LCEE more than any other life cycle embodied energy component.

The annual REE requirements for the residential buildings vary from 8 to 213 MJ m⁻² per year with an average of 62.3 MJ m⁻² per year.

Among the three major life cycle embodied energy components are initial embodied energy (IEE), recurrent embodied energy (REE), and demolition energy (DE). Among them, according to the reported results in the literature, the most influential energy components are REE and IEE. A rigorous review of literature was performed that

TABLE 5.3: Construction energy as a fraction of embodied energy (EE) of building material production. Adapted from the comprehensive literature review by (Manish Kumar, 2013).

Study	Construction Type	Material EE GJ m^{-2}	Construction EE GJ m^{-2}	Fraction %
(Treloar, 1993)	Concrete	8.30	0.47	5.64
(Graham J Treloar, Owen, and R. Fay, 2001)	Brick	9.86	0.88	8.88
(T.Y. Chen, J. Burnett, and C.K. Chau, 2001)	Steel	4.48	0.12	2.59
(Chulsukon et al., 2002)	Brick	3.04	1.13	37.17
(Scheuer, Keoleian, and Reppe, 2003)	Steel	5.40	0.31	5.74
(Junnila, Horvath, and Guggemos, 2006)	Concrete	5.10	1.18	23.06
(Randolph et al., 2007)	Brick	6.86	0.88	12.83
(Johnson, 2006)	Steel	0.77	0.12	15.82
(Johnson, 2006)	Concrete	0.76	0.15	19.13
(Nässén et al., 2007a)	Generic	3.10	0.35	11.29
(Haines et al., 2007)	Wood	2.59	0.14	5.27
(Utama and Gheewala, 2008)	Brick	0.84	0.17	20.53
(Utama and Gheewala, 2008)	Concrete	0.82	0.15	17.83
(Fridley et al., 2008)	Generic	9.24	0.07	0.74
(Yang, Lin, and Huang-Fu, 2008)	Concrete	3.81	0.58	15.22
(Kahhat et al., 2009)	Concrete	3.23	0.27	8.21
(Kahhat et al., 2009)	Wood	2.91	0.26	8.85
(Kahhat et al., 2009)	Steel	3.00	0.25	8.35
(Utama and Gheewala, 2009)	Brick	0.88	0.01	1.14
(Gustavsson, Joelsson, and Sathre, 2010)	Wood	3.22	0.29	9.01
(Leckner and Zmeureanu, 2011)	Wood	3.30	0.20	6.06

FIGURE 5.2: Construction energy as a percentage of building materials' embodied energy. Provided in the literature and gathered by (Manish Kumar, 2013).

included embodied energy case studies from 1976 through 2011.

5.4 Problem of Variation in Existing EE

Embodied energy values in building materials and buildings vary considerably across research studies; this variation could be up to 30–50%. Problems with energy data make the comparison of building materials and products difficult in embodied energy terms (Khasreen, Phillip FG Banfill, and Menzies, 2009).

There are certain parameters that cause embodied energy values to differ across research studies (Manish K. Dixit, Fernández-Solís, et al., 2010). Most of these parameters are related to embodied energy calculation methods, while some are actually data quality-related issues. (Manish Kumar, 2013) categorises them into the two categories: methodological parameters and data quality parameters.

5.4.1 Methodological parameters

System boundary: problem of incompleteness

(Khasreen, Phillip FG Banfill, and Menzies, 2009) asserted that research studies often do not clearly describe the system boundary adopted in their study and so it becomes difficult for the readers to determine what is included and excluded from the energy calculation.

(Raynolds, Fraser, and Checkel, 2000) emphasised the need for a system that ensures consistent system boundary selection across different studies. System boundary definition differs across studies, which leads to variations in the calculated embodied energy values (Manish K. Dixit, Fernández-Solís, et al., 2010).

Method of embodied energy calculation

Hybrid analysis (see section 5.6) is a method that includes both the process and the input-output data and is considered relatively complete and accurate. Research studies have applied different calculation methods and their embodied energy results differ significantly (Manish K. Dixit, Fernández-Solís, et al., 2010; Nebel, 2007).

(Robert H Crawford and Graham J Treloar, 2003) calculated embodied energy in both a residential and a commercial building as 6.6 GJ m^{-2} and 9.0 GJ m^{-2} , respectively using a process-based analysis. Furthermore, they found that embodied energy in the same buildings could decrease by 14.5–23% if an input-output-based analysis were to be used. (Robert Crawford and Graham Treloar, 2005) later studied a commercial building and concluded that when an input-output-based calculation was performed, the calculated values increased by 56% from the building's process-based values (8.0 GJ m^{-2}).

Energy inputs

Energy embodied in buildings and building materials is reported in primary or delivered energy terms. Delivered energy (e.g. electricity) is the energy used by a consumer. It is also known as 'end use,' 'site,' or 'final' energy. Primary energy is the energy of fossil fuel extracted from the Earth. Primary energy is extracted, processed, and converted to a form (delivered energy) that is usable for a range of purposes (Manish K. Dixit, Fernández-Solís, et al., 2010). Primary energy varies from delivered energy (and is usually high) owing to factors such as fuel types (e.g. electricity, natural gas, oil) and the means of delivered energy production (e.g. coal fired, natural gas fired, nuclear or hydro power plants) (G. Treloar et al., 2000; Thormark, 2000; Sartori and A. G. Hestnes, 2007; Hernandez and Kenny, 2010). Each of these power plants holds differing efficiencies and uses relatively more primary energy to generate delivered energy. For example, as reported by (G. Treloar et al., 2000), for every single unit of electricity 3.4 units of primary energy is burnt in Australia. This factor of 3.4 is known as the 'conversion factor' or 'primary energy factor' and differs across countries and energy carriers (G. Treloar et al., 2000; Hernandez and Kenny, 2010).

Figure 5.3 illustrates a generic process of generating electricity from primary fuels. It can be seen that the efficiency of energy conversion and the type of fuels are the two key aspects that affect the amount of delivered energy generated and supplied to the end users.

If the embodied energy of a building is reported in delivered energy terms, there is a strong possibility that these values would be nearly similar across different countries for the same building (Hernandez and Kenny, 2010).

(ISO 14040, 2009) defined feedstock energy as the 'heat of combustion of a raw material input that is not used as an energy source to a product system, expressed in terms of higher heating value or lower heating value.' 'Feedstock energy' is the heat

FIGURE 5.3: Process of electricity generation and related losses Provided in the (Manish Kumar, 2013).

of combustion or energy content of raw material input (e.g. wood and petrochemicals, such as oil and gas) used as an ingredient in the process of manufacturing a product (e.g. wood components, plastics and rubber) (Hernandez and Kenny, 2010; Trusty, 2006; Ardente et al., 2008).

(Thormark, 2000; Thormark, 2007) found the feedstock energy to be 27–94% of the materials' embodied energy (released materials). (Ardente et al., 2008) conducted a 'cradle to gate' LCA of the Kenaf-fiber insulation boards and revealed that nearly 50% of the total embodied energy was attributed to the material's feedstock.

Feedstock energy is significant and must therefore be considered in the embodied energy calculation (Thormark, 2006; Nässén et al., 2007b; Ardente et al., 2008; G. Hammond and G. Jones, 2008).

(Hegner, 2007) presents an interesting explanation of embodied energy. According to them, only energy that is available in a limited amount should be considered embodied energy. Here, they relate the phenomenon of embodied energy to greenhouse gas emissions because a major fraction of primary energy available in a limited amount comes from fossil fuels. Recent studies (Citherlet and Hand, 2002; Holtzhausen, 2007; Upton et al., 2008; Verbeeck and Hens, 2010; Perez Fernandez, 2008; De Meester et al., 2009; Pittet et al., 2012a; Black, Van Ooteghem, and Boake, 2010; Aste, Adhikari, and Buzzetti, 2010; Leckner and Zmeureanu, 2011) have each presented their energy results separately in nonrenewable energy terms to emphasise the environmental significance of embodied energy as an evaluation parameter.

Studies (Y. L. Langston and C. Langston, 2007; Pulselli, Simoncini, and Marchettini, 2009) have underscored a need to incorporate human energy within embodied energy analysis. However, has not often been accomplished due to the lack of a clear human energy calculation method. One significant study that calculated human energy was done by (Alshboul and Alzoubi, 2008) who performed an embodied energy analysis of the natural-dimensioned stone in Jordan. They measured human energy using work duration and metabolic rates. However, they found that the variability of individual metabolic rates posed difficulty in consistently calculating human energy. Another important work by (Cleveland and Costanza, 2010) discussed human labour and identified three components, which should be accounted for while quantifying human energy. These are:

1. The calorific value of food consumed by workers
2. The embodied energy of food

3. Fuel purchased with the salaries or wages of workers.

5.4.2 Data quality parameters

The following factors affect the quality of data used in energy analysis:

- Primary and secondary Data
- Data incompleteness
- Data representativeness

(Goggins, Keane, and A. Kelly, 2010) claimed that the accuracy of embodied energy data depends upon the methods of embodied energy measurement. Often, embodied energy is also calculated using Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) tools and datasets such as Athena, BEES 4.0, Ecoinvent, Eco-Quantum, Envest 2, OPTIMIZE, LICHEE, and SimaPro. However, some of these tools do not cover all stages of a building's life cycle and lack the capability to perform a full life cycle assessment (Manish Kumar, 2013; Itard and Netherlands, 2007; Haapio and Viitaniemi, 2008; Khasreen, Phillip FG Banfill, and Menzies, 2009).

Studies that perform embodied energy calculations based on process analysis often suffer from data incompleteness, thus accounting for nearly all processes would have been a difficult task (Menzies, Turan, and Philip FG Banfill, 2007; G. P. Hammond and C. I. Jones, 2010; Goggins, Keane, and A. Kelly, 2010). Data incompleteness should be verified when choosing one material dataset over another (Andrew Alcorn, 1996; R. H. Crawford, G. J. Treloar, et al., 2006; Nebel, 2007; Khasreen, Phillip FG Banfill, and Menzies, 2009).

The geographic relevance of data causes the largest variation in LCA or embodied energy results (Khasreen, Phillip FG Banfill, and Menzies, 2009; Optis and Wild, 2010). Energy tariffs paid by material manufacturers and material prices also vary between locations, causing an error of up to 2.5% in the calculations (Stephen Pullen, 1996). (Pittet et al., 2012b) noted that low income countries tend to use less efficient technology (of manufacture and construction) than developed countries.

5.5 Embodied Energy: Significance

Recent research has revealed that embodied energy may account for a larger energy consumption fraction of the total life cycle energy (G. K. C. Ding, 2004). [Figure A.2](#) and [Figure A.3](#) in [Appendix A](#) demonstrate the proportion of embodied energy in the total LCE of residential and commercial buildings, respectively, in four geographic regions: North America, Asia, Europe, and Oceania. The data has been collected by a rigorous literature review of published case studies of residential and commercial buildings across the globe. A description of the referred case studies can be found in [Figure A.4](#) and [Figure A.5](#) in [Appendix A](#).

The main purpose of the data presented in [Figure A.2](#) and [Figure A.3](#) is to show the variation in the relative proportion of embodied and operating energy that is contingent upon location, time, construction, and socio-economic parameters of the case study buildings. This data should not be taken as a rule of thumb rule for

estimating the proportion of embodied and operating energy.

It can be expected that the amount of embodied energy correlates to the resulting carbon emission. This correlation indicates that both the embodied energy and carbon can be used as an effective parameter for the environmental evaluation of various products (Hegner, 2007; Acquaye, 2010).

5.6 Calculation

The main methods of embodied energy analysis are process analysis, statistical analysis, input-output analysis and hybrid analysis (Graham J Treloar, 1998; Robert H Crawford and Graham J Treloar, 2003; G. K. C. Ding, 2004; Y. L. Langston, 2006). Figure 5.4 summarises these main methods. (Graham J Treloar, 1998) and (R.H. Crawford, 2004)'s input-output-based hybrid method is particularly useful in evaluating the embodied energy of a complex product in an economy where process energy data is available for certain industry sectors. The process-based energy intensities, on the other hand, were assumed to be measured fully and accurately. Inputs such as human energy, for example, may not be included in the available process data. It is also unclear how to factor human and capital resources into the equation. Furthermore, the field of embodied energy research lacks a specific technique for determining the energy embodied in a building accurately and fully. Established approaches are either insufficient or unspecific to the substance under investigation, resulting in inconsistent outcomes. The inclusion of process data, insertion of human and capital energy, sector-based disaggregation for improved precision, and avoidance of double counting are some of the suggested improvements.

In the context of the embodied energy measurement process, there are two critical points to consider. The first problem has to do with the system boundary, while the second concerns the current embodied energy measurement methods.

Among common system boundaries for buildings and building products are 'cradle to gate,' 'cradle to site,' and 'cradle to grave' systems. The cradle to gate system boundary includes upstream processes such as raw material extraction, through a point where the finished product leaves the factory gate (excluding transport of material to the building site) (Frey et al., 2010; Goggins, Keane, and A. Kelly, 2010). Figure 5.5 provides an illustration of various boundary definitions discussed in the literature.

System boundaries proposed by published studies differed in three ways. First, studies often included only one or few life cycle stages of a building in the embodied energy analysis (G. K. C. Ding, 2004; Edwards et al., 1994). The transportation and transformation processes between two consecutive life cycle stages were seldom considered in the calculation. Second, how far a study should go in the upstream and downstream of each life cycle stage was unclear (Horvath, 2004; Bo P Weidema et al., 2008; Reinout Heijungs, Huppel, and Jeroen Guinée, 2009). Finally, not all studies considered the whole building in the embodied energy calculation and covered one or more building components such as building structure, envelope, finishes, services and site features (G. K. C. Ding, 2004; Edwards et al., 1994; Optis and Wild, 2010).

Embodied Energy Analysis

Major processes of embodied energy analysis

FIGURE 5.4: Embodied energy analysis methods.

FIGURE 5.5: Various boundary definitions provided in the literature and gathered by (Manish Kumar, 2013). The whole embodied energy part is highlighted in light blue.

These differences in boundary definitions caused variation and incompleteness in embodied energy data due to the exclusion of important life cycle stages or building components (G. K. C. Ding, 2004; Khasreen, Phillip FG Banfill, and Menzies, 2009).

Because of the aforementioned issues in calculating embodied energy, (Manish Kumar, 2013) developed a methodology that is summarised in [section 5.7](#).

5.7 Research Design, Methods and Results

The aim of the study by (Manish Kumar, 2013) was to derive a less data-intensive and more streamlined method to consistently calculate the energy embodied in a building and its constituent materials. This aim was achieved by meeting the following objectives:

- Proposing a set of criteria for calculating the embodied energy of a structure and its materials
- Creating a system boundary model for the embodied energy analysis of a building and its materials
- Developing a formula for calculating the embodied energy of a building material based on the energy-cost relationship that is consistent and complete
- Identifying any connection between a building material's cost and price and its embodied energy

Although the amount of embodied energy and embodied carbon in a product were found to be strongly related, the study by (Manish Kumar, 2013) aimed to determine only embodied energy.

Since the United States' economy was used to create the embodied energy measurement process, the results should be used with caution when applied to a foreign economy. If comparable data were available, the measures suggested in the calculation method could be repeated with or without modifications. The term 'cradle to gate' is often used to describe the system boundary. However, since most transportation among the various sectors of the US economy was included in the input-output model, the measured embodied energy values can be assumed to have a 'cradle to site' system boundary.

In the input-output-based hybrid process, the following enhancements were suggested by (Manish Kumar, 2013):

- To avoid the double counting of energy inputs, calculate and use PEF⁸ for each form of delivered energy
- Using comprehensive output and input data sourced from the USCB⁹, disaggregation of sectors representing multiple products was performed
- Inputting process data in physical units for energy use (including fuel feedstock use) into the input-output model

⁸Primary Energy Factor.

⁹United States Census Bureau.

- Quantifying and including the resources embodied in labour and capital inputs in the input-output model
- To gain a better understanding of the environmental impacts of study materials, the energy intensities of study materials were calculated for each energy source

5.7.1 Quantifying embodied energy

Figure 5.6 illustrates the approach to developing the calculation method and quantifying the embodied energy of study materials. The following steps were taken to develop the calculation method:

Step I: Developing commodity-by-commodity direct and total requirement matrices using the raw make and use data sourced from the 2002 United States Benchmark Input-output Accounts published by the USBEA¹⁰ (USBEA, 2008). The matrices were adjusted for scrap as suggested by (Horowitz and Planting, 2009). The final matrices were checked for consistency with the direct and total requirement tables provided on USBEA website.

Step II: For the year 2002, data on energy usage by industry sectors in physical or energy units was collected. If the data was available in monetary units, it was converted to energy units using sector-specific energy prices. Furthermore, if the energy data was aggregated, it was decomposed into various fuel groups (e.g., coal, oil, and natural gas).

Step III: PEF for each form of energy supplied to industry sectors for end use was calculated. The energy lost and expended in collecting, refining, transmitting, and distributing an energy source, both directly and indirectly, was included.

Step IV: The energy embodied in human labour and capital inputs was calculated using the method recommended by the literature (e.g. (Joshi, 1999)). The measured values were then entered as two different columns in the input-output model, analogous to the five energy-producing sectors of the US economy (based upon (Schuett et al., 2012)). To prevent double counting, all energy and non-energy inputs to these two sectors were set to zero.

Step V: Using the precise composition of industry sector inputs and outputs, the industry sectors that manufacture more than one product were disaggregated. The method proposed by (Joshi, 1999) was used to disaggregate the sectors.

Step VI: (Graham J Treloar, 1998) recommends using the Power Series Approximation method to quantify the cumulative embodied energy of study materials. This method was chosen over Leontief's Inverse Matrix because it required the energy intensities to be calculated by upstream levels. Furthermore, the energy intensities were measured fuel by fuel so that potential analyses of the environmental impacts of fuel usage could be conducted.

¹⁰U.S. Bureau of Economic Analysis.

FIGURE 5.6: Approach to developing an input-output-based hybrid method. Reproduced from (Manish Kumar, 2013).

5.7.2 Main assumptions of the study by (Manish Kumar, 2013)

- When estimating human energy needs, it was believed that an employee's entire food energy was allocated to his or her job. In order to measure capital resources, input-output-based energy intensities for sectors producing capital goods were assumed to be sufficient. The weighted average energy intensities were calculated using the fractions of different capital goods in the overall capital expenditure, such as buildings, vehicles, machinery, and software.
- The indirect energy use was estimated using an input-output-based analysis when measuring the Primary Energy Factors (PEFs) for different energy sources other than electricity. Since the majority of energy-producing industries generate only energy-related goods, their energy intensities were believed to be specific to their primary products. Furthermore, it was believed that no energy could be obtained, so any energy gains recorded in 2002 were ignored.
- The total purchases of goods by each disaggregated sector were used to distribute the aggregated sector's total input of goods during the sectoral disaggregation phase. Similarly, total service purchases were distributed using each disaggregated sector's total service purchases. The usage of commodities by industries was disaggregated based on the share of each disaggregated product in the aggregated commodity's total production. The make of disaggregated commodities was considered to be the same as the aggregated commodity in the make table.
- When the human and capital inputs were entered, it was believed that they reflected energy resources that were generated by no industry sectors. All of these commodities' energy and non-energy inputs were held at zero.

The study was created to resolve four major problems that were described as research gaps. The LBD¹¹ research approach was used to propose a full and clear system boundary model as well as a set of embodied energy guidelines. Since the existing version of the input-output-based hybrid approach was deemed the most suitable method for measuring embodied energy, it was used as a foundation for the improvements suggested in the literature. The PEF was calculated for each energy source used in the US economy. The method proposed by (Graham J Treloar, 1998) to avoid the double counting of energy inputs was used. The human and capital energy were calculated and inserted into the input-output model using the approach offered by (Joshi, 1999). In addition, using the same approach (Joshi, 1999) and (Joshi, 1999), the industry sectors were disaggregated to obtain more study-specific results.

5.7.3 Calculation guidelines

The literature clearly points out serious issues with the way embodied energy calculations have been planned, carried out, and their results reported. The guidelines for calculating embodied energy can be tied to the four major issues with the current embodied energy research. These issues include:

1. Lack of embodied energy definition
2. Inconsistent system boundary model

¹¹Literature-Based Discovery.

3. Poor data quality
4. Lack of a standard calculation method

The following subsections describe the embodied energy guidelines.

Embodied energy definition

Embodied energy of a product The net sum of all primary energy, including human and mechanical energy, consumed directly or indirectly in products (goods) and processes (services) used in manufacturing and delivering a final product for end use is termed the embodied energy.

Life cycle embodied energy: building The net sum of embodied energy of all products (goods) and processes (services) consumed by a building in the life cycle stages of initial construction, occupancy and use, and demolition and material disposal is known as the life cycle embodied energy.

Life cycle operating energy: building The net total primary energy, including direct and indirect components, used by a building in its operation over its service life is called the life cycle operating energy.

Life cycle energy: building The sum of a building's total life cycle embodied and operating energy is termed the life cycle energy.

System boundary definition

The system under investigation is characterised by a boundary that extends from the biosphere and returns to it. The objective is to fully establish a boundary. The length and width of a system under study are described by two distinct dimensions, according to an in-depth review of system boundary models proposed in the literature (see [Figure 5.7](#)). The longitudinal dimension (or 'X' dimension) of a product, such as a building, encompasses the upstream and downstream of the product (e.g. life cycle stages). The upstream and downstream of each stage covered by the longitudinal dimension each are defined by the cross-sectional dimension ('Y' dimension). The longitudinal dimension's cross-sectional dimension 'Y' is often used to transition between stages. The following guidelines apply:

- Defining an 'X' dimension boundary entails monitoring each input from its point of origin in the upstream of a building to its disposal or recovery in the far downstream. The 'X' dimension (length) spans the entire life cycle of a building, beginning with material development and continuing through initial construction and use to end-of-life. Both resource transportation and transformation are also included. Energy and non-energy raw materials, labour, and machines are all included in the word 'resources.'
- Each 'X' dimension life cycle stage absorbs energy and non-energy inputs in the upstream and generates emissions, pollution, and waste in the downstream. The primary energy inputs are covered in the upstream of a life cycle stage, while the primary energy used in the remediation of emission, contamination, and waste generation is covered in the downstream. Full primary energy of both energy and non-energy inputs is referred to as 'all primary energy inputs.' The width of a system boundary is defined by this dimension (the 'Y' dimension).

A system under investigation can involve the whole building or parts of it in the case of a complex product like a building. The scope of the research, for example, could be limited to just the structure, envelope, or building facilities, or it could be expanded to include the location, surroundings, and neighbourhood. The 'Z' dimension is indicated by the various levels of study scope. It is recommended to include both the 'X' and 'Y' dimensions for a basic material (e.g., cement, aggregate, glass). It is recommended that all three dimensions (X, Y, and Z) of a complex product (e.g., windows, appliances, buildings) be covered, as shown in [Figure 5.7](#). A complex product is one that is made up of many different raw materials. A window assembly, for example, is made up of metal, glass, rubber, coatings, and gases inserted between the glass layers. A substance like concrete, which is made up of cement, chemicals, aggregate, sand, and water, is an example of a complex product.

The process of defining a system boundary begins with the stage of building materials production (see block 'A' in [Figure 5.8](#)), which includes the main production process, upstream processes like raw material extraction, treatment, and transportation, and downstream processes like finished product packaging, storage, and distribution. Each material (e.g., fuels, building materials, water) and product (building assemblies, machinery, machines, etc.) used in the construction of a building is subjected to the same block 'A' study.

As shown in [Figure 5.8](#), each block 'A' analysis is divided into blocks 'B' and 'C,' defining the input and output sides of the 'Y' axis. The products and processes that reach each life cycle stage, including the transitional stages, are determined on the input side (block 'B'). Raw materials (including feedstock energy), machinery and devices, and capital facilities (e.g., vehicles, software, temporary or permanent structures) are all part of the product category, each of which is fed into each life cycle stage. The block 'A' analysis is performed for each object in the product input group.

The transformation or transportation of resources, such as material, labour, and equipment, falls under the process category. Each input and output side includes mechanical and human energy usage, as well as losses due to energy source acquisition (primary fuel extraction or electricity generation), storage, and supply (primary or electrical energy transmission and distribution). Losses due to machinery performance and human labour productivity are also taken into account. Every primary fuel used by machinery and each food item consumed by labour is subjected to block 'A' analysis. The use of resources and energy in the remediation of resource use's environmental implications (block 'C') is covered on the production side (input side). Every item in the product and process category is linked to the block 'A' review, just like block 'B.' As a result, we can see that at a micro stage, the system boundary begins with block 'A' analysis, covers blocks 'B' and 'C,' and then returns to block 'A' analysis. This seems to be an endless cycle, with each block 'A' review being less important (in terms of its relative effect on the product under investigation) than the previous one.

Each stage of a building's life cycle includes blocks 'B' and 'C,' as shown in [Figure 5.9](#), which depicts a building's system boundary in detail. As shown in [Figure 5.9](#), each activity of transportation, loading and unloading, temporary storage, and so on is included in the transition from one stage to the next. All goods (cranes, trucks, loaders, dumpers, and so on) and processes (transportation, loading, and unloading) involved in the transitional stages have their block 'B' and 'C' calculations

FIGURE 5.7: The three dimensions of a system boundary for a building. Reproduced from (Manish Kumar, 2013).

FIGURE 5.8: System in the Y dimension. Reproduced from (Manish Kumar, 2013).

completed. There are two forms of resource recycling or reuse: open loop and closed loop. Resources can also be recovered by burning products containing feedstock energy (e.g. wood, plastic and other petrochemical products). The term 'open loop recycling' refers to the recycling and reuse of materials through life cycle stages or industry sectors. Within a life cycle stage or an industry sector, the closed loop involves reuse or recycling.

Data completeness

Data representativeness is determined by considering geographic place, time, and technology. It is essential to verify the representativeness of primary data if these factors are measured. For example, if data is from the same region and year as the analysis, and they reflect resource use technology in manufacturing and construction. If old data must be used for some purpose, changes must be made to bring it up to date. If no modifications can be made, an old-time analysis can be conducted. In this case, however, all other data should be from the same time span. Adjustments are needed when using data from a region other than the study because of socioeconomic and technical factors.

Calculation method

An input-output analysis appears to be the only way to account for all indirect inputs in the system boundary model suggested in [section 5.7.3](#). The chances of a process-based analysis' incompleteness being enhanced to the point that all indirect inputs are counted are slim. According to current studies, the accuracy of an input-output-based approach is expected to improve dramatically over time.

The embodied energy measurement should be done using an input-output hybrid system. To increase the input-output model's efficiency, process data on energy inputs can be obtained and added. The following guidelines refer to a hybrid approach focused on input-output data by (Manish Kumar, 2013):

1. It is suggested that energy and commodity costs be avoided, as this will increase the method's efficiency. If possible, process data can be used to replace direct requirement coefficients of energy usage to avoid depending on energy prices, which differ across industries and geographical boundaries. The direct energy requirement coefficients are expressed in energy units in this case.
2. It should be ensured that non-traditional inputs such as human energy and capital investment are quantified and included in the economic model.
3. If disaggregated data on major commodity inputs and outputs is accessible, sector disaggregation is a suggested approach for making the results of an input-output-based method more study relevant.
4. Due to the way economic input-output accounts are prepared, there is a high risk of double counting. One method to prevent the double counting of energy, is to set all energy and nonenergy inputs to zero and calculate energy intensities by fuel using Primary Energy Factors (PEFs). There are industries that buy energy goods and resell them for a profit, such as wholesale and retail trades. However, calculating their energy intensity based on how much they bought from energy-producing sectors could be misleading since the majority of the energy purchased was not consumed but exchanged.

FIGURE 5.9: Complete system boundary for a building. Reproduced from (Manish Kumar, 2013).

5. When using PEFs, it is assumed that they account for all indirect energy inputs consumed by an energy-producing field. As a result, It is critical to measure the PEF for each energy source in its entirety, taking into account all direct and indirect inputs. Calculating the PEFs is best done using a hybrid input-output strategy.
6. When all energy sources used in an economy are averaged into a single energy source for the purpose of measuring embodied energy, the embodied energy calculation loses its importance to environmental concerns. The effects of embodied energy by fuel form can be used to calculate other environmental impacts including carbon emissions and pollution.
7. Product prices are used to translate embodied energy intensities to embodied energy values per unit of mass or volume until the embodied energy intensities of industry sectors have been determined. Without using the price of the commodity, embodied energy per unit of mass or volume can be measured using the output quantity of a finished product and the overall embodied energy of the sector producing the product if appropriate data is readily available. Using commodity prices to translate energy intensities to energy units has significant drawbacks because product prices differ and can be under- or over-estimated. For example, the iron and steel mills sector not only produces virgin steel but also a diverse range of structural forms, each with their own sets of prices. Collecting data on total commodity volume in physical quantities is one way to avoid this. The cumulative embodied energy of the entire industry sector can then be determined by multiplying the calculated embodied energy values by the monetary sectoral production. The embodied energy per unit of mass or volume is calculated by dividing this value by the total embodied energy.

As (Manish Kumar, 2013) presents in his PhD thesis the start point for calculating the embodied energy is accessing the Input Output tables. For the continent of Europe this can be found via the [eurostat website](#). This method of calculating the embodied energy is very time-consuming and, for the purpose of this study, off-topic. (Manish Kumar, 2013) has also developed this methodology for a PhD dissertation. Therefore applying this method would not be in the interests of this study and this research will simply state the embodied energy results for the façade materials of the study by (Manish Kumar, 2013) (see [subsection 5.7.4](#)).

5.7.4 Embodied energy of materials

[Table 5.4](#) provides the values of embodied energy calculated by (Manish Kumar, 2013) for each study material. The values are listed for each calculation approach. The first column lists the embodied energy calculated using a basic input-output approach in which the total energy coefficients were calculated by dividing the total requirements with average energy prices. In the second approach, in order to avoid the use of average energy prices, the process data of energy use was inserted into the input-output model. Human and capital energy were added into the next approach. Finally, some sectors were disaggregated to quantify the material-specific embodied energy for materials such as hardwood, plywood, brick, stone, flat glass, gypsum building products, mineral wool insulation, steel, and primary aluminum.

[Figure 5.10](#) demonstrates the energy intensities in MJ kg^{-1} output of the study material sector by energy source calculated by (Manish Kumar, 2013) using the three

TABLE 5.4: Calculated values of embodied energy of study materials. Final Embodied Energy in (MJ kg^{-1}). Adapted from the comprehensive literature review by (Manish Kumar, 2013).

Study Material	IO-based Method	Hybrid Method	Hybrid with Human & Capital Method	After Disaggregation
Hardwood Plywood & Veneer	26.8	32.6	35,4	24,7
Adhesives	130,7	50,2	53,50	53,50
Plastic Pipes & Fittings	98,16	109,1	113,3	113,3
Polystyrene Foam Insulation	243,8	243,5	256,1	256,1
Bricks	4.9	3.7	3.9	4.4
Flat Glass	24.6	23.9	24.6	24.6
Stone	3	2.8	3.3	3.3
Mineral Wool Insulation	27.4	27.7	29.3	29.3
Primary Aluminium	67.9	184.4	186.5	190.7

approaches. It can be seen that the fuel intensities were quite different in the input-output-based and input-output-based hybrid approaches.

Figure 5.11 provides the final values of the embodied energy per unit of study materials' mass calculated by (Manish Kumar, 2013) using the input-output-based hybrid approach after sector disaggregation including human and capital energy. The values of embodied energy are listed by energy source. The relative share of human and capital inputs was significant in the case of study materials such as stone (nearly 15% of the total energy).

5.8 Chapter Brief

In this chapter, the study introduced a broader aspect of embodied energy consideration that a façade engineer should take into account. This chapter also comprehensively discussed the basic definition of embodied energy and its relevant associated terminology. The work of (Manish Kumar, 2013) was the main source of inspiration for this chapter. This chapter presented the research design, methods and results of the study by (Manish Kumar, 2013). His work was basically based on the Input-Output tables of the economy of the United States of America. This emphasises that the presented values in subsection 5.7.4 should be applied very cautiously.

The embodied energy calculation concept is still far from being considered in the planning phases of a façade. Additionally, there are not any benchmark values for the different types of façades and different materials that could make a comparison feasible. This matter will be more discussed in chapter 8 as a future field of study.

FIGURE 5.10: Relative share of energy sources in the total embodied energy intensities of study materials. Reproduced from (Manish Kumar, 2013).

Final Embodied Energy Breakup by Energy Source (MJ/kg)

	Oil & Gas	Coal	Electricity	Natural Gas	Petroleum	Human Energy	Capital Energy	Total Embodied Energy
Hardwood Plywood & Veneer	0,407	0,237	8,0875	3,6	9,637	1,7	0,933	24,6015
Adhesives	1,353	2,493	13,919	11,495	21,06	1,67	1,498	53,488
Plastic Pipes & Fittings	3,712	2,405	26,36	22,839	53,67	2,082	2,296	113,364
Polystyrene Foam Insulation	6,56	7,874	62,343	63,05	103,688	6,708	5,92	256,143
Bricks	0,0116	0,1	0,909	2,454	0,77	0,132	0,0977	4,5
Flat Glass	0,067	0,291	7,006	13,823	2,74	0,365	0,407	24,699
Stone	0,0	0,126	1,1	0,6	1,007	0,309	0,174	3,3
Mineral Wool Insulation	0,153	1,119	11,43	10,413	4,552	0,719	0,909	29,295
Primary Aluminium	5	0,565	137,874	14,289	30,615	1,27	1	190,613

FIGURE 5.11: Final embodied energy values by energy source using hybrid approach after sector disaggregation. Reproduced from (Manish Kumar, 2013).

Chapter 6

Integration of Embodied Energy for Façade in BIM

6.1 What is Building Information Modeling (BIM)?

6.1.1 Introduction

Building Information Modelling (BIM) is based on the idea of the continuous use of a digital building model over the entire life cycle of a building - from design, planning and construction to the operation of the building. It goes hand in hand with the idea of significantly improved data exchange and the resulting increase in planning efficiency by eliminating the time-consuming and error-prone re-entry of information. Thanks to the availability of modern software tools, nothing stands in the way of implementing this vision in planning practice from a technical point of view. While individual, particularly innovative planning offices and construction companies are already using BIM consistently, its widespread introduction in Germany is still pending. The public sector, which has already made the use of BIM in construction planning mandatory in many other countries, has a decisive role to play here (Borrmann et al., 2015).

6.1.2 Definition

A Building Information Model (BIM) is a comprehensive digital image of a building with a great depth of information. In addition to the three-dimensional geometry of the components, it also includes non-geometric additional information such as type information, technical properties, costs or eventually LCA indicators. The term Building Information Modelling describes the process of creating, modifying and managing such a digital building model with the help of corresponding software tools (Borrmann et al., 2015).

In a wider sense, however, this term is also used to describe the use of this digital model over the entire life cycle of the building—from planning, through execution, to management and finally to deconstruction (see [Figure 6.1](#)). This is where the enormous potential of BIM technology lies: if data is consistently used beyond the individual phases, the time-consuming and error-prone re-entry of information that has been common up to now can be reduced to a minimum (Borrmann et al., 2015).

In the US National Building Information Modelling Standard, BIM is defined as follows (NIBS¹):

¹National Institute of Building Sciences in USA.

FIGURE 6.1: Building Information Modelling is based on the continuous use and loss-free dissemination of a digital building model throughout the entire life cycle.

“Building Information Modelling (BIM) is a digital representation of physical and functional characteristics of a facility. A BIM is a shared knowledge resource for information about a facility forming a reliable basis for decisions during its life-cycle; defined as existing from earliest conception to demolition. A basic premise of BIM is collaboration by different stakeholders at different phases of the life cycle of a facility to insert, extract, update or modify information in the BIM to support and reflect the roles of that stakeholder.”

The BIM concept is not new. In fact, the first research papers on the construction and use of virtual building models were published as early as the 1970s (Eastman et al., 1974). The term Building Information Modelling was first used in 1992 in a scientific paper (Nederveen and Tolman, 1992). However, the term only became widespread after it was used by the company Autodesk in a white paper in 2003 Autodesk². In the meantime, extremely powerful software tools are available, so that the concepts, which were initially only developed theoretically, have now found their way into industrial practice (Borrmann et al., 2015).

The most obvious feature of a Building Information Model is the three-dimensional modelling of the building, which enables the derivation of consistent 2D plans for floor plans and sections. What is essential, however, is that BIM design tools, in contrast to pure 3D modellers, offer a catalogue of building-specific objects containing predefined components such as walls, columns, windows, doors, etc. These component objects combine the usually parameterised building elements. These component objects also combine the mostly parameterised 3D geometry representation with further descriptive features and defined relationships to other components. Working with these components is necessary, among other things, so that plans can later be derived from the BIM that comply with the applicable regulations and standards. In addition, the component-orientated modelling of a building also allows for the direct application of various analysis and simulation tools (Borrmann et al., 2015).

6.1.3 BIM in the planning process

With the implementation of the BIM methodology, there are already a number of advantages for the planning process. All technical drawings, including the various views, floor plans and sections, are derived directly from the model and are therefore automatically free of contradictions. Collision checks can be carried out between the sub-models of the various trades in order to detect conflicts at an early stage. Furthermore, various calculation and simulation programmes can be connected, which take over a variety of information, such as the building geometry, directly from the model. This includes static verifications as well as heat requirement calculations, evacuation simulations and lighting analyses. Due to the enormous depth of information offered by a Building Information Model, most of the required input information can be derived directly from the model. To some extent, the model can also be checked for compliance with legal regulations, standards and guidelines. And finally, the BIM model allows for extremely precise quantity takeoff, which forms the basis for a reliable cost estimate and also considerably speeds up the preparation of the bill of quantities for the tender (Borrmann et al., 2015). Additionally, the precise Bill of Quantities can be used for the life cycle assessment.

²Autodesk Industry Solution.

FIGURE 6.2: Planning and decision-making processes. This allows a more comprehensive influence on the design and costs of the resulting building, while at the same time reducing the costs of planning changes (MacLeamy, 2004). It also allows a consideration of the environmental impacts of the design.

The application of BIM in planning results in a shift of effort compared to the previous processes, which is illustrated in Figure 6.2. In conventional planning, the main effort for elaborating the design is made in later phases. This means that the application of various analysis and simulation tools and a comprehensive evaluation of the design are only possible at an advanced stage. By then, however, the possibilities for changing the design are already very limited or lead to considerable additional costs.

In contrast, the BIM-supported planning process shifts the planning effort to the early phases, in which a comprehensive digital model of the design is already created. The advantage of this is that the model can be used for initial simulations and calculations in these early phases. In this way, different design options can be examined in detail, which leads to reduced effort in later planning phases and increased design quality.

6.1.4 BIM model

It is very important to understand the geometry of the model and the structure of information within it in order to be able to run a successful LCA analysis and obtain a valid environmental impact result from the BIM model. BIM models built by different software are structured differently (Braholli, 2019).

The model used in this study was built in Revit, and as a result, the components of the model are categorised according to Revit hierarchy structure. For the dynamic

integrated LCA process, the Revit data structure has to be combined with the necessary LCA environmental information.

The general information related to the environmental impact in the BIM model is categorised as level zero information for the LCA. Every component in a Revit model falls under a specified category which contains the information of the first LCA level. Categories are divided into subdivisions which are known as 'Revit families'. Furthermore, 'types' is the term used to identify different Revit families, like a wall type that is composed of several layers.

In Revit, each element contains identification data like the dimensions or the material. This is considered as the second level of information that is contained in a Revit element (Braholli, 2019).

The third level of information in the Revit built model would be the material unit. Each material in Revit contains numerical information about its volume and area. Usually, the Revit materials also contain the sub-materials. For example, the wall material contains the brick material and the mortar material. This would be the deepest level of information in a BIM model (Hollberg and Ruth, 2016).

In this case, for the software to be able to extract an accurate value of the material quantity, each one of the materials and sub-materials should be separately modelled in Revit. Otherwise, the LCA results would not be accurate. The other solution is to choose from the material database the material that has already calculated the percentage of the sub-material (like the mortar in the brick wall). This can be possible by using the material database presented in [section 6.3](#).

6.1.5 BIM maturity for LCA integration

Integrating BIM and LCA would be a very beneficial approach in developing automated procedures for the calculation of the environmental impact. In order for this to happen the BIM model should reach a certain level of information that enables an automated tool to perform the LCA procedure (Hollberg and Ruth, 2016).

For a good LCA measurement in a BIM model, the degree of progress (the LOD) is critical. The required information for the procedure is determined by the model LOD and the software's ability to achieve that level and measure the built elements (Braholli, 2019).

It is important to connect the material from the chosen LCA database and the type of material in the BIM model in order to link the LCA data with the BIM model. This process can be accomplished by giving the material in the database the same identification number (ID number) as the one in Revit. If this process is followed correctly, an LCA measurement may be performed as early as the building's design phase.

In this case, the BIM maturity is critical to the operation. A well-structured model should include materials that are exactly the same as the ones that will be used from the chosen LCA database. Although it is a time-consuming operation, material mapping between the LCA database and the model should be performed manually

FIGURE 6.3: BIM maturity matrix proposed by Mark Bew and Mervyn Richards.

(see Figure 6.3).

6.1.6 Level of development in BIM-LCA integration

The level of development combines the levels of geometry and knowledge into a single element (Dupuis et al., 2017). The BIM model's LOD plays an important role in the LCA measurement process and the accuracy of the results.

The model should have a given volume for each element and all layers should be separately modelled in order to integrate BIM and LCA with automated procedures. The volumetric details, as well as other information such as the name and type of material, the construction process, and the composition, must be accurately extracted from Revit elements. As a result, data entry in the BIM model becomes a critical process that necessitates great care and precision.

6.2 Integration of LCA in BIM

A 'whole-building LCA' is the most common form of LCA in architecture, in which an entire building is studied at all stages of its life cycle. The results of these studies are reported in documents called environmental product declarations, which are used

by building material suppliers to analyse an individual product or material (EPDs³). The material and energy flows between the building and nature are analysed in a whole building LCA, including resources used, waste, and pollution to the air, water, and soil (O'Connor and Bowick, 2014).

The AIA⁴ has published a guide that explains what an LCA is and provides architects with guidance and suggestions for conducting one. The AIA recognises the importance of LCA in architecture, noting that 'the greatest motivation' for using LCA in the design phase is the ability of an architect to show the client that using LCA can boost and demonstrate the project's 'green-ness,' as well as aid significantly in increasing long-term paybacks through better decision making.

Most design processes have six phases, starting with pre-design or preliminary studies and ending with closeout or usage. The first of the six stages focuses on collecting preliminary data in order to start the design process (Hollberg and Ruth, 2016). This stage of the design process includes site analysis, feasibility studies and programming. The schematic design, also known as conceptual design, is the second level. This stage of the process marks the start of a series of design decisions; fundamental decisions affecting the shape and orientation are taken here (Hollberg and Ruth, 2016). The concept is refined and built in the third level. Although basic material choices are made at this point, there are still many unknowns about the building's architecture (Hollberg and Ruth, 2016). The layout of construction specifics takes place in the fourth level (Hollberg and Ruth, 2016). The development of construction documents and specifications takes place at this point. The design and closeout processes make up the final stage, which marks the transition between the construction and use phases of a building's life cycle (Hollberg and Ruth, 2016; Shreve, 2018) (see Figure 6.4).

The nature of the design process makes it difficult to determine when an LCA will be implemented. A bill of materials is needed to specify the quantities of materials in order to measure the embodied impacts. The precise bill of quantities, as Hollberg and Ruth call it, is only available towards the end of the design process, usually during the construction documentation phase. The act of conducting a whole building LCA is usually reserved for projects seeking green building certification due to a lack of data in the early design stages (Hollberg and Ruth, 2016). The earlier decisions are taken in the design process, and the less modifications to these decisions at later times, the greater the potential for reducing the building's environmental effects, according to (Basbagill et al., 2013). Hollberg and Ruth endorse this idea of incorporating LCA early in the design process, recommending that it be done during the schematic design phase (which they refer to as concept design) because significant design changes made after this point are expensive and time-consuming to correct⁵.

In their research (Hollberg and Ruth, 2016) identified 4 basic types of LCA tools, cataloging software based on this categorisation and their functionality.

The first of the four categories are the 'generic LCA tools' (see section 6.6), examples of which include GaBi, SimaPro, or Open LCA. These tools typically utilise a

³Environmental Product Declaration.

⁴The American Institute of Architects.

⁵This is a sentiment backed by many supporters of early stage LCA in the design process (Hollberg and Ruth, 2016).

FIGURE 6.4: The implementation within the context of the design process can be difficult, but the stage at which it is implemented determines the effectiveness of the analysis. Reproduced from *LCA in Architectural Design – a parametric approach* by (Hollberg and Ruth, 2016).

tabular format for inputting and interpreting data, (Hollberg and Ruth, 2016) state that these tools are not practical and do not integrate into the design process like some of the tools described in other categories. The second group, dubbed ‘Spreadsheet-based calculations,’ makes use of spreadsheets as the primary method for data input and analysis. To measure the environmental effects, most of the applications in this group used a bill of materials. A material’s embodied impacts are calculated by multiplying its mass by environmental data, which is usually obtained via EPDs. The process of converting a bill of materials into a tabular format may be time-consuming and error-prone; additionally, if several design variants exist, architects cannot thoroughly investigate the implications in order to make an effective design decision. (Hollberg and Ruth, 2016).

The third category ‘building component catalogues’ focuses on the development of building material databases. Like the spreadsheet-based tools, these databases are represented in a tabular format and feature predefined components that allow architects to change the parameters of the design quickly (Hollberg and Ruth, 2016). These tools, like the spreadsheet-based tools, require significant labour, and any changes made during the process require a feedback loop to recalculate the impacts.

‘CAD integrated tools,’ the fourth and final category, are incorporated into widely used drafting systems such as AutoCAD and Revit. A bill of materials is created during the modelling phase rather than at the end of the design process in this case. The introduction of Building Information Modelling into the early stages of construction, according to (Hollberg and Ruth, 2016), is the main issue with this method of

measuring embodied impacts.

LCAs typically use material weights and sizes, as well as chemical and waste outputs, while CAD and BIM systems use assemblies represented in linear feet or square feet (Bates et al., 2013). Despite the challenges of implementing BIM integrated LCA in the field of architecture, this represents the most significant opportunity for streamlining the entire building LCA phase. Figure 6.5 depicts the applications available to programmers, as well as the categories and functions that they fall under.

(Tsikos and Negendahl, 2017) believe that ‘the integration of projects’ LCA studies in BIM will not only make LCA faster but by using the graphical interface of BIM tools, the results from the LCA will be communicated better among the different engineering disciplines and architects.’

Architects will create an environment in which LCA is compatible with the design process, providing a design method that will allow for the analysis of a range of design variants, by combining LCA and BIM. According to (Shadram et al., 2016), the knowledge sharing properties that are incorporated into the BIM practice would be useful when determining environmental concerns. The opportunities presented by BIM have the potential to achieve significant time and cost savings, compared to traditional LCA processes.

(Tsikos and Negendahl, 2017) provide the best example for how LCA can be integrated with LCA using visual programming language (VPL).

(Tsikos and Negendahl, 2017) used dynamo, a VPL add-in built for Revit, to investigate the effects of combining LCA analysis with Revit. The aim of this model is to build a permanent connection between Revit Materials and a Life Cycle Inventory database so that the LCA process can be completed with no input from designers. The calculations needed to complete an LCA can be done during the modelling phase by linking the materials in the LCI database to the materials in Revit. This helps designers to construct a single model of a building and perform energy analysis without having to create additional models. The bridge between Revit and the LCI database executes the functions of the LCA programme and produces tabular and graphical outputs (Tsikos and Negendahl, 2017) in the modelling process, known as an Integrated Dynamic Model. The use of visual programming language offers the most versatility of all the BIM integrated LCA processes. The software used as an intermediary, on the other hand, necessitates a basic understanding of programming principles and can be time-consuming to learn. Despite this (Tsikos and Negendahl, 2017) state that ‘the IDM’s strongest advantage though, is the fact that it is a tool that can be easily modified by the user to meet any specific requirement.’⁶

Table 6.1 outlines the results of the analysis, identifying the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats that can come because of the integration of LCA and BIM methodologies (Diaz and Antön, 2014).

The benefits and strengths that integrating LCA into BIM practices brings to the practice of architecture, as seen in Table 6.1, highlight the value of examining

⁶If given the opportunity, the use of Dynamo as a tool for the completion of an LCA analysis provides the most flexibility in developing a solution for implementation in the early stages of the design process. However, through the course of learning the programme, much of the work involves tinkering with the program to get the desired results, something that can become time-consuming.

Type	Name	3D Model	Energy Demand Calculation	Embodied Impact Calculation	Optimisation	Online/Offline	Country
Generic LCA Tools	GaBi			●		Off	Germany
	SimaPro			●		Off	Netherlands
	OpenLCA			●		Off	Germany
	Umberto			●		Off	Germany
Spreadsheet-based Tools	Envest 2			●	□	On	UK
	SBS Building Sustainability		□	●		On	Germany
	Ökobilanz Bau		□	●		On	Germany
	eTOOL		□	●		On	Australia
	Athena Impact Estimator		□	●		Off	Canada
	Legep		●	●	□	Off	Germany
	Elodie		●	●		Off	France
GreenCalc+			●		Off	Netherlands	
Component Catalogues	EcoSoft			●		On	Austria
	Bauteilkatalog			●		On	Switzerland
	eLCA		□	●		On	Germany
	BEES			●		On	US
CAD Integrated	Impact	●	□	●		On	UK
	Cocon-BIM	□	●	●		Off	France
	Lesoi	□	●	●		Off	Switzerland
	360optimi	●	●	●		Off	Finland
	Tally	●	□	●		Off	US
	OneClick LCA*		●	●	□	On	Finland

● Full Functionality

□ Partial Functionality

* Revit Plug-in is still Beta version, status: April 18th, 2021

FIGURE 6.5: Present computer-aided LCA tools reproduced from (Hollberg and Ruth, 2016) and (Shreve, 2018).

TABLE 6.1: SWOT (S: Strength, W: Weakness, O: Opportunities, T: Threats) Analysis of LCA integration with BIM. Reproduced from (Díaz and Antón, 2014).

Label	Description
S	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Higher capacity for accommodating the three pillars of sustainability • More extensive use of environmental criteria by various stakeholders • Increased efficiency with regard to environmental assessment, making this task easier and less time-consuming • Avoidance of manual data re-entry • More information available about the project during early phases, leading to greater benefits in general • Higher effectiveness of environmental assessment due to its being performed in early design stages • Possibility to compare predicted environmental performance with real performance and chance to learn from experience
W	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Different stakeholders involved in the construction industry must be trained to include environmental criteria in their assessments • LCA process and way of presenting data are not standardised • Lack of environmental data for carrying out LCA • Assumptions have to be made for LCA calculation, thus increasing uncertainty of the assessment
O	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • It is becoming compulsory in the construction sector to consider environmental criteria. Various initiatives are being launched by different governments and the European Union for this purpose • There is increased demand for sustainable constructions in the market • These tools already exist. It is just a matter of integrating them to generate synergies • There is real need of a tool with such features in the market • There is a direct need to change the way of working in the construction industry, and as such an integrated tool and its application in the early design phases could contribute to this change • BIM is already becoming more widely accepted in the construction industry. If LCA is integrated in the BIM framework, this will make it even more acceptable for the stakeholders
T	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sometimes construction industry stakeholders are not aware of the importance of considering environmental aspects among project criteria at an early stage • Some stakeholders may refuse to implement this step due to the effort required to integrate the tool in the early design phases • There is a lack of research and development in the construction industry • There is a wide variety of stakeholders with different characteristics involved in the construction industry. This hinders standardisation in the industry and makes it more difficult to implement change • There is a lack of interoperability between different software systems

embodied environmental impacts. The SWOT review identified two major roadblocks: stakeholder participation and a lack of data and study on LCA integrated with BIM. These concerns, however, do not seem to be long-term problems; rather, they will be addressed as the practice of conducting whole-building LCA gains traction.

6.3 LCA Database Providers

Various LCA software instruments have been developed over the last 25 years. They began in the packaging industry and are now used in a wide variety of applications. They are gaining popularity in the construction industry. The environmental effect of a material or a building can be addressed using software. [Figure 6.5](#) displays the criteria. The programme will use ecological parameters to categorise the portion of the building that is being evaluated. Some software tools can evaluate the environmental effect of an entire house, while others only consider parts of it. Tools on the material level only consider the building substance; products on the building level should provide the ecological component of the operating energy.

In databases, you can find a collection of LCA data. A variety of databases are available, some of which are free to use. Some databases were published in XML format, which allows for easy access without the need for special software and provides a short and comprehensive overview. This type of information can easily be used to compare materials based on mass and volume. Some databases provide LCA data from the literature, while others show evaluation outcomes. The accuracy of context information must be reviewed for researched databases. Several free databases, such as Wecobis and Ökobau.dat, are available from the German government at [Nachhaltiges Bauen](#). Here some other examples:

- [ecoinvent](#)
- [openLCA](#)
- [The Evah Institute](#)
- [OneClick LCA](#)
- [Federal LCA Commons](#)
- [Environmental Footprint](#)
- [idea](#)
- [agri-footprint](#)
- [arvi](#). Publication database for the LCA topic.
- [AGRIBALYSE](#)
- [EuGeos' 15804+A2](#)
- [LC-Inventories from Switzerland](#)
- [Ökobaudat](#)
- [exiobase](#)
- [PSILCA](#). Social Life Cycle Assessment database.

- **Social Hotspot database.** Social Life Cycle Assessment.
- **ProBas.** The ProBas web portal represents a library for life cycle facts by German Federal Environmental Agency.

6.3.1 GaBi

PE International GmbH distributes GaBi (acronym for Ganzheitliche Bilanzierung, English: Holistic Assessment), a programme developed by the University of Stuttgart's Chair of Building Physics. GaBi basic, the first edition, was created in 1991 with the aim of calculating the environmental performance of industrial goods. Since then, several new versions have been released, culminating in GaBi 8.7.1 today. There are different life cycle stages and impact evaluation approaches to choose from. A database for material flows and construction materials is included in GaBi. It is also possible to provide output energy based on its environmental effects. The same can be said for steps of maintenance and refurbishment. They must be meticulously modelled. Built-it is a software feature that was created to make the building LCA process easier. Built-it's key feature is the subdivision of costs into building element levels according to DIN 276 Building Costs.

The programme necessitates a great deal of detail, provides a wide range of scenarios since each step is modelled separately, and presents the results with a high level of clarity and complexity.

6.3.2 Ecoinvent

Under Frischknecht's leadership, the ETH institutes (Paul Scherrer Institute, EMPA, Agroscope Reckenholz Tänikon, ART) published the LCA database 'ecoinvent' in 2003. According to their discipline, the institutes contribute LCA data. The information was compiled using European and Swiss elementary flows. The transport of goods, according to this, requires national and European average distances. The simple flow of information from the user is entered into a query tool. The information is saved in a database, which is used to calculate processes. The conversion of flows to processes allows for the use of the same measurement frame, resulting in database comparability. Ecoinvent gives the user the option to select from a variety of characterisation models. The popular LCIA models, such as CED, EcoIndicator 99, and the CML system, are all included in the ecoinvent database.

6.3.3 Ökobau.dat

PE International, an LCA firm, compiled Ökobau.dat, which was published by the German government in 2008. It is available in xml format, as well as in the JRC-defined ILCD format and as a software configuration. The database was designed for GaBi, but is also used by other software products, such as SimaPro. Professional software is not needed for the xml and ILCD formats. The ILCD file provides details on included life stages, end-of-life scenarios, and validity, while the database provides fast information.

FIGURE 6.6: LCA conventional method diagram reproduced from (Braholli, 2019).

6.4 Different Approaches of Integration of LCA in BIM

6.4.1 Conventional method

Many construction firms are currently employing this system. The procedure is also used by the generic LCA tools, such as spreadsheet-based and online component catalogues, which were described earlier. The calculations begin with manually extracting the bill of quantities from a 2D, 3D project or automatically extracting the bill of quantities from a BIM model. The values are then entered into the instrument, which is multiplied by the environmental impact indicators to produce the LCA performance. The indicators are manually entered into the tool or linked to the LCA database. The entire process is dependent on the project's construction phase, as the LCA requires sufficient data. Finally as aforementioned, since the calculations are done manually, the procedure is time-consuming in general and can result in a high error rate. Another drawback is that information flows only in one direction because the LCA findings are not linked to the model, making decision-making more challenging and complicated. In addition, to perform the procedures and calculations for LCA using traditional methods, an expert with specialised expertise in the field is needed (see Figure 6.6) (Braholli, 2019).

6.4.2 Static method with BIM tools

This approach uses third-party LCA software to calculate the LCA based on BIM model knowledge. The BIM model extracts the information in a standard exchange format that allows the tools to perform the calculations.

In this case, using an IFC file from a BIM model provides direct access to the model by eliminating the need to repeat data entry in the LCA tool. In any case, the data only flows in one direction, from the BIM model to the LCA tool, and not the other way around. When the BIM model is changed and the data has to be reloaded in the tool, interoperability issues may arise. The advantages of this approach are that it eliminates manual data entry from the beginning by replacing it with IFC or gbXML format exchange, and it can provide more LCA analysis results than conventional methods. Changes to the BIM model and reloading the details in the LCA calculation

FIGURE 6.7: LCA static method diagram with BIM tools reproduced from (Braholli, 2019).

tool are two disadvantages of the static LCA method. Furthermore, the data extracted in the exchange format (IFC, gbXML) is minimal, and interoperability issues can result in data loss. In this scenario, the evaluation results may be incomplete or incorrect. Technical systems are normally excluded from LCA calculations because they lack the requisite LOD for the process. Instead, they are calculated as a percentage of the overall number and added to the final figures (see [Figure 6.7](#))(Braholli, 2019).

6.4.3 Dynamic BIM integrated method

If a BIM model is available from which the Bill of Quantities can be automatically collected, this approach can be used. Following that, a parametric tool can be used to connect the extracted BOQ to an LCA database and conduct LCA analysis. In order for the method to operate, the quantities from the BIM model must be mapped and compared to the LCA parameters. This method is often aided by the construction phase. The dynamic approach allows the LCA values to be re-assigned to the BIM model and the details to be completed. Making decisions is still difficult, but in this situation, direct input during the design phase is possible. By combining BIM and LCA tools, it is possible to address some of the most significant drawbacks. Three of the main pillars of sustainability (environmental, economic, and social) should be considered from the beginning of the design process and addressed more effectively as a result (see [Figure 6.8](#)) (Braholli, 2019).

Application of OneClick LCA

OneClick LCA is an automated life cycle assessment software based in Finland that helps with the calculation of LCA. The programme owns a large database of EPDs. It has recently started to provide guidance for the companies seeking to apply to obtain EPD for their products. OneClick LCA is a cloud-based programme. In addition, the owner company Bionova Ltd. has recently developed plug-ins for structural programmes such as **Tekla** and **Grasshopper**. OneClick LCA is also available with a beta version of plug-in in Revit (see [Figure 6.9](#)).

OneClick LCA software can be used in three different ways in Revit to perform LCA analysis and calculate environmental impacts:

FIGURE 6.8: LCA dynamic method diagram integrated in BIM tools reproduced from (Braholli, 2019).

FIGURE 6.9: OneClick LCA plug-in beta version for Revit.

1. LCA procedure in the online application by manually inserting the data from the extracted BOQ
2. LCA procedure with Revit plug-in and OneClick LCA cloud
3. LCA procedure by importing IFC model and using Simple BIM

There is one other possible way of conducting LCA with the help of OneClick LCA in Revit, which is with the help of Revit-in-Rhino plug-in. This plug-in makes it possible to connect the model of Revit to Grasshopper through Rhino and there, with the help of the developed plug-in for OneClick LCA for the Grasshopper, the calculation can be executed.

The application of OneClick LCA needs a license.

Application of Tally plug-in

Tally is a BIM-integrated tool that allows you to perform LCA analysis directly from your Revit model. It is added to the Revit add-ins tab as a plug-in. Tally conducts the LCA study using North American standards and environmental factors. In contrast to OneClick LCA, it considers eight environmental impact categories, six of which

Tally™ pulls material quantities from the Revit model to create an accurate bill of goods.

FIGURE 6.10: Tally plug-in for Revit.

are compatible between the two methods. The information is collected directly from the BIM model in this case, as well as in the OneClick LCA plug-in, as an automated technique, which reduces the margin of error and information loss compared to other static methods. The materials are directly mapped in the plug-in, and the LCA analysis is completed by producing an Excel and PDF report. The user can easily understand and compare the findings, which are presented graphically. Tally, like OneClick, enhances the environmental decision-making process during the design phase by providing this semi-dynamic operating tool integrated with BIM software.

Also, according to the software's website: 'Tally facilitates the quantification of a life cycle assessment of building materials for whole building analysis as well as comparative analyses of design options.'

The process of the LCA within the Tally framework utilises GaBi 6 and the GaBi database to calculate the embodied impacts of building materials⁷.

The Figure 6.10 shows the workflow of the Tally software from the Revit model to the Tally Report.

Another benefit of Tally is the way the LCA data is organised and presented. Tally categorises and presents the data of the analysis in three ways: by life cycle stage, by division, and by Revit category. For the purposes of identifying hotspots within the

⁷Tally was developed by the architectural firm Kieran Timberlake. The tool successfully integrates the BIM software with the complex modelling processes associated with LCA analysis tools like GaBi 6.

TABLE 6.2: Comparison between integrated tools from OneClick LCA and the Tally plug-in.

	OneClick LCA	Tally
Type	Online platform and software, BIM integrated plug-in	BIM integrated plug-in
Open BIM interoperability	IFC, gbXML, Excel file upload, manual data entry, direct Revit interaction	IFC, direct Revit interaction
Material Databases	Large database of materials and EPD from several geographical regions and manufacturers, Several filters available by material, database, region, manufacturer	Custom database based on the GaBi database
BIM integration	plug-in, Design Authoring	plug-in
Tool advantages	Large material database Integrated Sustainability Certification. Several ways of data visualisation and interpretation Carbon designer tool. Baseline design offered and can be modified	Very well integrated with Revit software. Accurate comparative results in between design solutions and different material choices

buildings, the categorisation by Revit families will be utilised as the main comparison between baseline and prototype.

This shows the depth at which embodied energy analyses can occur. Using the data above, architects can make design decisions focused on several criteria such as maximising the energy demand from renewable resources within a project.

6.4.4 Tally vs. OneClick LCA

The LCA results are affected by the differences in EPD databases between OneClick LCA and Tally analysis. Using databases that differ as a result of selected geographical areas can produce different outcomes as the LCA analysis depends on the chosen material.

Another important conclusion is revealed regarding the interoperability of the tools with the BIM model and its level of detail. Since the geometrical and semantic data is directly extracted from the BIM model to perform the LCA analysis, the level of detail has a high impact on these calculations. Various issues were recorded during both procedures as a result of the lack of details in the analysed model.

On the other hand, the automated approach in the extraction of the material quantities from the model has lowers the error margin in the obtained information and eliminates as much of the loss of information as possible, compared to static and traditional methods.

6.5 Environmental Product Declaration

6.5.1 Introduction

Chapter 5 presented the scientific and theoretical solutions to address both Embodied Energy and Initial Embodied Energy. However, in practice, the method which (Manish Kumar, 2013) presents is based on input-output data economic tables, which can be found on the Eurostat website. For the purpose of this study, it is not pressing to deal nor process with such massive input-output tables.

The other alternative is to use EPDs⁸. For the whole purpose of this study, EPDs could provide some initial energy flow data. EPDs have increased in popularity over the last few years. To get a better understanding of an EPD, this chapter will answer the following questions:

- What is an EPD?
- What is the basic structure of an EPD?
- What are the different types of EPDs?
- How should EPDs be compared to each other?

This section has been derived mostly from (EN 15804+A2, 2019). This standard is the main guideline for conducting an EPD. So, to understand EPDs, this section will delve into this subject. First, section 6.5 gives a short introduction to the primary purpose of conducting an EPD. Then, it discusses different elements of an EPD (see Figure 6.11). The next step is to summarise the needed information from (EN 15804+A2, 2019) very strictly.

6.5.2 Definition

‘An EPD according to (EN 15804+A2, 2019) standard provides quantified environmental information for a construction product or service on a harmonised and scientific basis. It also provides information on health-related emissions to indoor air, soil, and water during the use stage of the building. The purpose of an EPD in the construction sector is to provide the basis for assessing buildings and other construction works and identifying those, which cause less stress to the environment.’

An EPD communicates verifiable, accurate, non-misleading environmental information for products and their applications, thereby supporting scientifically-based, fair choices and stimulating the potential for market-driven continuous environmental improvement.

EPD information is expressed in information modules, which allow easy organisation and expression of data packages throughout the life cycle of the product. The approach requires that the underlying data should be consistent, reproducible, and comparable.

6.5.3 Types of EPD

The types of EPD are defined with respect to life cycle stages, which they cover. All construction products and materials shall declare modules A1–A3, modules C1–C4 and module D. There are conditions in which products can be exempt, if they fulfil:

⁸Environmental Product Declaration.

FIGURE 6.11: Simplified structure of an EPD. An EPD consists of three main pillars, Programme Operator, Third Party Verification, and last but not least Product Category Rules. This study does not discuss the first two parts rigorously. But it will give a short introduction about Programme Operator and Third Party Verification. On the other hand, Product Category Rules are the main focus in this chapter.

TABLE 6.3: The types of EPD: It corresponds with Figure 6.12. Type one in Figure 6.12 is with almost white colour illustrated and the colour change continues to dark blue in accordance with the sequence of types' number here in this table.

Number	System boundary	Definition
1(white)	Cradle to gate with modules C1–C4 and module D	Minimum of stages to be declared for the default EPD
2(light grey)	Cradle to gate with options A1–A3, C, D and additional modules (A4 and/or A5 and/or B1–B7)	Shall be based on a functional unit or declared unit
3(grey)	Cradle to grave and module D	Shall be based on a functional unit or declared unit
4(dark grey)	Cradle to gate (A1–A3)	The minimum to be declared for all construction products with exemption. Not allowed for products containing biogenic carbon.
5(blue)	Cradle to gate with options A1–A3 and additional modules (A4 and/or A5)	Only possible for construction products with exemptions

The product or material is physically integrated with other products during installation so cannot be physically separated from them at end of life.

The product or material is no longer identifiable at end of life as a result of a physical or chemical transformation process.

The product or material does not contain biogenic carbon.

Construction products and materials that are identified as exemptions may omit the modules C1–C4 and D. They shall provide information on where to find scenarios for the end of life modules as a justification.

The types of EPD also known as *system boundaries* are shown in Table 6.3. It is possible to have an EPD for a substance or preparation (e.g. cement), for product (e.g. window), for a construction service (e.g. cleaning services as part of maintenance) and for an assemblage of products and/or a construction element (e.g. wall) or technical equipment (e.g. lift). For the type of calculation of EPD see Figure 6.13.

6.5.4 Comparability of EPD for construction products

According to (EN 15804+A2, 2019), the comparability of EPD of products is defined by the contribution that the products make to the environmental performance. In this matter there are two important aspects which shall be considered:

1. *to be based on the product's use in and its impacts on the building.*
2. *the complete life cycle (all information modules).*

Additionally, EPDs that are not in a building context are not tools to compare construction products and construction services. Also, for the comparison at the sub-building level, e.g. for assembled systems, components, products for one or more life cycle

	One product	Many products
One manufacturer	Product and manufacturer specific (one/several plants)	Product group and manufacturer specific (one/several plants)
Many manufacturer	Product specific but many manufacturers average (industry average EPD)	<i>Practically not possible</i>

FIGURE 6.13: EPD can be calculated at different levels and for material, product, assembly or system. Product EPD can give conversion tables for variant products.

stages, the basis for comparison of the assessment is the entire building. This shall be maintained by ensuring that:

- the same functional requirements as defined by legislation or in the client's brief are met.
- the environmental performance and technical performance of any assembled systems, components, or products excluded are the same.
- the amounts of any material excluded are the same.
- excluded processes, modules or life cycle stages are the same.
- the influence of the product systems on the operational aspects and impacts of the construction workers are taken into account.
- the elementary flows related to material inherent properties, such as biogenic carbon content, the potential to carbonate or the net calorific value of a material, are considered completely and consistently.

There are further notes which should be considered:

For the sustainability assessment of buildings comparisons of the environmental aspects and impacts need to be undertaken in conjunction with the social and economic aspects related *to the building*.

For the interpretation of a comparison, benchmarks or reference values are needed. The difference between two products may be insignificant in the building context.

Where an EPD does not cover all life cycle stages relevant for the comparison or if the assumptions underlying the scenario of a declared information module are not applicable in the building context, then investigations will be required to determine the environmental aspects and impacts of specific scenarios for the calculation of modules beyond the cradle to gate modules. These calculations shall be based on scenarios and conditions that are appropriate for the building as the object of assessment.

6.5.5 Introduction to (EN 15804+A2, 2019)

General

This European standard provides core product category rules (which are discussed in [subsection 6.5.6](#)) for all construction products and services. The aim of the standard is to provide a structure to ensure that all Environmental Product Declarations (EPD) of construction products, construction services and construction processes are derived, verified and presented in a harmonised way.

The process of the standardisation of EN 15804 has taken place in accordance with EN ISO 14025. The EN 15804 will cover all the common issues horizontally for all product types in order to minimise vertical (branch specific) deviations. The standard deals with a set of quantifiable, predetermined environmental impact indicators (EN 15804+A2, 2019).

Thus a set of standards are provided that are intended to assess the sustainability of construction works, the means for developing a Type III environmental declaration of construction products. These standards are listed below:

- EN 15643–1, *Sustainability of construction works – Sustainability assessment of buildings–Part1: General framework*
- EN 15643–2, *Sustainability of construction works – Assessment of buildings–Part2: Framework for the assessment of environmental performance*
- EN 15978, *Sustainability of construction works – Assessment of environmental performance of buildings–Calculation method*
- CEN/TR 15941, *Sustainability of construction works – Environmental product declarations – Methodology for selection and use of generic data*
- EN 15942, *Sustainability of construction works – Environmental product declarations – Communication formats: business to business*

Scope

As mentioned in [section 6.5.5](#), this standard provides core product category rules (PCR) for Type III environmental declarations for any construction product and construction service. However, it should be noted that the assessment of social and economic performances at product level is not covered by this standard (EN 15804+A2, 2019). The core PCR defined in this standard describes:

1. The indicators to be declared, information to be provided and the way in which they are collated and reported
2. Which stages of a product's life cycle are considered in the EPD and which processes are to be included in the life cycle stages
3. Rules for the development of scenarios
4. The rules for calculating the Life Cycle Inventory and the Life Cycle Impact Assessment (see [section 4.7](#) and [section 4.6](#)) underlying the EPD, including the specification of the data quality to be applied
5. The rules for reporting predetermined, environmental and health information, that is not covered by LCA for a product, construction process and construction service where necessary

6. The conditions services under which construction products can be compared based on the information provided by EPD

Additionally, it emphasises that the rules and requirements for the EPD of construction services and construction products will be identical.

Terms and definitions

As with all other standards, the standard EN 15804 in its structure follows for its purposes a specific definition of the terms, which is selectively listed as follows. Some of the terms have been already discussed in the last four chapters. Still, here it is important to consider the terminology of the EN 15804.

Ancillary material: input material or product that is used by the unit process producing the product, but which does not constitute part of the product.

Comparative assertion: environmental claim regarding the superiority or equivalence of one product versus a competing product that performs the same function.

Functional equivalent: quantified functional requirements and/or technical requirements for a building or an assembled system (part of works) for use as a basis for comparison.

Information module: compilation of data to be used as a basis for a Type III environmental declaration covering a unit process or a combination of unit processes that are part of the life cycle of a product.

Life cycle assessment (LCA): compilation and evaluation of the inputs, outputs and the potential environmental impacts of a product system throughout its life cycle.

Life cycle inventory analysis (LCI): phase of life cycle assessment involving the compilation and quantification of inputs and outputs for a product throughout its life cycle.

Non-renewable energy: energy from sources which are not defined as renewable energy sources.

Non-renewable resource: resource that exists in a finite amount that cannot be replenished on a human time scale.

Product category rule (PCR): set of specific rules, requirements and guidelines for developing Type III environmental declarations for one or more product categories.

Programme operator: body or bodies that conduct a Type III environmental declaration programme. It can be a group of companies, industrial sector or trade association, public authorities or agencies, or an independent scientific body or other organisation.

Renewable energy: energy from renewable non-fossil sources. Examples include: wind, solar, aerothermal, geothermal, hydrothermal and ocean energy, hydropower, biomass, landfill gas, sewage treatment, plant gas and biogases.

Renewable resource: resource that is grown, naturally replenished or naturally cleansed, on a human time-scale. It is capable of being exhausted, but may last indefinitely with proper stewardship (like trees in forests). Activities that occur in

the technosphere such as recycling are not considered natural replenishment or natural cleansing. Human time scale here refers to the typical life of a human rather than the time humans have been in existence.

Reference service life (RSL): service life of a construction product which is known to be expected under a set of reference in-use conditions and which can form the basis for estimating the service life under other in-use conditions. The RSL is described as part of the functional unit and considered in the calculation of replacements at both the construction product level and construction works level (B4) and refurbishment (B5).

Secondary fuel: fuel recovered from previous use or from waste which substitutes primary fuels. This type of fuel is considered from the point where the secondary fuel enters the system from the previous system. Any combustible material recovered from previous use or from waste from the previous product system and used as a fuel in a following system is a secondary fuel (like solvents, wood, tyres, oil, animal fats)). Examples for primary fuels are: coal, natural gas, biomass.

Secondary material: material recovered from previous use or from waste which substitutes primary materials. It is measured from when it enters the system from another system. Materials recovered from previous use or from waste from one product system and used as an input in another product system are secondary materials. Examples include: recycled scrap metal, crushed concrete, glass cullet, recycled wood chips, recycled plastic.

Type III environmental declaration: environmental declaration providing quantified environmental data using predetermined indicators and, where relevant, additional environmental information. The calculations are based on ISO 14040 and ISO 14044. Type III declaration is actually adapted from ISO 14025:2006.

Upstream, downstream process: process(s) that either precedes (upstream) or follows (downstream) a given life cycle stage.

6.5.6 Product category rule

(EN 15804+A2, 2019) defines the PCR as follows:

'The product category referred to in this standard includes all construction products and construction services for buildings and other construction works.'

The environmental information of an EPD covering all life cycle stages and module D (cradle to grave and module D) shall be subdivided into the modules A1 – A3, A4 – A5, B1 – B7, C1 – C4 and module D (see [Figure 6.14](#)).

General

Both the functional unit and declared unit provide a reference by means of which the material flows (input and output data) for each information module of a construction product are normalised (in a mathematical sense) to produce data, expressed on a common basis. The functional or declared unit provides the reference for combining material flows attributed to the construction product and for the addition⁹ of environmental impacts for the selected stages of the construction product's life cycle at

⁹Addition here means the calculation of environmental impacts of a building or construction works by summation of the quantified impacts per indicator and per module of the construction products constituting the building.

the building level. The functional unit should specify some particular points, which are depicted in [Figure 6.15](#).

Objective of the core PCR

The objective of the core PCR can be summarised in the following six points:

1. The provision of verifiable and consistent data for an EPD, based on LCA
2. The provision of verifiable and consistent product-related technical data or scenarios for the assessment of the environmental performance of buildings
3. The provision of verifiable and consistent product-related technical data or scenarios potentially related to the health of users for the assessment of the performance of buildings
4. That comparisons between construction products are carried out in the context of their application in the building
5. The communication of the environmental information of construction products from business to business
6. The basis, subject to additional requirements, for the communication of the environmental information of construction products to consumers

Functional unit

The primary purpose of the functional unit in LCA studies according to ISO 14044 is to provide a reference by which material flows, LCA results and any other information are normalised to produce data expressed on a common basis. This allows for a comparison with other product systems which have been assessed to fulfil the same functional unit.

Declared unit

The declared unit may be used as an alternative to a functional unit. It shall be applied if a functional unit cannot be defined, e.g. since a function of the product cannot unequivocally be described. The declared unit in the EPD shall be declared applying one of the unit types listed in [Table 6.4](#).

6.5.7 Product stage A1-A3

The product stage is an EPD data module that must be included. It contains the data modules A1 to A3, as shown in [Figure 6.12](#). The system's natural boundary is defined as the processes that provide the system's material and energy inputs, as well as the subsequent manufacturing and transportation processes up to the factory gate, as well as the processing of any waste produced by those processes.

The system boundary between the system under analysis and the previous system (providing the secondary materials) is set when the previous system's outputs, such as materials, goods, building elements, or electricity, enter the end-of-waste state in the case of secondary materials or energy recovered from secondary fuels.

The product stage includes:

Information modules	Description	Explanation
A1	Raw material extraction and processing, processing of secondary material input (e.g. recycling processes)	Product stage: including provision of all materials, products and energy, as well as waste processing up to the end-of waste state or disposal of final residues during the product stage. Module A1, A2 and A3 may be declared as one aggregated module A1-3.
A2	Transport to the manufacturer	
A3	Manufacturing	
A4	Transport to the building site	Construction process stage: including provision of all materials, products and energy, as well as waste processing up to the end-of- waste state or disposal of final residues during the construction process stage. These information modules also include all impacts and aspects related to any losses during this construction process stage (i.e. production, transport, and waste processing and disposal of the lost products and materials).
A5	Installation into the building	
B1	Use or application of the installed product	Use stage, related to the building fabric: including provision and transport of all materials, products and related energy and water use, as well as waste processing up to the end-of-waste state or disposal of final residues during this part of the use stage. These information modules also include all impacts and aspects related to the losses during this part of the use stage (i.e. production, transport, and waste processing and disposal of the lost products and materials).
B2	Maintenance	
B3	Repair	
B4	Replacement	
B5	Refurbishment	
B6	Operational energy use (HVAC)	Use stage related to the operation of the building: These information modules include provision and transport of all materials, products, as well as energy and water provisions, waste processing up to the end-of-waste state or disposal of final residues during this part of the use stage.
B7	Operational water use	
C1	De-construction, demolition	End-of-life stage: including provision and all transport, provision of all materials, products and related energy and water
C2	Transport to waste processing	
C3	Waste processing for reuse, recovery and/or recycling	
C4	Disposal	
D	Reuse, recovery and/or recycling potentials, expressed as net impacts and benefits	Benefits and loads beyond the system boundary

FIGURE 6.14: Information modules within any of the life cycle stages are communicated depending on the types of EPD.

FIGURE 6.15: Functional unit specifications.

TABLE 6.4: List of declared unit types.

Type	Example	Note
An item (piece) and an assemblage of items	1 brick or 1 window	dimensions shall be specified
Mass (kg)	1 kg of cement	
Length (m)	1 m of pipe or 1 m of a beam	dimensions shall be specified
Area (m ²)	1 m ² of wall elements or 1 m ² of roof elements	dimensions shall be specified
Volume (m ³)	1 m ³ of timber or 1 m ³ of ready-mixed concrete	

- A1 Extraction and processing of raw materials (e.g. mining processes) and biomass production and processing (e.g. agricultural or forestry operations)
- A1 Reuse of products or materials from a previous product system
- A1 Processing of secondary materials used as input for manufacturing the product, but not including those processes that are part of the waste processing in the previous product system
- A1 Generation of electricity, steam and heat from primary energy resources, also including their extraction, refining and transport
- A1 Energy recovery and other recovery processes from secondary fuels, but not including those processes that are part of waste processing in the previous product system
- A2 Transportation up to the factory gate and internal transport
- A3 Production of ancillary materials or pre-products
- A3 Manufacturing of products and co-products
- Manufacturing of packaging
- A1-A3 processing up to the end-of-waste state or disposal of final residues including any packaging not leaving the factory gate with the product

The guidelines for determining the end-of-waste state of this European standard apply regardless of the geographical coverage of a product process.

The system boundary with nature is characterised as the point at which material flows from natural systems to the technosphere (i.e. when material flows are triggered or affected by human technological activity) and emissions are emitted from the technosphere to nature. As a result, the studied system should include all technological processes that are required to provide the functional or declared unit of the product.

6.5.8 Construction stage

The construction process stage includes the optional information modules for:

- A4 Transportation from the production gate to the construction site
- A4-A5 Storage of products, including the provision of heating, cooling, humidity control, etc.
- A4-A5 Wastage of construction products (additional production processes to compensate for the loss of wastage of products)
- A4-A5 Waste processing of the waste from product packaging and product wastage during the construction processes up to the end-of-waste state or disposal of final residues
- A5 Installation of the product into the building including manufacture and transportation of ancillary materials and any energy or water required for installation or operation of the construction site. It also includes on-site operations to the product

TABLE 6.5: Parameters describing resource use. Adapted from (EN 15804+A2, 2019).

Nr.	Parameter	Unit (expressed per fU or per declared unit)
1	Use of renewable primary energy excluding renewable primary energy resources used as raw materials	MJ, net calorific value
2	Use of renewable primary energy resources used as raw materials	MJ, net calorific value
3	Total use of renewable primary energy resources (primary energy and primary energy resources used as raw materials)	MJ, net calorific value
4	Use of non-renewable primary energy excluding non-renewable primary energy resources used as raw materials	MJ, net calorific value
5	Use of non-renewable primary energy resources used as raw materials	MJ, net calorific value
6	Total use of non-renewable primary energy resources (primary energy and primary energy resources used as raw materials)	MJ, net calorific value
7	Use of secondary material	kg
8	Use of renewable secondary fuels	MJ, net calorific value
9	Use of non-renewable secondary fuels	MJ, net calorific value
10	Net use of fresh water	m ³

6.5.9 Indicators describing resource use in EPD

Table 6.5 presents indicators describing resource use which shall be included in each module declared in the EPD.

The first six described parameters in Table 6.5 can be summarised as in Figure 6.16.

6.6 LCA Data Set Types

Data categories and data set types describe the origin or data basis and representativeness (product-specific, averaged, etc.) of the data.

The **Ökobaumat**¹⁰ distinguishes between the data categories A to C and a total of 5 dataset types. The **Ökobaumat** distinguishes between the latter with regards to the representativeness of the data:

1. **Specific dataset:** Manufacturer (company) specific dataset for a particular product

¹⁰The Ökobaumat platform is provided as a standardised database for ecological evaluations of buildings by the German Federal Ministry of the Interior, Building and Community.

FIGURE 6.16: First six parameters according to Table 6.5 describing resource use summarised to get a better understanding.

2. **Average dataset:** Average data sets of industrial associations, multiple companies or multiple factories (that is, based on industrial production data of companies)
3. **Representative dataset:** Data representative of a country/region (e.g. average DE)
4. **Template dataset:** Non-specific data sets for specific products created on the basis of a 'sample EPD'
5. **Generic dataset:** Generic data according to (EN 15804+A2, 2019) as well as other data not modeled on the basis of industrial data (for example, based on literature, expert knowledge, etc.)

The categories have been depicted in Figure 6.17.

6.6.1 Category A: EPD with programme operation

Category A data is life cycle assessment data according to (EN 15804+A2, 2019) from environmental product declarations (EPDs). The programme guidelines and product category rules (PCR) must be publicly available and prepared according to (EN 15804+A2, 2019) and EN ISO 14025.

6.6.2 Category B: Verified EPDs and LCA data

Category B data according to (EN 15804+A2, 2019) is not produced as part of an EPD program in accordance with EN ISO 14025 (Category B1) or published as part of an EPD (Category B2). However, like the category A data, it has been externally verified or subjected to a critical review. The inclusion of category B data requires coordination with the Ökobaudat user group. Here, the respective requirements for the inclusion of the data in the Ökobaudat are determined as needed, depending on the origin of the data, among other things. In principle, proof of conformity with (EN 15804+A2, 2019) for the respective data sets must be provided separately by means of an external verification (category B1) or critical review (category B2) on the part of the applicant or supplier of LCA data. An 'external audit' is required as a critical audit, which is to be carried out analogously to a verification in accordance with EN ISO 14025.

Group	Data category	Description	Data basis	Conformity check	Dataset type (sub-type)
Construction product datasets	A	Construction product with program operation	Manufacturer/Factory location	Independent external verification via program operation	Specific dataset
			Association/Country		Average dataset
					Template dataset
	B1	Construction product without program operation	Manufacturer/Factory location	Independent external verification not via program operation	Specific dataset
			Association/Country		Average dataset
					Template dataset
B2	Construction product data set (non EPD)	Manufacturer/Factory location Representative data for country/region	Independent external critical review	Specific dataset Representative dataset	
Construction product datasets	C	Construction product data set (non EPD)	Replacement data for country/region	None	Generic dataset
Other life cycle data		Transportation process			
		Usage stage			
		General end-of-life process			
		Energy supply			

FIGURE 6.17: Data categories and datasets according to Ökobaumat.

6.6.3 Category C: Generic data sets

Category C data is produced following (EN 15804+A2, 2019), but is not subject to external verification by an independent third party. Category C data includes substitute data provided by Ökobaumat for product categories for which no Category A or Category B data is available ('generic data'). This LCA data is provided with safety margins of 10% to 30% in the course of data generation. Generic data sets are commissioned by BBSR as required and are produced according to uniform, consistent procedures audited by independent third parties. They comply with the requirements for the modelling and calculation of LCA data formulated in the principles. Other LCA data that is not compliant with (EN 15804+A2, 2019) (note: these can also be verified EPDs according to EN ISO 14025) is generally not included in Ökobaumat.

In Ökobaumat, the indicator values for the production phase (modules A1 to A3) of the generic data sets are given a safety margin. These safety margins are intended to conservatively estimate the environmental impacts under worst-case assumptions and thus compensate for uncertainties in the data quality. For the determination of the certainty margins, the data sets are classified in three levels with respect to completeness of modelling and (technological, temporal and geographic) representativeness. Depending on the completeness and representativeness of the datasets, safety margins of 10%, 20% or 30% are assigned to the datasets. Data sets that do not meet the requirements of level 3 in terms of completeness and representativeness cannot be included in Ökobaumat or must be improved.

Chapter 7

Application of Dynamo for Integrating LCA in BIM

7.1 Introduction

In [chapter 6](#) different approaches to the integration of LCA in BIM were discussed. This chapter now presents the application of Dynamo (see [section 7.3](#)). This method is a dynamic BIM integrated method that this study has opted for. For the purpose of this study a case study, has been predetermined. This chapter first introduces the case study in [section 7.2](#). It then follows up with the presentation of the application of Dynamo in [section 7.4](#). At the end, in [section 7.5](#), the results of the calculated embodied energy for one element of the case study will be discussed.

7.2 Case Study: Main Gate East (MGE)

Eyemaxx Tower Offenbach UG is planning the construction of a new high-rise building on the Hafeninsel site in Offenbach¹. The architects in charge of the construction project are Meixner Schlüter Wendt Planungs GmbH. The planned new building consists of a multiple-bent building structure and is orientated with its long side in a southeast-northwest direction along the river. This results in the majority of the façade having a northeast and southwest orientation. The dimensions of the planned new building in the southeast-northwest direction are about 60 m. The length in the northeast-southwest direction is about 15 m. The building is used as an office building with a high-quality catering unit on the first floor. A special use unit is located on the top floor with access to a roof terrace (see [Figure 7.1](#)).

The building is to be given a horizontally structured façade that supports the sculptural effect and makes the bending edges visible. The façade is planned as a storey-high unitised façade with fixed glazing in a 2.7 m grid. Each façade element has a minimised opening panel for comfort ventilation, so that this is provided in every second extension grid, even in the case of small-scale timbering. The element façade consists of thermally separated aluminum profiles, so that the entire house has a continuous insulation level. The façade is designed in accordance with the required sound insulation requirements.

The total area of the unitised façade is approximately 6420 m² for standard floors above the ground floor. The ground floor façade is a steel transom-mullion façade that has an area of about 643 m².

¹Located 15 km far away in the east side of Frankfurt am Main.

FIGURE 7.1: Rendering model of the project. Produced by the architects.

7.2.1 Façade typing

The appearance of the high-rise façade is derived from a few different basic modules, which form the building envelope across two levels. The rear glass level, which together with the opaque panels is perceived as a dark surface, also forms the thermal and vapour-tight envelope. A layer of horizontal strips suspended from the glass, which with their light appearance form a strong contrast to the rear layer, provide additional external sun protection.

The façade system is based on an unitised structure with 2.70 m façade elements and a development grid of 1.35 m. In order to offer maximum flexibility in the room layout, there is a ventilation flap for comfort ventilation in every second extension grid. On each floor there is at least one horizontal band at parapet height. In addition, there is an additional 'intel ribbon' on approximately half of the floors, which not only provides more passive shading but also prevents the floors from being strictly readable and gives the façade the appearance of a two-dimensional volume. In this way, a significant part of the façade can be covered with two typical façade modules, each of which is offset from one floor to the next, thus significantly shaping the façade (see [Figure 7.2](#) and [Figure 7.3](#)).

The façade typing was carried out in the course of the existing planning, together with the architects. The basis for the typification is the use and the design of the particular façade. This can be summarised as in [Table 7.1](#).

7.2.2 BIM model

The exploded view of the BIM model of the MGE project can be found in [Figure 7.4](#) and [Figure 7.5](#). For the unitised façade on the ground floor, the following components are designed.

A horizontal ribbon belt at ceiling line height will cover the external sun protection casket. This will be executed in single storey steps and is cable guided. The main

FIGURE 7.2: Main Gate East front view above the ground floor.

FIGURE 7.3: Main Gate East front view ground floor.

TABLE 7.1: Façade typing of the MGE project developed in a collaboration with architects.

Façade type	Structure	Location
1.0	Unitised façade	Standard floor, 2–17. upper floor
2.0	Unitised façade	Special use, 17 th floor
3.0	Unitised façade	Office, event and catering, ground floor plus 1 st floor
4.0	Transom mullion façade	Lobby and catering, ground floor
4.1	Transom mullion façade	Windbreak lobby and restaurant
5.0	Cold façade	Roof and terrace, 17 th floor
5.1	Windshield	Terrace, 17 th floor
5.2	Transom mullion façade	Terrace, 17 th floor
5.3	Sheet metal façade, ventilated	Shell cladding, 17 & 18 th floor
5.4	Sandwich panels	Technical housing, 18 th floor
6.0	Thermal insulation composite system	Shell walls, plastered, 18 th floor
7.0	Thermal insulation composite system	Plinth façade

window profile on the ground floor is a steel profile with an aluminium cap structure. This profile will be the house for 3-fold insulating glazing. The glazing has a 2-storey height and is vertically continuous at the ground floor (see [Figure 7.4](#)).

[Figure 7.5](#) depicts other parts of the unitised façade above the ground floor for the MGE project. It consists of following central parts:

- Guide rail
- Sun protection case
- Bracket plate
- Insulation panels with openings
- Edged sheet metal with integrated bulkheads
- Batten for horizontal lamellas each offset in height

The given BIM model for this study is an excerpt that will be repeated for the whole geometry of the tower. One of the elements of the BIM model is selected for programming with Dynamo. Every single element in the Revit model, like instances and types, has an ID. It is a way for the Revit database to be able to keep elements organised, find what it needs to find, and act as an all-inclusive database. This element is a glass pane with 'element ID' = '617067'. The volume of this element will be multiplied with 'energy use indicators' of EPD for stages A1-A3 to calculate the initial embodied energy. To be able to verify the calculated volumes in Dynamo, this value has been extracted from the model in Revit simultaneously. It can be achieved by exploring the properties panel of the element. The volume is 0.130 m³ (see [Figure 7.6](#)).

FIGURE 7.4: Exploded view of the Main Gate East project at the ground floor.

FIGURE 7.5: Exploded view of MGE, other stories.

FIGURE 7.6: Selected element with element ID=617060 for Dynamo calculation. The volume can be seen that is 0.130 m³.

7.3 What is Dynamo?

Dynamo, the application, is a software that can be downloaded and run in either stand-alone ‘Sandbox’ mode or as a plug-in for other software like Revit or Maya. It is described as:

“A visual programming tool that aims to be accessible to both non-programmers and programmers alike. It gives users the ability to visually script behaviour, define custom pieces of logic, and script using various textual programming languages.²”

Once the application is installed, Dynamo will enable us to work within a Visual Programming process wherein we connect elements to define the relationships and the sequences of actions that compose custom algorithms. We can use our algorithms for a wide array of applications—from processing data to generating geometry—all in real time and without writing one bit of code (see [Figure 7.7](#)).

7.4 Concept and methodology

In Revit, it is possible to create the BIM model containing all the information needed for each object, thus creating an object-based data BIM model. There are many ways to create a parametric tool to calculate LCA results and several have already been developed (Hollberg and Ruth, 2016). One way to achieve this is by using visual programming tools like Dynamo. To calculate the results via parametric tools, the input information from the BIM model must be obtained. So, the data included in the BIM model should be complete and responsibly inserted into the object. All the information that is going to be used as input should come from a single BIM model (Hollberg and Ruth, 2016).

In this thesis, the required information for LCA calculation (geometrical and semantic) is extracted from the BIM model via Revit software. The ‘energy use indicators (embodied energy indicators part of the LCA parameters)’ in EPDs is taken from a collected database in Excel format. Dynamo is used to create the dynamic link between the model and the databank. The created scripts in Dynamo can be run from Dynamo (Dynamo Player³) and directly visualise the results in the Dynamo Player and write them into an Excel file.

Creating a dynamic tool with a direct result approach over the BIM model is the most beneficial way to impact the decision-making process during the design of a building. The method to achieve that was by creating a link between the BIM model and the LCA database (in this case the collected database in Excel format) by using Dynamo scripts. This integration was achieved through an approach that is based on element ID mapping which can be seen in [Figure 7.8](#).

The parametric tool which was created in Dynamo runs the connection between the model and the database, simultaneously reads information from the model and the databank (geometrical and environmental) and uses this information to run the LCA calculations and produce the results (see [Figure 7.9](#)). These results (initial embodied energy indicators) will be exported into an Excel file. After that, the results

²Autodesk website.

³See [subsection 7.4.5](#).

(A)

(B)

FIGURE 7.7: 7.7a: Dynamo a visual programming plug-in in BIM Revit. By using Dynamo Player (the logo on the right side of Revit’s logo) interface the scripts can be run in the background. Then the inputs and outputs will be asked using the interaction face of Dynamo Player. 7.7b: The environment of Dynamo.

FIGURE 7.8: Dynamo script concept.

will be imported automatically to the model and appear in front of the created 'shared parameters'.

In [subsection 7.4.1](#) the produced Excel file will be presented. Then in [subsection 7.4.2](#) to [subsection 7.4.4](#) the Dynamo scripts will be comprehensively discussed.

7.4.1 Preparing an LCA Excel database

For the purpose of this study, the LCA databases presented in [section 6.3](#) were not utilised. Instead a special Excel file was created. The Excel file consisted of four sheets. The first sheet named 'EPDs' is where all the needed information from the EPDs was filled in. The EPDs of various manufacturers for opening elements (door, window), glass, curtain wall and insulation were included. The number of manufacturers who have published EPDs is limited. The first column of the first sheet contained a unique 'LCA ID' number that differentiated each product from the others. This ID number could be utilised to distinguish the calculated LCA values in Revit for different products. The first sheet of the Excel can also be developed and other EPDs can be added on later (see [Figure 7.10](#)).

The second sheet named 'LCA parameters' presented the embodied energy indicators, their descriptions and three other parameters which will be imported to Revit using Dynamo as 'shared parameters'. Shared parameters are definitions of parameters that you can add to families or projects. Shared parameter definitions are stored in a file independent of any family file or Revit project; this allows you to access the file from different families or projects. The shared parameter is a definition of a container for information that can be used in multiple families or projects. The information defined in one family or project using the shared parameter is not automatically applied to another family or project using the same shared parameter. In

FIGURE 7.9: Revit model link with the Dynamo script.

order for information in a parameter to be used in a tag, it must be a shared parameter. Shared parameters are also useful when you want to create a schedule that displays various family categories; without a shared parameter, you cannot do this. If you create a shared parameter and add it to the desired family categories, you can then create a schedule with these categories⁴.

The 'LCA parameters' sheet can also be extended in the future to other LCA indicators such as GWP⁵.

The third sheet named 'LCA results' is where Dynamo exported the calculated results (see Figure 7.11). And later on Dynamo will read the results from this sheet to write them back in Revit.

The last sheet of this Excel named 'ModelData' is where Dynamo exports all the elements. Each element of a model as mentioned before has a unique ID. Here in this sheet, the given names for an element in accordance with the element ID will be stored.

This Excel file serves as the solo connector that makes a bridge between the LCA calculation and the BIM model.

7.4.2 Dynamo script 1

The element ID is unique to its element so is a helpful way to be 100% sure that the right element will be selected. This script is dedicated to the purpose of extracting all the elements of the model. Here, all elements and their names will be sorted out and exported to the Excel table (see Figure 7.12).

7.4.3 Dynamo script 2

In step one of this script the energy use indicators which are defined in subsection 6.5.9 are extracted from the Excel file. Here it is important which EPD will be applied for the calculation. For instance, if the glazing pane modelled in BIM is 'float glass'

⁴Autodesk website.

⁵Global Warming Potential.

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K	L	M	N	O	P	Q	R
	Name	Category	Manufacturer	Compliance	Type	Valid to	Mod	PERE	PERM	PERT	PENRE	PENRM	PENRT	SM	RSF	NRSF	FW
1	Vetrolam 30 VFI0	Glass	Vetrotec Saint-Gobain	ISO 14025/EN 15804:19	generic	Dec 24 AI-A3		122	126	1140	0	1140	0	287	0	0	0,421
2	Vetrolam 60 VFI2	Glass	Vetrotec Saint-Gobain	ISO 14025/EN 15804:19	generic	Dec 24 AI-A3		126	126	1220	0	1220	0	344	0	0	0,439
3	Vetrolam 25 30	Glass	Vetrotec Saint-Gobain	ISO 14025/EN 15804:19	generic	Dec 24 AI-A3		88,2	745	745	0	745	0	172	0	0	0,271
4	Flachglas	Glass	Flachglas Wernberg GmbH	ISO 14025/EN 15804:12	specific/generic	Dec 22 AI-A3		0,931	45,47	0	45,47	0	45,47	0,11	0	0	0,0785
5	Einscheibensicherheitsglas	Glass	Flachglas Wernberg GmbH	ISO 14025/EN 15804:12	specific/generic	Dec 22 AI-A3		7,3	64,92	0	64,92	0	64,92	0,103	0	0	0,172
6	Verbandsicherheitsglas	Glass	Flachglas Wernberg GmbH	ISO 14025/EN 15804:12	specific/generic	Dec 22 AI-A3		29,38	145,3	0	145,3	0	145,3	0,122	0	0	0,3508
7	Mehrscheibensicherheitsglas 2 fäch	Glass	Scheuten Glas Nederland Glas Tech Unit	ISO 14025/EN 15804:12	specific/generic	Dec 22 AI-A3		0,6	44,8	0	44,8	0	44,8	0,11	0	0	0,0553
8	Mehrscheibensicherheitsglas 3 fäch	Glass	Scheuten Glas Nederland Glas Tech Unit	ISO 14025/EN 15804:12	specific/generic	Dec 22 AI-A3		7,39	63,59	0	63,59	0	63,59	0,12	0	0	0,0517
9	Verbandsicherheitsglas	Glass	Scheuten Glas Nederland Glas Tech Unit	ISO 14025/EN 15804:12	specific/generic	Dec 22 AI-A3		30,73	139,77	0	139,77	0	139,77	0,14	0	0	0,0517
10	Mehrscheibensicherheitsglas 2 fäch	Glass	Scheuten Glas Nederland Glas Tech Unit	ISO 14025/EN 15804:12	specific/generic	Dec 22 AI-A3		29,54	498,39	0	498,39	0	498,39	0,88	0	0	0,11
11	Mehrscheibensicherheitsglas 3 fäch	Glass	Scheuten Glas Nederland Glas Tech Unit	ISO 14025/EN 15804:12	specific/generic	Dec 22 AI-A3		42,56	749,58	0	749,58	0	749,58	1,32	0	0	0,17
12	Flachglas	Glass	Anahi India Glass Ltd.	ISO 14025/EN 15804:12	specific	Oct 23 AI-A3		14,4	472	0	472	0	472	12,6	0	0	0,082
13	Centrafam 120 IGL: CFI20-5 (5/8/4/4/8/5)/16 Argon/4 Toughened	Glass	Vetrotec Saint-Gobain	ISO 14025/EN 15804:19	generic	Dec 24 AI-A3		374	3420	0	3420	0	3420	10,9	0	0	1,07
14	Centrafam 120 IGL: CFI20-5 (5/8/4/4/8/5)/16 Argon/4,4,2 Stadip	Glass	Vetrotec Saint-Gobain	ISO 14025/EN 15804:19	generic	Dec 24 AI-A3		384	3630	0	3630	0	3630	11,7	0	0	1,1
15	Centrafam 120 IGL: CFI20-5 (5/8/4/4/8/5)/12 Argon/6 Toughened	Glass	Vetrotec Saint-Gobain	ISO 14025/EN 15804:19	generic	Dec 24 AI-A3		375	3490	0	3490	0	3490	11,5	0	0	1,08
16	Centrafam 120 IGL: CFI20-5 (5/8/4/4/8/5)/16 Argon/6 Amesal	Glass	Vetrotec Saint-Gobain	ISO 14025/EN 15804:19	generic	Dec 24 AI-A3		359	3400	0	3400	0	3400	11,3	0	0	1,03
17	Centrafam 120 IGL: CFI20-5 (5/8/4/4/8/5)/12 Argon/6 7	Glass	Vetrotec Saint-Gobain	ISO 14025/EN 15804:19	generic	Dec 24 AI-A3		439	3950	0	3950	0	3950	13,2	0	0	1,26
18	Centrafam 120 IGL: CFI20-5 (5/8/4/4/8/5)/14 Argon/6 Toughened/14 Argon/6 7	Glass	Vetrotec Saint-Gobain	ISO 14025/EN 15804:19	generic	Dec 24 AI-A3		443	3960	0	3960	0	3960	13,2	0	0	1,27
19	Pyranova	Glass	Schott Technical Glass Solutions GmbH	ISO 14025/EN 15804:12	specific	Apr 21 AI-A3		415	1820	0	1820	0	1820	0	0	0	0,496
20	Pyranova	Glass	Schott Technical Glass Solutions GmbH	ISO 14025/EN 15804:12	specific	Apr 21 A5		0,107	1,1	0	1,1	0	1,1	0	0	0	0,0116
21	Pyrowis 30 DGL: PY6-12-4	Glass	Vetrotec Saint-Gobain	ISO 14025/EN 15804:19	generic	Dec 24 AI-A3		118	110	0	110	0	110	2,72	0	0	0,366
22	Pyrowis 30 DGL: PY6-12-4	Glass	Vetrotec Saint-Gobain	ISO 14025/EN 15804:19	generic	Dec 24 AI-A3		130	1110	0	1110	0	1110	2,87	0	0	0,434
23	Pyrowis 30 DGL: PY6-12-6t	Glass	Vetrotec Saint-Gobain	ISO 14025/EN 15804:19	generic	Dec 24 AI-A3		134	1190	0	1190	0	1190	3,44	0	0	0,481
24	Pyrowis 30 DGL: PY6-12-P76	Glass	Vetrotec Saint-Gobain	ISO 14025/EN 15804:19	generic	Dec 24 AI-A3		193	1590	0	1590	0	1590	3,44	0	0	0,589
25	Pyrowis 30 DGL: PY6-12-42 (laminated safety glass)	Glass	Vetrotec Saint-Gobain	ISO 14025/EN 15804:19	generic	Dec 24 AI-A3		147	1310	0	1310	0	1310	3,71	0	0	0,452
26	Pyrowis 30 DGL: PY6-14-4-14-4	Glass	Vetrotec Saint-Gobain	ISO 14025/EN 15804:19	generic	Dec 24 AI-A3		186	1600	0	1600	0	1600	4,59	0	0	0,64
27	Stahl-/Edelessiden	Curtain wall	Janssen AG	ISO 14025/EN 15804:12	specific/generic	Nov 17 AI-A3		208,49	1859,19	0,0000323	1859,19	0	1859,19	0,00014	0,000473	0,000177	262,38
28	Stahl-/Edelessiden	Curtain wall	Janssen AG	ISO 14025/EN 15804:12	specific/generic	Nov 17 A4		1,83	50,32	0	50,32	0	50,32	0,00017	0,00017	0,00017	0,18
29	Konstruktion der UNICLAS6 IFACADE	Curtain wall	Uniglas GmbH & Co.KG	ISO 14025/EN 15804:12	specific/generic	May 22 AI-A3		769	286	0	286	0	286	769	0	0	0,0928
30	Konstruktion der UNICLAS6 IFACADE	Curtain wall	Uniglas GmbH & Co.KG	ISO 14025/EN 15804:12	specific/generic	May 22 A4		0,07	0	0	0	0	0	1,4	0	0	0,00013
31	Stahl-/Edelessiden	Curtain wall	Janssen AG	ISO 14025/EN 15804:12	specific/generic	Nov 17 AI-A3		0	168	0	180	0	180	0	0,00157	0,000654	214
32	Stahl-/Edelessiden	Curtain wall	Janssen AG	ISO 14025/EN 15804:12	specific/generic	Nov 17 A4		0	0,65	0	39,7	0	39,7	0	0,000148	0,00154	-1,65
33	Passchhaus-Holz-Metallfenster der Baureihe dw-plus integral	Curtain wall	Wiegand Fensterbau	ISO 14025/EN 15804:12	specific/generic	Sep 17 AI-A5		399,01	0	0	1519,04	0	1519,04	0	0	0	476,4
34	Passchhaus-Holz-Metallfenster der Baureihe dw-plus integral	Window	Schuco International KG	ISO 14025/EN 15804:12	generic	Jul 22 AI-A3		611	3450	0	3450	287	3740	7,47	0	0	1,36

FIGURE 7.10: Excel firs sheet named 'EPDs'.

FIGURE 7.11: The Excel file has four sheets. The second sheet 7.11a: LCA parameters, the third sheet 7.11b: LCA results and the fourth sheet: 7.11c: ModelData.

FIGURE 7.13: Script 2: extracting the LCA values from the prepared Excel table.

FIGURE 7.14: Script 2: extracting the volume of an element.

FIGURE 7.15: Script 2: the volume or the area of each material will be multiplied with the selected EPD as LCA values.

FIGURE 7.16: Script 2: the calculated embodied energy indicators will be exported to the Excel file in the 'LCA results' sheet.

FIGURE 7.17: Script 2: creating shared parameters from the 'LCA parameters' sheet of the excel.

FIGURE 7.18: Exporting element name and ID. Input and output nodes of Dynamo can be managed through Dynamo Player.

for the visible scripts and a current view of the status of the script (see [Figure 7.18](#) to [Figure 7.20](#)).

7.5 Results

The volume of the selected glazing pane is 0.13 m^3 as aforementioned in [subsection 7.2.2](#). The applied EPD is from the 'Scheuten Glas Nederland Iso Glass Unit' company for 3-fold glazing. The energy use indicators of this product are indicated in [Table 7.2](#).

By multiplying the EPD values with the volume of the glazing, the initial embodied energy values (stages A1 to A3) are calculated and summarised in [Table 7.3](#).

The results are also visible in the third sheet of the discussed Excel file. The results are then imported to Revit (see [Figure 7.21](#)).

FIGURE 7.19: Calculation of embodied energy. Input and output nodes of Dynamo can be managed through Dynamo Player.

FIGURE 7.20: Writing back the results from Excel to the Revit. Input and output nodes of the Dynamo can be managed through Dynamo Player.

TABLE 7.2: Energy use indicators of the glass product from the company 'Scheuten Glas Nederland Iso Glass Unit'. The declared values are for 1 m³ and LCA A1 to A3 stages, before multiplying with the volume.

Energy use indicator	Declared value	Unit
PERE	42.56	MJ
PERM	0	MJ
PERT	42.56	MJ
PENRE	749.58	MJ
PENRM	15.44	MJ
PENRT	765.02	MJ
SM	1.32	kg
RSF	0	MJ
NRSF	0	MJ
FW	0.17	m ³

TABLE 7.3: The result of the calculated energy use indicators from EPD for the glass product of the company 'Scheuten Glas Nederland Iso Glass Unit'. After multiplying with the volume.

Energy use indicator	Calculated value	Unit
PERE	5.55	MJ
PERM	0	MJ
PERT	5.55	MJ
PENRE	97.76	MJ
PENRM	2.01	MJ
PENRT	99.78	MJ
SM	0.17	kg
RSF	0	MJ
NRSF	0	MJ
FW	0.02	m ³

FIGURE 7.21: Assigning initial embodied energy values into Revit.

Chapter 8

Conclusion

8.1 Introduction

Climate change is the most important issue of our time. It is fueled by the development and operation of buildings, which account for 36% of global energy consumption and 39% of CO₂ emissions connected to energy. To achieve the Paris Agreement's¹ aim of limiting global warming to 1.5°C, comprehensive actions within the construction sector are required.

In the EU, this issue stems mostly from there being a large stock of inefficient buildings (75%) as well as a low rate of repair (0.4–1.2%) and new construction (0.4–1.2%). The EU has pledged to become the first climate-neutral continent by 2050, thanks to the establishment of the EU Green Deal². This entails, among other things, a considerable improvement of building energy efficiency.

In Germany, the construction industry accounts for 35% of total energy consumption and 30% of CO₂ emissions. The majority of the building stock was constructed prior to the first Thermal Insulation Ordinance³ in 1977, which was the first rule governing the heating demand of structures. More than two-thirds of heating systems do not adhere to contemporary best practices.

The German government's climate protection programme aims to achieve a practically carbon-neutral building stock by 2050, with an interim goal of a 66-67% decrease in CO₂ emissions by 2030 compared to 1990 levels. To meet these climatic goals, net zero buildings have been introduced. Net zero buildings are becoming more common in the residential sector, the non-residential construction industry is still catching up.

A net zero-energy building⁴ is a residential or commercial building with significantly decreased energy demand as a result of efficiency improvements of the operational energy, allowing the balance of energy needs to be met using renewable technology. This means that, in the future, all the consumed energy in the construction industry will be indicated by embodied energy. Saying that, the importance of acknowledging the embodied energy for a building increases continuously. Not only for the façade but also for other parts of the building.

Recent technical terms such as 'zero-energy building', 'life cycle energy assessment', 'environmental product declaration' and 'initial embodied energy' could be

¹Source: www.unfccc.int.

²EU green deal website.

³In German: Wärmeschutzverordnung.

⁴ZEB.

confusing for civil engineers, especially façade engineers. This study managed to address the embodied energy topic, introducing its definition, characteristic and scope in [chapter 5. section 6.5](#) was dedicated to environmental product declaration in order to make these subjects more comprehensible. However, there remains a concern that dealing with these concepts inadequately could lead to unintentional environmental deception, if they are not understood comprehensively by the practitioners. This could ultimately lead to a ‘greenwashing’ or unintentional deception regarding environmental matters.

Consequently, this chapter will give a brief yet comprehensive insight into the topic of ‘greenwashing’ in [section 8.2](#). After that, [section 8.3](#) will discuss the results from [section 7.5](#). The last section of this chapter ([section 8.4](#)) will present some future research fields of study for the façade engineers.

8.2 Unintentional Deception (greenwashing)

According to green marketing literature, unintended deception is a significant part of the greenwash issue. Companies may feel compelled to do whatever possible to avoid unintended deception due to them valuing customer sovereignty, believing it is their social responsibility to contribute to systemic environmental change. An alternative to misleading ads has been suggested, and some producers have made it a selling point by calling it Full Product Transparency. Due to the use of EPDs, which have been on the market for more than two decades, Full Product Transparency is advocated as something new. EPDs are generally presented as objective, accurate, reliable, third-party validated facts which, above all, are transparent. But a central question remains within this study: Can EPDs help avoid unintended deception and provide transparency?

Deception can be both deliberate and unintentional, according to (Gardner, 1975)’s theoretical and *Terrachoice*’s realistic definitions. The likelihood of the customer being misled is a central feature of the first concept. According to some scholars, it has become clear that realistic examples of unintentional green deception show a lack of accountability in terms of relevance, comprehensiveness, data quality, third-party verified evidence, and clarification. According to some studies, significance is a critical element of avoiding unintended fraud, and it takes precedence over the amount of details disclosed (comprehensiveness). Too few details (vagueness) can deceive consumers just as much as too much detail or unbalanced information (irrelevance). Similarly, consistency is a crucial component of accountability (Lugt, 2011).

While EPDs are said to strive for openness and truthfulness, literary research indicates that the EPD format has significant drawbacks. First and foremost, the achievement of these goals is highly dependent on LCA methodology and the criteria outlined in the PCR. Certain EPDs, for example, may be viewed as too informative, thus making details less clear. A short description of the key results is also missing from EPDs. While the information appears to be balanced, its efficacy is determined by the intelligibility of this positive and negative information combination. Consumers are often unable to determine whether the provided information refers to a positive or negative environmental performance, according to (Christiansen, Wesnæs, and Bo P Weidema, 2006). Furthermore, due to the reliance on LCA, the data quality can be questioned, a concern that is well understood within the LCA field. Similarly,

the subjective existence of certain allocation and system boundary-setting approaches makes scientific legitimisation difficult. Consumers can be confused unwittingly if quantitative data is interpreted too literally, representing current environmental impacts (rather than past impacts), whereas it should be viewed as approximations rather than specific scores. Companies should be mindful of these pitfalls and the likelihood of unintended fraud, and prepare for them if they choose to avoid it (Lugt, 2011).

Certain structural requirements, on the other hand, are met. Market education (relevance), usability (data quality), and offering a comprehensive image are all advantages of EPDs. Consumer education is critical for preventing unintended deception and increasing environmental consciousness, all of which are necessary steps towards a more sustainable society. Furthermore, although the EPD's comprehensiveness is dependent on the PCR, the LCA is the most robust environmental assessment method for products available. However, there is room for growth in terms of user orientation (Lugt, 2011).

The virtue of accuracy appears to be a prerequisite, given the significant effort associated with operationalising accountability in general and the development of the EPD. Furthermore, considering that businesses still have other moral responsibilities, this virtue may help in determining if the costs associated with the production of the EPD are excessive or not. Moreover, this virtue appears to be critical for reducing the likelihood of unintended deception in the EPD format, as this would necessitate additional consumer education. Overall, it can be inferred that EPDs are not as straightforward as they are often portrayed to be, and that they may not be entirely effective in preventing unintended manipulation and providing transparency. Some producers' arguments that Full Product Transparency and EPDs offer real, reliable, and impartial information fall short of the results that EPDs may provide in terms of transparency, and may even be misleading. Since these producers claim to have years of experience with LCA studies and therefore are well aware of the methodological problems, it is possible that these misleading EPD claims are not unintentional (Lugt, 2011).

8.3 Discussion

This study commenced by introducing basic knowledge about the façade in [chapter 1](#). Then in [chapter 2](#) a scientific definition of sustainability was discussed. Next came [chapter 3](#) which presented 'sustainable development' and its characteristics. In order to find a pragmatic way to conceptualise 'sustainability' this study dedicated [chapter 4](#) to life cycle assessment one of the most practiced tools to assess the sustainability of construction products and ultimately one of the main pillars of the 'environmental product declaration'. [Chapter 5](#) focused on the scientific approaches to calculate the embodied energy for different building materials. This chapter was also successful in acquainting the readers with the definitions of 'embodied energy', 'initial embodied energy', 'system boundaries' and so on. This study made it clear that there is no single standard or guideline within the construction industry that can be applied to calculate initial embodied energy. This need can be fulfilled later in the future by the authorities. [Chapter 6](#) started by interrogating how the calculation of initial embodied energy be integrated into the conventional methods of façade planning by means of different softwares and plug-ins. This chapter then delved into the topic of environmental

product declarations through summarising the standard (EN 15804+A2, 2019). By explaining the structure of an EPD, it became clear how initial embodied energy is defined in an EPD, namely embedded in the A1 to A3 stages of LCA reported calculation. Before jumping to any conclusion, [chapter 7](#) applied the integration of the calculation of initial embodied energy into Revit software through using Dynamo. At this point, the selected approach of this study (which is to use Dynamo for calculating initial embodied energy in Revit) is discussed comprehensively. The advantages and disadvantages of this method will be set out in [subsection 8.3.1](#).

8.3.1 Working with Dynamo

Dynamo is an open source visual programming tool embedded in Revit. This makes it one of the most powerful tools to simplify sophisticated models of the façades of skyscrapers in Revit. Using Dynamo to integrate the calculation of embodied energy does not require the utilisation of other softwares such as Grasshopper or Rhino. Any model component in Revit can be tracked by using Dynamo. This makes it very easy to assign EPD values from different manufacturers. The applied approach in the Dynamo script is based on selecting one element manually in Revit using the 'select model' node in Dynamo. There are other approaches alongside this, such as 'material mapping'. The 'material mapping' approach identifies all the assigned materials in Revit and calculates the initial embodied energy for the total mass of a specific material. One of the suggestions that this study emphasises with regards to the application of the 'material mapping' approach, is to consider the embodied energy for the façade model from the early planning stages. By doing that, the façade of a building will be modelled and the materials will be assigned to each component of the model, in accordance with EPDs. This means that, the assigning of materials in Revit would not be due the pure definition of material such as steel, aluminium, insulation or glass. Instead, it identifies how an EPD will be declared for a façade system that contains aluminium, insulation and glazing at the same time. For this specific formation, a material will then be defined and assigned in Revit. A similar approach can be used in other façade design planning softwares. Wicono and Schüco, for example, use resources that provide an integrated LCA of a façade product. These software solutions have an embedded mass calculation that is linked to ecological data. As a result, exporting the entire profile is relatively easy (Hildebrand, 2014).

The amount of total use of renewable primary energy resources (primary energy and primary energy resources used as raw materials)⁵ for a 0.13 m³ glazing pane product of the company 'Scheuten Glas Nederland Iso Glass Unit' is 5.55 MJ = 154 kW h. The amount of total use of non-renewable primary energy resources (primary energy and primary energy resources used as raw materials) is 99.78 MJ = 2772 kW h. This amount of total use of non-renewable primary energy is almost comparable to the amount of annual electricity usage of a conventional building with two occupants.

8.3.2 Literature reviews

If the entire life cycle energy use of buildings is optimised, the construction sector, particularly structures that currently consume a substantial amount of energy, may make a major difference. Both the operating and embodied energy use in a building's life cycle should be decreased for this goal. The focus of energy research, on the other hand, has remained primarily on the optimisation of operating energy. This

⁵PERT.

was due to a number of factors. Existing embodied energy data is either unavailable or inconclusive, incomplete, and non-representative. To make matters worse, there has been no attempt to define the term ‘embodied energy.’ There is very little information available on how to compute embodied energy in a consistent manner. By constantly establishing the system limits and employing quality data, there are no rules that can streamline the embodied energy computation (Manish Kumar, 2013).

If embodied energy can be estimated from cost data, a widely used information tool such as Computer-Aided Design (CAD) or Building Information Model (BIM) can be used to determine the overall embodied energy of a building’s façade. This will not only make the entire embodied energy calculation procedure easier, but it will also aid in its broad use in the process of whole-building energy accounting.

(Manish Kumar, 2013) has improved the current form of the input-output-based hybrid analysis in three ways. As already discussed in [chapter 5](#), first, the input-output model was updated using actual energy use data in energy units. The energy embodied in human and capital inputs was quantified and contributed to the input-output model in the second step. Third, using the Benchmark Input-Output data from 2002, the method of sector disaggregation was achieved. Additionally, the PEF⁶ for each energy source was estimated in detail in the study by (Manish Kumar, 2013). Also presented is a mechanism for converting energy intensities per unit of monetary output to embodied energy per unit of mass without the use of variable material and energy prices. The revelation that the energy embodied in a product may be estimated in a thorough and standardised manner with results particular to the product under consideration was one of the most significant values of the research by (Manish Kumar, 2013). The positive and substantial link between a material’s price and its embodied energy was one of the study’s biggest discoveries. It was also interesting that when the human and capital inputs were included, the link became stronger.

Primary Energy and GWP do not necessarily show similarities and cannot be reduced to one indicator. Results often have the same tendency but need to be checked in detail. Both indicators should be displayed.

8.3.3 Optimisation of embodied energy

The forms of façades and their embodied energies are shown in [Figure 8.1](#). It is possible to recognise fuzzy circles. Curtain walls with just one layer perform well in terms of environmental efficiency, solid punctured wall systems are in the centre, and twin façades have the most embodied energy. This condensed overview highlights trends but does not rule out exceptions. It does, however, convey the effect of the second layer for curtain walls, which was previously mentioned. Punctured wall façades are heavier and come in a variety of colours and textures (Hildebrand, 2014).

Since their weather barrier is loosely linked, ventilated façades provide better recycling scenarios than warm façades with an EIFS⁷ (Hildebrand, 2014). The façade accounts for around a third of the environmental effects on average. Because of the various types of façade construction that are meant to be part of the

⁶Primary energy factor.

⁷Exterior Insulation Façade System.

FIGURE 8.1: Embodied energy and weight in façades. Façades within one typology shows similar results and can be grouped according to both indicators. Adapted from (Hildebrand, 2014).

office building, the indicator amounts vary. This number is influenced by the design method and the amount of façade surface area (Hildebrand, 2014).

The façade depicts both large percentages and the capacity for optimisation. The façade, it can be deduced, has the greatest optimisation potential. The interdependencies of façade forms, as well as their ecological effects, need to be explored further. It is necessary to specify how the ecological dimension is influenced by the characteristics, material choice, and construction process.

(Shreve, 2018) suggests different strategies which can be considered from the early design phase in order to reduce and optimise the consumed embodied energy for façade structures. Table 8.1 also identifies the subcategories and associated strategy from (Lupíšek et al., 2015); these subcategories will represent those strategies.

8.4 Future Research

This research study has shown that there is unlimited potential for the integration of LCA in the Revit model of a building envelope. There exists the potential to connect recent planning and designing tools, such as BIM Revit, with the calculation of the environmental impacts of a façade. As has been discussed, to achieve a circular and environmental friendly façade structure, the consideration of LCA for the façade should be applied in the early designing phases. This allows façade engineers to be able to find the optimal façade design in accordance with the amount of embodied energy.

TABLE 8.1: Design strategies for the reduction of embodied energy.
Reproduced from (Shreve, 2018).

Strategy	Sub-strategy
Reduction of required building materials	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Optimisation of layout plan •Optimisation of structural system •Low-maintenance design •Flexible and adaptable design •Component's service life optimisation
Substitution of traditional materials	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Reuse of building parts and elements •Utilisation of recycled materials •Substitution for bio-based and raw materials •Use of innovative materials with lower environmental impacts •Design for deconstruction •Use of recyclable materials

There is always scope for future research. This study has come across some of these fields that can be further researched based on this thesis. In [Figure 8.2](#), three phases for future research have been identified and summarised.

8.4.1 Phase one

To take advantage of the designed Dynamo script, in future BIM models the initial embodied energy can be considered from the early stages of designing. In addition, based on diverse specifications for each project model, the Dynamo script can be modified. If a model of a project is sophisticated, selecting every element manually would probably not be the optimal approach. Therefore, based on suggestions from façade BIM users, modifications could be considered.

8.4.2 Phase two

As mentioned previously in [chapter 5](#), there are currently no benchmarks for the embodied energy values of a façade. This means that the calculated embodied energy for a façade cannot be compared with specific values in order to achieve an evaluation. Having embodied energy numbers is certainly the first step but without any benchmarking, no decisions can be made. This study suggests a comprehensive evaluation of embodied energy values using EPDs for different façade types. After the evaluation and data processing, benchmarks could be identified. These benchmarks would work as a spectrum to categorise different façades. After categorising, decisions can be made as to which type of façade has the highest embodied energy. The following questions should be considered.

1. What are the properties of embodied energy and the potential for global warming in façades?
2. What are the characteristics of embodied energy in the building substance? How is embodied energy distributed over the building elements for office buildings?

FIGURE 8.2: Future study fields to integrate embodied energy in façade engineering.

3. Is the environmental impact determined by the form of the façade?
4. What is an adequate method to rate the ecological impact of the façades?
5. What parameters are suitable for the ecological evaluation of façades? How can the parameters be communicated?
6. What are the characteristics of embodied energy in façades?
7. Does the type of façade define the environmental impact?

8.4.3 Phase three

The final step should be to focus on optimising the design of a façade in accordance with its embodied energy. Here it is very important to consider other involved parameters, especially the circularity. Finding a façade with the lowest embodied energy is not always environmentally neutral. Considering an analysis of all life cycles of a façade is vital to be able to achieve a sustainable optimisation of embodied energy for a façade. The following questions should be considered in future research studies:

1. How can embodied energy in façades be optimised?
2. How can the information about the embodied energy in the building context affect the design process?
3. How can knowledge about embodied energy be translated into strategies for the design process?
4. How can the amount of embodied energy in a building's façade be reduced?
5. Which façade elements have the greatest potential to improve the environmental impact?

Appendix A

Data references from literatures

FIGURE A.1: Transportation energy as percentage of total materials' embodied energy. Produced by (Manish Kumar, 2013).

FIGURE A.2: Embodied energy fraction in the total REE of referred residential buildings. Produced by (Manish Kumar, 2013).

FIGURE A.3: Embodied energy fraction in the total REE of referred commercial buildings. Produced by (Manish Kumar, 2013).

Study	% of EE	Study	% of EE	Study	% of EE
Malin, 1993	15.8	Itard, 2007	28.0	Pullen, 2000a	23.6
Malin, 1993	12.2	Citherlet & Defaux, 2007	18.6	Pullen, 2000a	31.9
Malin, 1993	26.3	Citherlet & Defaux, 2007	29.7	Pullen, 2000a	36.0
Malin, 1993	20.7	Citherlet & Defaux, 2007	51.5	Pullen, 2000a	29.6
Blanchard & Reppe, 1998	10.2	Citherlet & Defaux, 2007	14.8	Pullen, 2000a	36.8
Blanchard & Reppe, 1998	25.8	Citherlet & Defaux, 2007	20.8	Pullen, 2000a	25.3
Shaw et al., 1998	4.7	Citherlet & Defaux, 2007	42.0	Fay et al., 2000	100.0
Keoleian et al., 2001	9.6	Karlsson & Moshfegh, 2007	16.6	Fay et al., 2000	38.8
Keoleian et al., 2001	26.5	Karlsson & Moshfegh, 2007	38.5	Fay et al., 2000	30.9
Olgvy & Herdt, 2004	36.4	Thormark, 2007	36.5	Fay et al., 2000	27.6
Olgvy & Herdt, 2004	23.2	Thormark, 2007	33.7	Fay et al., 2000	25.2
Lippke et al., 2004	8.6	Thormark, 2007	37.0	Fay et al., 2000	100.0
Lippke et al., 2004	9.8	Sobotka & Rolak, 2009	1.6	Fay et al., 2000	42.6
Lippke et al., 2004	10.1	Bribian et al., 2009	18.1	Fay et al., 2000	33.9
Lippke et al., 2004	11.2	Blengini, 2009	7.1	Fay et al., 2000	30.2
Winistorfer et al., 2005	10.8	Anastascos et al., 2009	1.8	Fay et al., 2000	27.5

(A)

Almeida et al., 2005	47.8	Pullen, 2000a	32.9	Langston & Langston, 2007	25.4
Thormark, 2006	39.8	Pullen, 2000a	25.2	Langston & Langston, 2007	20.4
Thormark, 2006	30.4	Pullen, 2000a	34.1	Langston & Langston, 2007	21.3
Thormark, 2006	28.7	Pullen, 2000a	25.5	Langston & Langston, 2007	15.7
Thormark, 2006	41.6	Pullen, 2000a	21.5	Perkins et al., 2009	32.9
Thormark, 2006	31.3	Pullen, 2000a	39.0	Perkins et al., 2009	38.2
Thormark, 2006	28.9	Pullen, 2000a	32.9	Perkins et al., 2009	44.5
Thormark, 2006	36.5	Pullen, 2000a	34.3	DINCEL, 2009	32.8
Thormark, 2006	25.1	Pullen, 2000a	26.7	DINCEL, 2009	56.4
Thormark, 2006	22.8	Pullen, 2000a	22.4		

(B)

FIGURE A.4: Description of referred case studies and percentage of embodied energy in the total LCE. Adapted from (Manish Kumar, 2013).

Winistorfer et al., 2005	10.5	Anastaseos et al., 2009	2.0	Vale et al., 2000	31.6
Winistorfer et al., 2005	9.4	Gustavsson & Joelsson, 2010	25.7	Vale et al., 2000	37.4
Baouendi et al., 2005	6.3	Gustavsson & Joelsson, 2010	10.3	Vale et al., 2000	69.2
Baouendi et al., 2005	7.2	Gustavsson & Joelsson, 2010	8.7	Fay et al., 2000b	43.3
Norman et al., 2006	14.5	Gustavsson & Joelsson, 2010	16.8	Fay et al., 2000b	76.3
Norman et al., 2006	12.9	Gustavsson & Joelsson, 2010	28.8	Newton et al., 2000	73.8
Haines et al., 2007	9.2	Gustavsson et al., 2010	9.9	Newton et al., 2000	69.6
Haines et al., 2007	11.5	Dodoo et al., 2010	1.1	Newton et al., 2000	49.7
Haines et al., 2007	15.1	Dodoo et al., 2010	1.9	Newton et al., 2000	70.2
Kim, 2008	6.8	Dodoo et al., 2010	2.4	Newton et al., 2000	62.2
Kim, 2008	5.2	Dodoo et al., 2010	2.6	Newton et al., 2000	54.7
Leckner & Zmeureanu, 2011	20.4	Dodoo et al., 2010	3.4	Newton et al., 2000	71.5
Leckner & Zmeureanu, 2011	36.8	Dodoo et al., 2010	3.7	Newton et al., 2000	62.5
Chulsukon et al., 2002	30.9	Dodoo et al., 2010	1.3	Newton et al., 2000	42.2
Chulsukon et al., 2002	30.3	Dodoo et al., 2010	2.2	Newton et al., 2000	70.7
Humphrey et al., 2004	44.4	Dodoo et al., 2010	3.0	Newton et al., 2000	59.3
Humphrey et al., 2004	62.0	Dodoo et al., 2010	3.0	Newton et al., 2000	51.6
Jeyasingh & Sam, 2004	41.5	Dodoo et al., 2010	3.9	Newton et al., 2000	45.2
Huberman & Pearlmutter, 2004	4.6	Dodoo et al., 2010	4.4	Newton et al., 2000	37.0
Huberman & Pearlmutter, 2004	26.2	Blengini & Di Carlo, 2010	18.3	Newton et al., 2000	29.4
Huberman & Pearlmutter, 2004	14.8	Blengini & Di Carlo, 2010	54.0	Newton et al., 2000	35.0
Huberman & Pearlmutter, 2004	55.5	Aste et al., 2010	14.1	Newton et al., 2000	28.6
Pearlmutter et al., 2007	81.5	Aste et al., 2010	18.8	Newton et al., 2000	25.0
Pearlmutter et al., 2007	79.4	Aste et al., 2010	46.8	Treloar et al., 2000b	38.0
Pearlmutter et al., 2007	90.9	Buchanan & Honey, 1994	38.3	Johnstone et al., 2001	17.9
Pearlmutter et al., 2007	77.3	Buchanan & Honey, 1994	73.3	Troy et al., 2003	17.3
Huberman & Pearlmutter, 2008	66.6	Buchanan & Honey, 1994	84.2	Troy et al., 2003	13.3
Huberman & Pearlmutter, 2008	54.2	Pullen, 1996	19.1	Troy et al., 2003	18.9
Huberman & Pearlmutter, 2008	57.0	Pullen, 1996	32.7	Troy et al., 2003	18.1
Huberman & Pearlmutter, 2008	53.4	Pullen, 1996	37.2	Troy et al., 2003	16.7
Huberman & Pearlmutter, 2008	53.4	Pullen, 1996	32.3	Troy et al., 2003	74.1
Huberman & Pearlmutter, 2008	57.6	Pullen, 1996	29.4	Troy et al., 2003	16.9
Utama & Gheewala, 2008	14.2	Pullen, 1996	47.6	Troy et al., 2003	14.4
Utama & Gheewala, 2008	7.7	Pullen, 1996	87.4	Mithraratne & Vale, 2004	26.0
Utama & Gheewala, 2009	16.5	Pullen, 1996	40.7	Mithraratne & Vale, 2004	29.3
Utama & Gheewala, 2009	31.4	Pullen, 1996	31.1	Mithraratne & Vale, 2004	42.6
Chel & Tiwari, 2009	12.2	Pullen, 1996	27.0	Duell & Martin, 2005	66.7
Barnes & Rankin, 1975	10.7	Pullen, 1996	42.3	Duell & Martin, 2005	69.3
Barnes & Rankin, 1975	7.7	Pullen, 1996	46.7	Duell & Martin, 2005	71.2
Barnes & Rankin, 1975	29.0	Pullen, 1996	40.7	Duell & Martin, 2005	66.7
Barnes & Rankin, 1975	25.4	Pullen, 1996	33.3	Duell & Martin, 2005	69.3
Fossdal & Edwardson, 1995	4.9	Pullen, 1996	55.2	Duell & Martin, 2005	71.5
Fossdal & Edwardson, 1995	3.6	Jaques, 1996	6.2	Page, 2006	21.2
Feist, 1996	53.7	Jaques, 1996	38.6	Page, 2006	20.3
Feist, 1996	31.5	Fay & Treloar, 1998	100.0	Page, 2006	28.4
Feist, 1996	17.3	Fay & Treloar, 1998	38.4	Page, 2006	7.8
Kohler et al., 1997b	16.2	Fay & Treloar, 1998	30.6	Page, 2006	6.3
Adalberth, 1997b	17.1	Fay & Treloar, 1998	27.4	Page, 2006	8.6
Adalberth, 1997b	15.8	Fay & Treloar, 1998	25.1	Randolph et al., 2006	37.5
Adalberth, 1997b	15.6	Fay & Treloar, 1998	100.0	Randolph et al., 2006	35.9
Winther & Hestnes, 1999	28.3	Fay & Treloar, 1998	42.2	Randolph et al., 2006	38.2
Winther & Hestnes, 1999	11.3	Fay & Treloar, 1998	33.6	Randolph et al., 2006	34.4
Winther & Hestnes, 1999	7.7	Fay & Treloar, 1998	30.0	Randolph et al., 2006	44.9
Winther & Hestnes, 1999	5.1	Fay & Treloar, 1998	27.4	Randolph et al., 2006	49.7
Winther & Hestnes, 1999	8.8	Pullen, 2000a	22.4	Randolph et al., 2006	44.3
Thormark, 2002	49.6	Pullen, 2000a	29.1	Randolph et al., 2006	50.3
Thormark, 2002	39.8	Pullen, 2000a	16.7	Randolph et al., 2006	40.3
Thormark, 2002	38.4	Pullen, 2000a	21.3	Randolph et al., 2006	32.6
Citherlet & Hand, 2002	27.6	Pullen, 2000a	29.7	Randolph et al., 2006	50.5
Citherlet & Hand, 2002	31.9	Pullen, 2000a	31.9	Randolph et al., 2006	53.7
Almeida et al., 2005	29.9	Pullen, 2000a	24.3	Langston & Langston, 2007	20.5
Almeida et al., 2005	40.1	Pullen, 2000a	15.0	Langston & Langston, 2007	19.9
Almeida et al., 2005	41.5	Pullen, 2000a	31.3	Langston & Langston, 2007	21.4

FIGURE A.5: Continued, description of referred case studies and percentage of embodied energy in the total LCE. Adapted from (Manish Kumar, 2013).

Appendix B

Dynamo Scripts and Dynamo Player

FIGURE B.1: Dynamo script concept.

FIGURE B.3: Dynamo script 3 exporting the results for one glazing pane element of the façade for the project Main Gate East.

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